

University of the West of Scotland

Doctoral Thesis

**Securing Guest Kernels and Enhancing
Host Resource Utilization in Cloud
Computing Systems**

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*A thesis submitted in fulfillment of the requirements
for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy*

in the

School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Fernando Vano-Garcia, declare that this thesis titled, “Securing Guest Kernels and Enhancing Host Resource Utilization in Cloud Computing Systems” has been composed by myself. I also declare that the work has not been submitted for a DBA, DProf, EngD or PhD or comparable academic award. This research is done wholly while in candidature for a research degree at this University. I confirm that the work submitted is the production of myself and my supervisor, and when the work of others has been referred to, appropriate credit has been given.

All the research presented in this thesis have been subjected to a rigorous peer-review process and published in different international top conferences and academic journals.

The work presented in Chapter 4 has been published in The Twelfth International Conference on Mobile Ubiquitous Computing, Systems, Services and Technologies as *Slicedup: A Tenant-Aware Memory Deduplication for Cloud Computing*.

The work presented in Chapter 5 has been published in two progressive papers. The problem described in this chapter was first stated and briefly analyzed in a short paper in the IEEE 17th International Symposium on Network Computing and Applications (NCA) as *How Kernel Randomization is Canceling Memory Deduplication in Cloud Computing Systems*. Later, the work was extended with a comprehensive analysis of the problem, providing a solution and a proper evaluation of its implementation in the Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing (JPDC) as *KASLR-MT: Kernel Address Space Layout Randomization for Multi-Tenant Cloud Systems*.

The work presented in Chapter 6 is under review at the time of writing this declaration.

Finally, the work presented in Chapter 7 has been published in IEEE Access as *E-BOOT: Preventing Boot-Time Entropy Starvation in Cloud Systems*.

Fernando Vano-Garcia

“I have approximate answers and possible beliefs and different degrees of uncertainty about different things, but I am not absolutely sure of anything and there are many things I don't know anything about.”

Richard P. Feynman

For you, Jose Miguel, for being the light that brought me here.

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UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

Abstract

School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences

Doctor of Philosophy

Securing Guest Kernels and Enhancing Host Resource Utilization in Cloud Computing Systems

by Fernando Vano-Garcia

Cloud computing has completely changed our lives. This technology is one of the building blocks of our modern society and it dramatically impacted on how we play, work and live. It has been widely adopted in many sectors mainly because it reduces the cost of performing tasks in a flexible, scalable and reliable way.

However, all of these benefits also come with threats. Since this technology is core for our society, it is also a very rewarding target for attackers and therefore it is imperative to have secure cloud systems.

To offer secure cloud services, vendors and providers must safeguard their infrastructure with up-to-date defenses and countermeasures to ensure the provision of high levels of protection, enabling users and consumers to enjoy their services as securely as possible. Unfortunately, the application of certain security mechanisms at infrastructure level can lead to the reduction of the efficient use of hardware resources, such as inefficient memory utilization. Therefore, in some cases security mechanisms cannot be easily combined with other optimization mechanisms and techniques used to obtain more profit of the existing resources. When this occurs, providers are forced to undertake actions that impact performance and to use their resources inefficiently in order to keep security [1–3]. In other cases, priority is given to resource optimization, thereby compromising security [4–6].

This thesis makes contributions to overcome existing barriers that prevent the secure and efficient utilization of memory resources in cloud environments.

Memory deduplication is an important memory saving technique particularly desired in cloud environments because it is capable of reducing memory footprint across virtual machines. Unfortunately, it is known that it can introduce security problems through side channels. To overcome this problem and to enable the use of the memory saving technique, we propose Slicedup, a memory deduplication design that prevents side-channel attacks in multi-tenant cloud systems. As described in Chapter 4, Slicedup allows cloud providers to secure the use of memory deduplication, increasing the profit of existing memory resources and decreasing the total cost of managing and ownership.

Kernel randomization is an essential and widely used security technique that consists in placing kernel memory regions at random locations to hinder the successful exploitation of

vulnerabilities that rely on knowing valid addresses. Unfortunately, its use in cloud environments produces alterations in memory contents, leading to a breakage of memory sharing and, consequently, to a higher memory consumption. In Chapter 5, after analyzing the problem and its causes in detail, we propose KASLR-MT, a new kernel randomization design for multi-tenant cloud systems compatible with memory deduplication that maximizes memory savings rate while providing a strong security. Afterwards, Chapter 6 presents the evolution and the next steps of this security technique, and we extend the effectiveness of KASLR-MT to include support for a finer granularity to include protection against info-leaks.

Concerning the security of important components of the kernel, the availability of high quality entropy is critical and necessary to ensure that such security mechanisms operate correctly and without any weakness that could compromise their effectiveness. Unfortunately, it is unfeasible to generate true randomness by running deterministic algorithms in computers. As a consequence, obtaining high quality entropy is still a challenge, specially at boot time. In Chapter 7, after analyzing the boot-time entropy starvation problem, we propose E-Boot, a novel technique that provides high-quality random numbers to guest virtual machines, being the first technique that completely satisfies the entropy demand of virtualized boot-loaders and operating systems at boot time.

As a result of this research, we provide important advantages to the efficiency of environments based on virtualization technologies such as multi-tenant cloud computing systems, which are the foundation of most of the services we currently use on a daily basis and for which we strongly depend.

Keywords: IaaS, Cloud, Virtualization, Security, Operating Systems, Memory Management

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List of Abbreviations/Acronyms

ABI	A pplication B inary I nterface
AES	A dvanced E ncryption S tandard
API	A pplication P rogramming I nterface
ASLR	A ddress S pace L ayout R andomization
BIOS	B asic I nput/ O utput S ystem
BPF	B erkeley P acket F ilter
CCCMD	C loud C overt C hannel based on M emory D eduplication
COW	C opy O n W rite
CPU	C entral P rocessing U nit
CSPRNG	C ryptographically S ecure P seudo R andom N umber G enerator
DAD	D uplicate A ddress D etection
DEP	D ata E xecution P revention
DRAM	D ynamic R andom- A ccess M emory
ECDSA	E lliptic C urve D igital S ignature A lgorithm
EFI	E xtensible F irmware I nterface
EGD	E ntropy G athering D aemon
ELF	E xecutable and L inkable F ormat
ESP	E FI S ystem P artition
FFS	F lip F eng S hui
FWH	F irmware H ub
FaaS	F unction a s a S ervice
GCC	G NU C ompiler C ollection
GCM	G alois/ C ounter M ode
GNU	G NU's N ot U nix!
GOT	G lobal O ffset T able
HAVEGE	H ARdware V olatile E ntropy G athering and E xpansion
HID	H uman I nterface D evelopments
HRNG	H ardware R andom N umber G enerator
HTTPS	H ypertext T ransfer P rotocol S ecure
IP	I nternet P rotocol
IaaS	I nfrastucture a s a S ervice
ISA	I nstruction S et A rchitecture
KASLR	K ernel A ddress S pace L ayout R andomization
KDF	K ey D erivation F unction
KSM	K ernel S amepage M erging
KVM	K ernel-based V irtual M achine
LFSR	L inear- F eedback S hift R egister
LLC	L ast- L evel- C ache
LTS	L ong T erm S upport
LXDE	L ightweight X 11 D esktop E nvironment

MT	M ulti- T enant
NAT	N etwork A ddress T ranslation
NIST	N ational I nstitute of S tandards and T echnology
NX	N o E xecute
OS	O perating S ystem
PIC	P osition I ndependent C ode
PLT	P rocedure L inkage T able
PRNG	P seudo R andom N umber G enerator
PTE	P age T able E ntry
PaaS	P latform a s a S ervice
RFC	R equest F or C omments
RNG	R andom N umber G enerator
ROP	R eturn- O riented P rogramming
SDRAM	S ynchronous D ynamic R andom- A ccess M emory
SHA	S ecure H ash A lgorithms
SIV	S ynthetic I nitialization V ector
SRAM	S tatic R andom A ccess M emory
SSH	S ecure S hell
STS	S tatistical T est S uite
SaaS	S oftware a s a S ervice
TCB	T rusted C omputing B ase
TCP	T ransmission C ontrol P rotocol
TLB	T ranslation L ookaside B uffer
TLS	T ransport L ayer S ecurity
TPM	T rusted P latform M odule
TPS	T ransparent P age S haring
TRNG	T rue R andom N umber G enerator
TSX	T ransactional S ynchronization E xtensions
UEFI	U nified E xtensible F irmware I nterface
USB	U niversal S erial B us
UUID	U niversally U nique I dentifier
VMM	V irtual M achine M onitor
VM	V irtual M achine

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Cloud computing has undeniably transformed our society and the way we interact with the world and with people. Over the last decade, it has been gradually established as the *de-facto* model, evolving and offering new possibilities for both academia and industry. In our daily life, cloud services are vastly used for many different needs such as doing business, staying informed, doing the shopping, socializing, entertaining and many others. The utilization of this kind of services is continuously growing, as well as its revenue [7].

The cloud paradigm provides unbounded computing resources on-demand, reducing costs due to *economies of scale* [8]. Customers can benefit from vast computing power and storage capabilities of large data centers following a pay-as-you-go model, without the need to possess the necessary hardware resources. Virtualization technologies are one of the fundamental building blocks of cloud computing. Resources utilization can be maximized along with a flexible and efficient on-demand workload multiplexing, yielding to potentially energy efficient infrastructures [9] by aggregating the users demands.

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) [10] is considered one of the fundamental building blocks for cloud services because, at this level, users are able to configure virtualized environments with high flexibility without the concern of deploying large rooms of physical computers. Hence, service providers supply storage, networking and virtualization so that users have full control over the system from Operating System (OS) layer upwards. Efficient resource management is fundamental to deal with a proper cloud infrastructure [11–13]. Hardware resources are a critical asset in the business, and they must be managed and utilized adequately. Cloud service providers will obtain more benefits if they are able to operate more virtual machines with the same resources [14, 15]. Furthermore, there is a stack of services relying on IaaS, for example *Platform as a Service* (PaaS), *Software as a Service* (SaaS) or *Function as a Service* (FaaS) to name a few. Any security issue affecting the base layer will also affect the upper ones.

Nowadays, new cloud paradigms and virtualization technologies have emerged due to the compelling tendency to shift to a finer granularity, with the aim of increasing the ability to dynamically scale resource utilization and maximally exploit the infrastructure resources. Serverless computing [16, 17] is an example of cloud computing model that has recently reached a relevant situation in its development. In contrast to IaaS, where the provider supplies storage, networking and virtualization so that the client has full control over the system from OS layer upwards, the serverless computing model enables dynamic resource allocation,

leaving the scaling of infrastructure requirements to the provider. This approach avoids over-provisioning of resources, eventually decreasing effective costs.

This is important because, given the significance that cloud computing has in people's lives, it is imperative to offer security standards to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability in all cloud computing architectures. Cloud providers must ensure the highest possible level of security in order to prevent attacks and to guarantee a suitable quality to their users.

Since the finding of the first computer bug back in 1947 [18], the cybersecurity landscape has been changing swiftly. Attackers are aware of the fact that computers are the building blocks of our society. For this reason, bugs with security implications are being abused in order to make profit of those vulnerabilities. Given the asymmetric nature of the confrontation between attackers and defenders, the former enjoy their tactical advantage, while the latter design and develop defense mechanisms to prevent the successful exploitation of the most complex attacks.

Besides, the complexity of the attacks increases as more defense mechanisms are introduced. During the past decade, the development of userland security countermeasures against the exploitation of different vulnerabilities has gained considerable weight. Some of these mitigations used for protecting userland programs have their kernel-level version (e.g., address randomization), but in general it is relatively more constraint to implement them for the kernel [19]. In addition, the deployment of different sandboxing technologies motivates attackers to target the kernel to get a stronger control of the whole system. As a consequence, there has been a transition in the *battlefield* from userland to kernel because the complexity of userland exploits has overtaken the kernel ones [20].

Unfortunately, although cloud infrastructure providers desire to offer as much security as possible for their services while maximizing the exploitation of their resources, having both at the same time is not always possible. Current security mechanisms are far from perfect and, in many cases, they introduce cost-prohibitive overheads. For example, as described in chapters 5 and 6 of this thesis, we have identified important cases in which critical security mechanisms such as kernel randomization can increase the memory consumption in the presence of optimization mechanisms such as memory deduplication. In these cases, some providers may prefer to sacrifice the security of their users if they consider that the cost of implementing certain security mechanisms is too costly for them.

It is extremely important to conduct research on defense mechanisms to prevent and/or mitigate as far as possible the extent of known attacks. Similarly, it is equally important to research on the efficient exploitation of resources, especially if the essential security mechanisms have a high cost of either performance or memory use. Otherwise, due to the inherent *invisibility* of security (i.e., it might seem futile while everything is fine, until a disaster occurs), a high cost for deploying protection techniques leads to the risk that such techniques are never deployed, causing advantageous scenarios for attackers. In the present context, in which our society is highly dependent on these technologies, this is potentially catastrophic. This thesis is focused on addressing these challenges and provide solutions to improve security while reducing costs to make it more affordable.

1.2 Thesis Aim & Objectives

The continuous reporting of diverse vulnerabilities and data breaches in many different sectors along with the ever-increasing investment in cloud-based security over the past few years [21–23] is a strong indicator that security in these environments is fundamental [24]. On the other hand, the optimization of existing applications and mechanisms for their use in cloud environments to reduce their overhead (cost savings) is one of the top cloud strategies [25]. This is mainly because many of them are not designed for cloud environments, where the sharing of resources is one of the bases on which this model is established. It is particularly important for cloud infrastructure providers to be able to exploit their available resources efficiently and without having to sacrifice security.

Therefore, the starting premise for this thesis is that security mechanisms generally have an associated cost, either in terms of performance or in terms of resource utilization. On this basis, the **aim** of this thesis is to advance the knowledge in the field of security mechanisms in cloud systems to strengthen kernel hardening techniques and security mechanisms to reduce their associated cost (premise) by achieving a better understanding about how these mechanisms interact with the rest of the system and how they influence and affect the optimal exploitation of available resources in computing systems.

To accomplish this aim, we focus on randomization-based security mechanisms and the efficient exploitation of memory resources, and define the following specific objectives:

1. **To enable a secure and effective utilization of optimization techniques for maximizing the exploitation of memory resources in cloud environments.** Since memory resources are a valuable asset in cloud environments, *Memory Deduplication* is an important optimization mechanism. In our research, we focus on analysing the challenges and concerns of this technique to identify the causes that discourage its usage and to design solutions that allow its secure and effective adoption in cloud systems, enabling providers to maximize their benefits. We conduct a brief survey of different side-channel attacks that rely on sharing memory, and we provide a design solution that allows cloud infrastructure providers to use memory deduplication securely.
2. **To reduce costs in terms of memory utilization of security mechanisms, to improve the efficiency of optimization techniques to maximize the exploitation of memory resources in cloud environments without compromising the security.** *Kernel Randomization* is an important kernel security mechanism widely used by major operating systems that provides protection against unknown attacks. In cloud environments, the entropy derived from the application of *Kernel Randomization* impacts the efficiency of *Memory Deduplication*, leading to an exceeding memory consumption and consequently reducing the providers' profit. In our research, we focus on identifying the causes of this phenomenon, quantifying this cost and providing a cost-effective solution that avoids the overuse of memory resources while maintaining equivalent levels of security. To achieve this, we study, analyze and quantify the impact that kernel randomization has on memory deduplication in the Linux kernel, and then we provide a solution that eliminates the memory usage overhead without sacrificing the security of this important defense mechanism. This is done for both current kernel randomization versions and future upgrades, providing the solution not only for the present but also for when new problems arise in the near future.

3. **To strengthen kernel hardening techniques and boost the kernel boot speed by ensuring the supply and availability of high-quality entropy from the very beginning of the boot process.** The availability of high-quality entropy is critical to ensure proper security levels, especially for long-term protection mechanisms initialized at early phases of the kernel boot. Given the nature of deterministic machines, obtaining randomness in early boot environments is challenging and can lead to boot time delays and hangups. In our research, we focus on solving this challenge and providing methods and techniques to supply the necessary randomness to guest kernels in cloud environments. We survey the state-of-the-art entropy sources and thoroughly analyze the Linux kernel boot process to identify and quantify the problem and all the affected components. Afterwards, a solution is proposed to improve the entropy availability of all current solutions, providing high-quality entropy from the very first moments of the boot process and solving the boot-time entropy starvation problem with a negligible overhead.

1.3 Research Contributions

Throughout the development of our research, we have worked in different ways seeking to address the established objectives. The following bullet points describe how the research objectives proposed for this thesis have been accomplished:

- Recent research literature shows that the wide memory sharing between virtual machines in cloud environments through the use of the memory deduplication optimization mechanism enables the appearance of side channels that can cause isolation breakage and therefore the violation of the confidentiality of the data of third-party users of the cloud. In this direction, after reviewing the state-of-the-art side-channel techniques related to memory deduplication in cloud systems, we propose a suitable solution to enable bounded memory deduplication in host machines of multi-tenant cloud systems, preventing side-channel attacks between trusty guest virtual machines belonging to the same tenant and thus enabling a more efficient use of memory resources, which are extremely important for cloud providers. With it, different tenants can enable a safe memory sharing by deduplication among their own virtual machines, even if they co-reside in the same host.
- We have analyzed in depth the effects produced in the memory of the host machine when the kernel randomization security mechanism is employed in guest kernels, identifying the causes for which memory deduplication undergoes the cancellation of shared memory. We have also studied the problem for the specific case of Linux, revealing in detail the effects produced by each randomized kernel address/component on each of the kernel memory regions. Such research has been carried out for both standard coarse-grained and novel fine-grained kernel randomization approaches.
- From the knowledge extracted from our previous contributions, we propose a novel kernel randomization design for multi-tenant cloud systems that is compatible with memory deduplication, maximizing memory savings by deduplication while providing a strong security. Based on the analysis performed for the Linux kernel, we implement and evaluate our solution for Linux. Our results showed that the design is not intrusive, highly scalable and capable of providing an effective combination of memory resources exploitation and security. We demonstrate the high scalability and flexibility of the

design by extending its functionality to include support for the function-granular kernel randomization approach.

- To strengthen kernel hardening techniques and boost the kernel boot speed, we address the challenge of obtaining high-quality entropy at boot-time. We perform a comprehensive chronological analysis of the Linux kernel boot process, discovering that several kernel components initialized at early stages require randomness under entropy starvation conditions. Then, we propose a novel technique that solves the boot-time entropy starvation problem by providing high-quality random numbers to guest virtual machines. The proposed solution is the first approach that completely satisfies the entropy demand of virtualized boot-loaders and operating systems at the early steps of the boot time process. We also implement and evaluate our solution for Linux, proving its effectiveness and negligible overhead.
- The Linux operating system is widely used, especially in cloud environments. Throughout our research, exploiting its open source nature, the Linux kernel is utilized to study the problems and to implement and evaluate the proposed solutions. In this sense, we also contribute to the Linux project, providing the patches corresponding to the proposed solutions. Additionally, we have found a bug and a potential vulnerability in the implementation of the kernel randomization security mechanism. Under some circumstances, the bug causes an overlapping of two kernel memory regions due to incorrect calculation of boundaries and sizes. As a result, privileged memory can be overwritten, being the first step in developing an attack able to control a system.

1.4 Outcomes

Academic Publications

Title: Slicedup: A Tenant-Aware Memory Deduplication for Cloud Computing

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: Conference Paper – CORE index: C

Publisher: The Twelfth International Conference on Mobile Ubiquitous Computing, Systems, Services and Technologies (UBICOMM).

Article ID: [ubicomm_2018_1_30_10065](#)

Title: How Kernel Randomization is Canceling Memory Deduplication in Cloud Computing Systems

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: Conference Paper – CORE index: A

Publisher: 2018 IEEE 17th International Symposium on Network Computing and Applications (NCA)

Article ID: [10.1109/NCA.2018.8548338](#)

Continued on next page...

Academic Publications

(Continued)

Title: KASLR-MT: Kernel Address Space Layout Randomization for Multi-Tenant Cloud Systems

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: JCR Q2 Journal Article – Impact Factor: 1.819

Publisher: Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing (JPDC)

Article ID: 10.1016/j.jpdc.2019.11.008

Title: E-BOOT: Preventing Boot-Time Entropy Starvation in Cloud Systems

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: JCR Q1 Journal Article – Impact Factor: 4.098

Publisher: IEEE Access

Article ID: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2984414

Title: An Info-Leak Resistant Kernel Randomization for Virtualized Systems

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: JCR Q1 Journal Article – Impact Factor: 4.098

Publisher: IEEE Access

Article ID: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3019774

Software Tools

Title: Dedupdiff

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: Tool to compare different memory dumps and generate deduplication stats, specially designed to analyze the differences and effects produced by the randomization of the contents location. The features include graphic representation of the memory contents indicating differences and similarities and the calculation of different metrics such as redundancy, shareability (with and without local redundancy) and overhead.

Title: Kaslr-Dedup Test Suite

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: Test suite for analysing the influence of kernel randomization on memory deduplication. Includes concurrent execution of virtual machines and memory dumps extraction with support for compression/decompression, error detection and automatic retry of failed tests. It uses QEMU as a backend VMM, allowing paravirtualization techniques to be integrated for customized and flexible analysis of guest virtual machines.

Contributions to the Linux Kernel

Title: KASLR Bug Fix

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: While checking the Linux kernel source code to study how its particular kernel randomization implementation operates, we discovered a bug in the calculation of the sizes and boundaries of the randomized kernel memory regions. The kernel does not check these boundaries correctly and thus creates a plausible overlap of two kernel memory regions. We have proposed a patch that fixes the error so that the limits are calculated correctly without causing any overlap.

URL: <https://fervagar.com/bugs/kaslr-20>

Title: KASLR-MT patch

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: Patch with the implementation of KASLR-MT for Linux. This implementation is discussed in detail in chapter 5.7.

URL: <https://fervagar.com/links/kaslr-mt>

Title: E-Boot patch

Authors: [Fernando Vano-Garcia](#) and Hector Marco-Gisbert

Description: Patch with the implementation of E-Boot for Linux. This implementation is discussed in detail in chapter 7.8.

URL: <https://fervagar.com/links/e-boot>

1.5 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is divided into 7 chapters. Each chapter is a self-contained module aligned with the fulfillment of the objectives mentioned in section 1.2. The following list briefly describes the structure of the thesis through the main points of each chapter:

- Chapter 1 introduces the thesis, stating the motivation and later describing the objectives, contributions and outcomes produced from the research.
- Chapter 2 contains a brief and concise introduction to the basic concepts and background knowledge necessary to understand the research work presented in the subsequent chapters. The concepts presented are virtualization, memory deduplication, pseudo-random number generators and address space layout randomization. Finally, we provide a quick discussion about two ways of randomize code. All these concepts will be present throughout the thesis. Chapters 4 and 7 provide their own background section as the concepts presented therein concern only that specific chapter.
- Chapter 4 provides a state-of-the-art review of the known side-channel techniques related to memory deduplication in cloud systems. Then, we propose and discuss a suitable solution to enable memory deduplication in multi-tenant clouds preventing side-channel attacks.

- Chapter 5 exposes the problem of kernel randomization breaking memory sharing by deduplication. We examine the reasons that cause it and the derived consequences, and perform a comprehensive analysis of the impact of kernel randomization on memory deduplication. Then, based on the results of this analysis, we propose KASLR-MT, a kernel randomization design that keeps strong security levels while significantly reduces the impact of memory deduplication cancellation. Finally, we implement the proposed solution in the Linux kernel and evaluate its effectiveness and security.
- Chapter 6 describes that the problem exposed in chapter 5 and fixed by KASLR-MT re-emerges with the appearance of new kernel randomization approaches that arise from the need to extend protection against info-leak attacks. In this chapter, we prove that the previous KASLR-MT design is not enough when the randomization is of a finer granularity and needs to be fixed to face these new challenges. To address this, we re-analyze in depth the impact of these new approaches to provide a solution to this new problem.
- Chapter 7 discusses the process of random number generation in computers, along with an exhaustive investigation of the main entropy sources and entropy collection techniques. The problem of boot-time entropy starvation is described, examining the reasons that cause it and the derived consequences. Then, we present a comprehensive chronological analysis of the Linux kernel boot process with all the components requesting random data during the boot-time, identifying the cases in which there is insufficient quality entropy available when these requests are made. To solve the boot-time starvation problem, we propose E-Boot, a practical solution that provides high-quality entropy to virtual machines in cloud systems at early stages of the boot process. Finally, we implement the proposed solution in the Linux kernel and evaluate its effectiveness and overhead.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Virtualization

Virtualization is a technology that enables the creation of one or more virtual instances of a machine or computing system within a real physical machine. It offers the possibility of optimising the exploitation of the physical machine's resources. For example, instead of having two dedicated physical machines each one running a service that uses 50% of the resources, virtualization allows us to create two virtual instances of those machines and run them on a single physical machine, maximizing the efficiency of the resources. In fact, virtualization is one of the core technologies that cloud systems rely on.

The hypervisor monitors and supervises the use that the guest virtual machines make of the host's resources. It acts as an arbiter and intermediary between the hardware and the virtual machines, which allows a flexible resource allocation and the support of security measures to guarantee the isolation of the virtual machines. In some contexts it is also known as Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM). There are two commonly distinguished types of hypervisors, depending on whether they are standalone or integrated within an OS. Therefore, type 1 hypervisors run directly on the hardware, while type 2 hypervisors are part of an OS. Naturally, each approach has its advantages and disadvantages. For example, type 2 approaches are easier to deploy since they can leverage existing hardware support and mechanisms in the memory manager component of the host operating system, while type 1 can be smaller, more cost-efficient and can potentially reduce the size of the Trusted Computing Base (TCB) thus reducing the attack surface.

In the context of computer architectures, it is also typically distinguished between virtualizable and non-virtualizable architectures. Gerald J. Popek and Robert P. Goldberg defined in 1974 the so-called *Popek and Goldberg virtualization theorem* [26], which specify the conditions that a certain computer architecture needs to fulfill to support virtualization efficiently. Despite its relative antiquity, this theorem is still relevant nowadays. Accordingly, virtualizable architectures are those that support virtualization throughout its instruction set architecture (ISA), allowing the use of *trap-and-emulate* hypervisors that execute most of the virtual machine instructions directly on the real processor.

There are different virtualization techniques [27, 28] that have been evolving throughout the last decades along with the increasing popularity and the progressive maturation of this technology. In this regard, the term full virtualization indicates that the guest can be completely decoupled from the hardware so that it is unaware that it is being virtualized. An early strategy for achieving full virtualization is binary translation, which translates kernel code to replace non-virtualizable

instructions to achieve trap-and-emulate functionality. Another common technique is para-virtualization, whereby the guest OS is modified to replace the non-virtualizable instructions with interruptions to the hypervisor (hypercalls). Besides these techniques, most modern architectures include hardware-assisted virtualization support, providing dedicated machine instructions and new CPU execution modes that allow the hypervisor to operate in a new root mode below *ring-0* [29–31].

2.2 Memory Deduplication

Memory deduplication is a memory saving technique that tries to identify identical chunks of physical memory and merge them into a single copy, freeing the redundant duplicates for a more efficient use of memory. Given the noteworthy importance of efficient memory resource utilization for cloud computing providers, memory deduplication is a desired feature. It is able to reduce the memory footprint across virtual machines [32, 33], increasing the profit of existing memory resources and decreasing the total cost of managing and ownership.

When memory deduplication is used with virtualization technologies, it is usually operating at the hypervisor layer, along with the memory manager of the physical host machine. In these environments, the amount of redundant memory will depend mostly on the memory contents that the virtual machines produce. If the different virtual machines use the same or similar operating systems, many redundant memory will be generated on the host machine. The same applies if the workload of the virtual machines in userspace is similar and likely to find identical memory blocks among them.

In almost all modern operating systems, the whole memory is organized and divided in memory blocks, known as pages [34]. Typically, each memory page consumes 4096 bytes of physical memory. This strategy facilitates an efficient management of the physical memory resources and enables virtual memory, which is a fundamental feature for virtualization. Thanks to this memory organization, memory deduplication can merge all pages with identical content into a single copy. Note that swapped pages can not be deduplicated but only the ones that reside in physical memory.

Different architectures support different page sizes [35]. The determination of the page size is architectural and entails a trade-off between distinct advantages and disadvantages. A greater page size implies less page table entries and less Translation Lookaside Buffer (TLB) faults, resulting in higher runtime performance [36]. However, large page size can produce internal fragmentation and reduce the memory savings rate [37] due to fewer chances of finding two pages with equal content. Thanks to the memory management virtualization support, it is possible for hypervisors to implement memory deduplication using pages of 4096 bytes, independently of the page size of the guest view. For example, although a Linux kernel guest uses 2 MiB pages, the host can divide the guest's memory into 4 KiB pages.

Memory pages are compared in pairs. There are several implementation techniques used to speed up the comparison process. For example, VMware's Content-Based Page Sharing uses hashing to identify pages with potentially-identical contents [38]. However, at least one bit-to-bit comparison must be performed before merging two identical pages into one single copy in physical memory. Otherwise, a possible hash collision could lead to serious weaknesses.

The merging operation is typically achieved by mapping the identical pages into a single entry in the page tables, along with the usage of the Copy-On-Write (COW) mechanism [39]. The

COW mechanism allows a memory manager to share an object among processes belonging to different virtual address spaces. It is an optimization heavily used by operating systems for copy operations, for example when a new process is created. A *COWed* object is write-protected and when any of the processes tries to modify its own instance a new copy is generated to ensure the integrity of the contents.

2.3 Pseudo-Random Number Generators

Without random numbers, many applications would fail and security could not be provided. In cryptography, random numbers are needed to generate private and public keys, initialization vectors, challenges, salts in password hashes, etc. In science, random numbers are used for several different applications, for example for running complex simulations using Monte Carlo methods [40] and randomized controlled trials [41].

Digital computers are deterministic physical machines and it is not possible to produce true random numbers from a finite state machine [42]. A Pseudo-Random Number Generator (PRNG) is a deterministic algorithm capable of generating large sequences of numbers derived from an initial state (or seed). The output of a PRNG has similar properties to real random numbers, and it will look random for anyone who does not know the initial state. However, it is possible to reconstruct the exact sequence of numbers produced by a PRNG knowing its initial seed or internal state. This is a desired property in some cases. For example, it allows the reproducibility of experiments and simulations by only providing the initial seed value. Contrarily, it can be fatal in the context of cryptography, since it would allow attackers to easily bypass any security provided by secret keys.

For cryptographic functions demanding high quality random numbers to generate secret keying material, regular PRNGs are insufficient. A Cryptographically Secure Pseudo-Random Number Generator (CSPRNG) is a sub-class of PRNG with more restrictive properties, including high-complexity for 1) reversing the internal state from a given output, 2) predicting past and future outputs from a given output, and 3) the ability to feed it without compromising its correct operation. To have all those properties, it is fundamental to seed the CSPRNG with high-entropy random data. Otherwise, an attacker knowing the initial state of a particular generator will be able to predict the entire output sequence. A secure seed can be obtained from the output of another CSPRNG, from non-deterministic physical processes or from unpredictable events [43–48]. Once it is initialized with a high-entropy seed, it can be used to reliably obtain large sequences of artificial random numbers from a few true random bits. Random numbers generated by a properly seeded CSPRNG are considered computationally secure.

2.4 Address Space Layout Randomization

Address Space Layout Randomization (ASLR) [49] is a security technique that consists in placing the memory regions of a program at random locations. The objective of this technique is to hinder the successful exploitation of vulnerabilities that rely on knowing program addresses [50, 51]. An attacker must obtain valid addresses where code or data is located in memory to trigger a malicious payload [52–54]. This is in part because the *Data Execution Prevention / No-Execute* (DEP/NX) prevents execution of injected code.

ASLR has some requirements in order to be applied correctly. It needs a high-quality entropy source for generating cryptographically secure random numbers to determine the addresses where the program will be loaded [55, 56]. If this requirement is not fulfilled, the predictability of the generated addresses will be high and then it will be easier for an attacker to guess correctly a valid address [57, 58] and bypass ASLR.

Kernel ASLR (KASLR) or *kernel randomization* is the application of this technique to the kernel [59]. Similarly to userland programs, kernel memory regions are randomized to mitigate attacks that rely on knowing where the kernel is loaded. Even though the technique is applied to both kernel and userland, the application of this technique in kernel space has completely different implications and limitations than in userland so that, in practice, they are actually two different techniques. For example, the use of position-independent code (PIC) along with a Global Offset Table (GOT) permits to place a userland library on virtually any location without having to modify addresses in the code (e.g. jumps or data access) by using offsets relative to its position; but this approach is not always possible/desired for the kernel.

Furthermore, the randomization of kernel memory regions is done at boot-time and it cannot be changed until next reboot, which is much less frequent than restarting userland applications. This has significant direct implications such as the (in)ability to conduct aggressive brute force attacks against the kernel and the relevance of an info-leak to reveal kernel addresses. Since the randomization is only applied at boot time, any info-leak revealing an address pertaining to a particular kernel memory region will de-randomize that memory region, and the bypass will be effective until next reboot [60, 61].

2.5 Randomizing Code

In order to randomize code, the loader must be able to choose an arbitrary address and, then, load the code at that address. To achieve this, the code being randomized must be compiled and linked to allow loaders to put it at random memory locations [62]. There are mainly two different approaches to enable code to be randomized: Position-Independent Code (PIC) and relocations. Both approaches can load and run code at random virtual addresses, but they have implementation differences that have an impact on performance and shared memory.

Position-independent code is a piece of machine code that can be executed regardless of where it is loaded in memory without any code modification. This feature is crucial for shared libraries, to keep the code segment as non-writable and to allow memory sharing by several processes using the Copy-On-Write (COW) mechanism [39]. Instead of referencing symbols with absolute addresses, PIC uses indexed addressing using relative offsets. For example, a data variable can be referenced relatively using the program's instruction pointer if it is close enough. To efficiently access symbols and data beyond the addressable limits of an architecture, userland programs use a look-up table called Global Offset Table (GOT). This table is placed in a data segment, writable and private for each process, and contains absolute addresses of global exported symbols. Hence, PIC allows randomization of code memory regions without altering its contents.

On the other hand, relocatable code is a piece of machine code that can also be executed regardless of where it is loaded in memory, but the executable segment must be patched when it is loaded [63, 64]. Relocation information is consulted by the loader in order to adjust symbol references through different parts of the program with final absolute addresses. Although the final program with the absolute references can be more efficient than position-independent

code, the load time work of relocatable code is considerably heavier, as every reference in code must be fixed-up. In contrast to PIC, randomized relocatable code cannot be shared and therefore is not suitable for shared libraries. Relocations in code pages trigger the Copy-On-Write mechanism, generating private copies of these pages for each process using the same library loaded at different virtual addresses. The result is a decrement of memory sharing among processes, which is the main purpose of shared libraries.

Chapter 3

Literature Review

This chapter provides an overview of the literature on the main concepts studied throughout this thesis, with the aim of giving a picture of the state of knowledge regarding memory deduplication, kernel randomization and the boot-time entropy starvation problem.

The memory deduplication technique was pioneered in the Disco VMM [65]. An important limitation of the Disco's implementation was that it needed the active involvement of the guest operating system [38], which needed to be modified to enable the memory sharing functionality. Different techniques were used to achieve this such as hooking library routines and the use of special network interfaces to communicate with other virtual machines. This limitation was solved later on by VMware ESX Server with Content-Based Page Sharing [38], enabling the memory sharing based on memory contents and directly from the host machine. This solution provided the possibility to obtain the benefits of memory deduplication in a more flexible way and without needing to alter the guest operating system, allowing its use not only for para-virtualization but also for full-virtualization. It is noteworthy that this approach is suitable for both Type 1 and Type 2 hypervisors [66]. Afterwards, other hypervisors and VMMs also introduced this functionality to increase their memory sharing benefits, such as VirtualBox's Page Fusion [67] and Xen's Difference Engine [33]. In that article [33], Gupta et al. explored other approaches to memory sharing by deduplication, studying memory sharing at finer granularity and with lower memory usage rates using page patching and compression.

Although memory deduplication was initially designed to be used in virtual machine monitors and hypervisors [32, 38, 65, 68, 69], it was applied for memory contents of non-virtualized environments as well. Then, it was widely adopted by most of the operating systems. For example, the Linux kernel included Kernel Samepage Merging (KSM) in the version 2.6.32 [70] and Windows introduced Memory Page Combining in Windows 8 [71]. Furthermore, data deduplication is commonly used in other areas such as databases or web contents [72–74].

Chapter 4 discusses that although memory deduplication is a desired mechanism because of the memory sharing benefits that it offers [32, 33, 75–79], it introduces weaknesses in the form of covert channels and side-channel attacks. Various articles described the problem with different attacks and different outcomes, such as detecting the existence of specific software in other virtual machines [80], detecting specific/targeted virtual machines in multi-tenant cloud environments [81] and fingerprinting the victim's guest OS [82]. A more detailed revision of the state-of-the-art academic articles regarding side-channel attacks by abusing memory sharing in virtualized environments will be presented in Section 4.3 of Chapter 4. Slicedup is also proposed in Chapter 4 as a solution to this problem and discusses various existing countermeasures [81, 83–87], comparing them with the approach followed by our proposed solution.

After presenting Slicedup to enable the use of memory deduplication in multi-tenant cloud environments without having to sacrifice security, the next technology studied in this thesis is the kernel randomization security mechanism. The application of this defence mechanism to the kernel is relatively new, since it has been introduced in the main operating systems over the last decade approximately. For example, it introduced by Apple in Mac OS X Mountain Lion (Mac OS X 10.8) [88], by Microsoft in Windows Vista and by Linux in the kernel version 3.14. Throughout this period of time, the kernel randomization mechanism has been studied by security researchers with the aim of improving its security. Hence, it repeatedly attacked using different techniques to bypass its protection, disclosing randomized locations of the kernel. Among the techniques used to bypass KASLR are using the Intel's Transactional Synchronization Extensions (TSX) [61], abusing the processor's branch predictors [52], abusing modern tagged TLB architectures [89], and out-of-order execution [90]. Fortunately, each study demonstrating a certain attack provides its corresponding countermeasure, thus adding more complexity to the attackers' task.

However, kernel randomization introduces another problem which has not been thoroughly researched in the literature. The main problem is that the kernel randomization mechanism alters the memory contents, which directly interferes with the effectiveness of memory deduplication. Therefore, activating the kernel randomization security mechanism potentially leads to a loss of benefits in terms of memory sharing in virtualized environments. This problem is discussed in detail in chapters 5 and 6. As of the date of writing this thesis and to the best of the authors' knowledge, there is only one research work that studies the effects of address randomization on memory deduplication [1]. However, this article presents the problem from a broad perspective, without delving into the details of the problem and its causes, and without proposing an effective solution. This thesis explores the problem in depth and proposes KASLR-MT to enable cloud infrastructure providers to utilize the kernel randomization security mechanism with full compatibility with memory deduplication so that maximum benefits from memory sharing can be achieved without sacrificing security.

Finally, Chapter 7 addresses the boot-time entropy starvation and proposes E-Boot as a novel solution to ensure the supply and availability of high-quality entropy from the very beginning of the boot process, with the aim of strengthening kernel hardening techniques and boost the kernel boot speed. As with the problem discussed in the paragraph above, there is limited research in the literature studying the boot-time entropy starvation and proposing effective and efficient solutions. For example, Fernandes et al. [91] explore the issue of entropy starvation in virtualized systems, concluding that the entropy generation rate in virtual machines is very slow and that leads to large boot-time blocks. Everspaugh et al. [92] study the challenge of entropy generation in virtual machines and provide a solution to prevent the RNG of different VM snapshots from producing the same output. However, the article does not solve the boot-time entropy starvation. In other article, Vassilev and Staples [93] briefly outline the boot-time entropy starvation problem and propose an Internet service called Entropy as a Service, which provides a remote delivery of random numbers using the cloud model. As discussed in Section 7.4 of Chapter 7, this approach has its advantages and limitations, but unfortunately it cannot be used by boot-loaders, operating systems or any device that requires entropy at early boot stages because it requires the system to be completely booted in order to establish a remote connection to request entropy. Hence, E-Boot provides a novel and efficient solution that overcomes the boot-time entropy starvation problem for cloud environments and all kind of machines that rely on virtualization technologies.

Part I

A Secure Memory Deduplication For Cloud Systems

Chapter 4

Memory Deduplication and Cache Side-Channel Attacks

Memory deduplication allows cloud infrastructure providers to increase the profit of memory resources by taking advantage of the redundant nature of virtual machines' footprint.

Although it is an important feature to manage the memory resources of a cloud system efficiently, unfortunately, it enables different types of side-channel attacks which, in practice, means disabling memory deduplication.

In this chapter, we present Slicedup, a tenant-aware memory deduplication mechanism that prevents side-channel attacks. Our proposal enables cloud providers to get the deduplication saving benefits while preventing side-channel attacks among tenants.

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4.1 Introduction

Cloud computing has extraordinary importance in modern society. It is a computing paradigm that allows users to access external resources in an “on-demand” basis, without having to bear the costs of infrastructure maintenance (physical servers, electricity bills, etc.). Physical resources are owned and maintained by a third party (cloud infrastructure provider), and users can obtain the desired computing resources securely and flexibly [94]. It is commonly believed that the concept of cloud computing first appeared in the 90s [95]. Since then, its popularity has grown broadly. Nowadays, cloud computing has been widely adopted in many sectors (e.g., telecommunications, content providers, etc.), mainly because it reduces the cost of performing tasks in a scalable and reliable way.

Despite the effort of many researchers to provide protection mechanisms [96, 97], attackers always end up finding new techniques to achieve their goals. Cloud infrastructure providers desire efficient resource management as well as to provide adequate levels of security for their customers. Unfortunately, this is not always possible, and performance mechanisms can compromise the system security. Memory deduplication is an instance of this problem. In virtualized environments, deduplication is commonly applied to the entire guest memory region corresponding to the virtual machine (often called guest physical memory) [98]. Hence, those pages belonging to that memory region will be candidates for being shared across all virtual machines.

Applying memory deduplication to the guest physical memories of all the virtual machines running in the same host can increase the opportunities to find matching pages to share, and thus increase the benefits produced by this mechanism. However, this sharing in a multi-tenant cloud environment can lead to serious security issues, which could allow a malicious attacker to abuse it and compromise other customer’s highly sensitive information. For this reason, operating systems recently decided to deactivate memory deduplication by default [99, 100]. Other virtualization technologies such as VMware also recommend disabling memory deduplication to protect against side-channel attacks based on memory shared [2]. However, yielding to this problem by disabling deduplication can lead to significant losses of memory utilization.

In this chapter, we present the challenges of memory deduplication concerning security in cloud systems, first presenting a state-of-the-art survey of known problems that memory deduplication introduces in virtualized systems. Then, we propose a solution to allow memory deduplication in multi-tenant cloud systems protecting against external side channel attacks.

4.2 Background

4.2.1 Cache Memory

Cache memory is a small and high-speed Static Random Access Memory (SRAM) located in the Central Processing Unit (CPU), which stores recently accessed data from the main memory. The purpose is to speed up the access to program instructions and data, exploiting the principle of locality [101]. As a consequence, the processor can obtain the information directly from the cache, rather than from main memory, which has more access latency. Modern processors contain different levels of cache in their memory hierarchy, which typically consists of three cache levels where the first and second are private for each execution core and the last level is

shared by all the cores. The lower levels in the memory hierarchy contain smaller and faster memories, while the higher levels consist of bigger and slower memories.

There are different ways of organising a cache memory. The simpler approach is a direct-mapped cache, where an address is always associated with a single entry in the cache. This is cheap and works fast, but it introduces problems of address collisions (conflict miss). Another approach is a fully-associative cache, where any address can be stored in any entry of the cache. It is more expensive because a comparator is used to check the existing tags in the cache for every access, along with the need of an eviction policy (e.g., Least Recently Used). The n-way set associative caches are a combination of both approaches. The cache is divided into cache sets and each set consists of several cache lines (or ways). Sets are indexed with addresses to map specific memory locations (directly mapped), and the lines of each set are fully associative.

4.3 Threats of Memory Deduplication

Memory deduplication is a significant mechanism to save considerable amounts of memory in a cloud environment. The amount of redundant memory will depend on the memory contents that the virtual machines produce. Its memory sharing effectiveness has been empirically analyzed by several works [32, 33, 75–79]. For example, Chang et al [76] tested various kinds of workloads through extensive experiments, obtaining diverse results depending on the specific workload, from 11% to about 86% of memory saved.

Nevertheless, although memory deduplication is a desired mechanism by the potential benefits in terms of memory savings it can provide, it introduces weaknesses that can be exploited by malicious attackers and compromise the security of the system. It allows guests to communicate through a covert channel, which can be used by attackers to perform cross-VM access driven attacks and leak sensitive information. In this section, we present the state-of-the-art of side-channel attacks where the attacker shares memory with the victim in a virtualized environment.

4.3.1 Shared Memory Side-Channels

In a virtualized environment, memory deduplication is applied to pages in the physical host. This includes the sharing of pages belonging to different virtual machines that are located in the same host. A covert channel can be made because of the timing difference of the write operation to a page that is being shared by deduplication. This operation can be distinguished from a standard write to a page which is not being shared because a private copy must be done, and it takes more time. Figure 4.1 shows an example where the redundant memory of two virtual machines is shared by deduplication in the host machine. The bottom of the figure shows an outline of both opposite operations: the merging of two identical pages and the writing of a page previously merged. The delay produced when writing a memory page that has been shared produces a covert channel that allows attackers to detect if the page has been previously shared by the host. Therefore, an attacker can craft a page in their own address space, and then check if it has been deduplicated by the host. In the affirmative case, at least another virtual machine holds a page with those contents.

The first study that exploits memory deduplication to perform a side-channel was carried out by Suzaki et al. [80]. They were able to check/detect the existence of specific applications in a different virtual machine located in the same physical host. Later, the same authors improved

Figure 4.1: Overview of the memory deduplication covert channel. Two virtual machines are shown along with the physical memory of the host machine. The coloured rectangles (A, B, C, D) represent memory pages with different contents. With memory deduplication, pages with the same contents can be merged, keeping a single physical copy and eliminating redundant ones. When a write operation is executed afterwards on a shared page, the host machine has to create a new copy prior to writing to it. This produces a delay that enables distinguishing between writing to shared and non-shared pages.

their work, discussing more approaches and countermeasures, being able to detect a specific virtual machine previously marked in a multi-tenant cloud environment [81]. Concurrently, Owens and Wang [82] were able to fingerprint guest operating systems using the same technique.

Xiao et al. [102, 103] studied the security implications of memory deduplication from the perspectives of both attackers and defenders. They presented a method to detect virtualization and another to detect rootkits that modify kernel read-only data, both using memory deduplication covert channels. Suzuki et al. [104] continued their research on this topic, presenting more memory disclosure attacks based on memory deduplication that are able to detect the security level of attacked operating systems, find vulnerable applications, and confirm the status of attacked applications.

Two years later, Barresi et al. [105] developed an attack using the same technique, leaking the address space layouts [49] of the victim virtual machines, while Gruss et al. [106] presented a memory-disclosure attack in sandboxed JavaScript, without the need for the victim to execute any program, merely visiting a remote website controlled by the attacker. Rong et al. [107] even proposed a practical protocol of Cloud Covert Channel based on Memory Deduplication (CCCMD).

4.3.2 Shared Memory + Cache Side-Channels

In addition to the techniques presented in the previous section, there is a rich literature of side-channel attacks that combine memory deduplication with cache covert channels. These techniques rely on memory sharing with the victim virtual machine. When an attacker accesses to one of these shared pages, she is accessing to the same physical page frame that the victim is using. As a consequence, that page is located in the same cache line for both attacker and victim, due to the physically-indexed Last-Level-Cache (LLC).

In 2014, Yarom et al. [85, 108] introduced the `FLush+ReLoad` technique as an extension of a previous study about cache side-channel attacks [109]. It consists in measuring the access time of a specific cache line in the LLC, instead of measuring the writing time to a COWed page. The attacker flushes the monitored cache line and waits for the victim to access the memory line. Given that the victim page is shared with the attacker, they share the cache set for that page, and the attacker can ensure that a specific memory line is evicted from the entire cache hierarchy. Then, if the victim accesses to the data while the attacker is waiting, the monitored cache line will be filled again. In the last phase, the attacker reloads the cache line and measures how much time it takes. If the victim has accessed the memory line, the time will be short. Otherwise, the cache line will be empty, and the operation will be longer. Given that this technique is using the LLC, the attacker and the victim can be running in a different execution core of the physical machine and the attack will still work. With this technique, the authors achieved a successful extraction of GnuPG private encryption keys from a victim, along with the exploitation of a vulnerability introduced to elliptic curve cryptographic protocols, recovering OpenSSL Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) nonces.

This technique has been used by several studies since then. Irazoqui et al. [110, 111] retrieved an Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) cryptographic key and private keys from other cryptographic libraries in a cloud environment, using `Flush+Reload`. Later, they presented another paper where cryptographic libraries are detected across virtual machines, along with their IP addresses. Gülmezoğlu et al. [112] improved the technique and presented a *known-ciphertext only* cache side-channel attack against AES. Bengier et al. [113] used `Flush+Reload` to attack OpenSSL ECDSA signatures.

The `Evict+Reload` technique, introduced by Gruss et al. [114], is a variation of `Flush+Reload`. It consists of two phases. First, in the profiling phase, the attacker crafts a model (a template [115, 116]) of signals and noise from the cache side-channel traces, which is a matrix with the cache-hit ratio of the address of a specific target event generated on a device that the attacker controls. Secondly, in the exploitation phase, the attacker uses the template matrix previously crafted to deduce events in the system cache, based on the differences of cache hits. After the attack is performed, a report is generated in the attacker machine to be manually analyzed. Both phases use standard cache side-channel attack techniques (e.g., `Flush+Reload`) to obtain the cache hit ratio. Nevertheless, the authors noted that the technique can be adapted to evict a cache line without using the *flush cache line* instruction, thus invalidating a countermeasure proposed by other studies [85, 87, 108]. The method they used to evict a cache line indirectly is to access a physically congruent large array [114].

The `FLush+FLush` technique was presented by Gruss et al. [117]. With it, they achieved a stealthy method to perform cache side-channel attacks without access to the data. Consequently, `Flush+Flush` does not generate more cache misses than a benign program, avoiding some countermeasures that relied on hardware performance counters for detection [83, 118, 119]. Instead of measuring the access time of a memory location, they measured the time that

the *flush cache line* instruction takes. If the data is cached, this instruction takes more time than if the data is not cached, enabling the side-channel. Furthermore, given that it can work at a higher frequency, Flush+Flush is more efficient than other cache side-channel techniques previously known, in terms of speed.

There is a study that introduces a different technique for victim-memory shared side-channel attacks, which avoids the measurement of time. Disselkoen et al. [120] proposed a method to abuse last level cache in a virtualized system using the Intel Transactional Synchronization Extensions (TSX) instruction set [121, 122]. Intel TSX allows the programmer to specify *transactions* of code, in a way that either all the code is successfully executed (transaction completed) or, if anything fails, all the changes made in memory during the transaction are cancelled (transaction aborted). The authors are able to determine if the cache state has been modified by the victim or not, by means of the hardware callbacks provided by Intel TSX. These callbacks are executed if the victim accesses to the target data. As a consequence, there is no need for timing measurement, given that the attacker gets a side-channel through the state of the transactions (completed or aborted).

4.3.3 Shared Memory + Rowhammer

Previous techniques exploit the fact that the attacker is sharing memory with the victim in a read-only fashion, to leak sensitive information of all kinds and bypass security mechanisms like Address Space Layout Randomization [49]. On the other hand, some studies combine this condition with the Rowhammer technique [123] to not only read arbitrary data in the victim system but also to write. Rowhammer is a technique that exploits a hardware vulnerability present in many modern Dynamic Random-Access Memory (DRAM) modules. DRAM memory cells can leak their charges to nearby memory rows if they are repeatedly activated in a short period of time, modifying the contents of a row which was not intended to be accessed. As a consequence, an attacker is able to flip bits of arbitrary physical memory locations by repeatedly activating one or both adjacent rows.

Bosman et al. [86] built a “weird machine” that is able to perform a byte-by-byte disclosure of sensitive data of neighbour virtual machines. In this paper, they also disclose high-entropy randomized pointers, providing three different approaches: memory alignment probing, partial reuse, and birthday heap spray. After leaking and gathering all the needed information of the victim using the previous methods, the authors combine memory deduplication with Rowhammer to attack the browser, performing a write operation in a physical page belonging to the victim, without requiring any software vulnerability to perform the attack.

Similarly, Razavi et al. [124] introduced a novel exploitation technique called Flip Feng Shui (FFS). With it, an attacker is able to *exchange* the physical location of a page that is shared with the victim by using memory deduplication. Then, she can trigger a Rowhammer attack and modify their contents, inducing bit flips in a fully controlled way. As a consequence, this technique allows an attacker to write into a page of the victim virtual machine.

4.4 Slicedup: A Tenant-Aware Memory Deduplication for Cloud Systems

In this section, we present Slicedup, a memory deduplication design for multi-tenant clouds, where each tenant is the administrator of a group of trust that consists of multiple virtual machines. Slicedup restricts the memory sharing to virtual machines pertaining to the same group and avoids the sharing with virtual machines belonging to a different tenant. It enables the use of memory deduplication to maximize the resource utilization of the host machine in multi-tenant environments by allowing the execution of multiple virtual machines of different tenants on a single host without the problems of side-channel attacks across tenants. This way, memory deduplication can be used while maintaining a level of security for tenants equivalent to running their virtual machines on a dedicated host machine because memory is never shared across security boundaries. In addition, the memory sharing rates for virtual machines belonging to a specific tenant are the same as with standard deduplication.

Our proposed solution is to add tenancy awareness to the deduplication algorithm, identifying every virtual machine based on a Tenant ID. Since the deduplication is performed on the host machine, the algorithm that compares the memory pages is able to discern the virtual machines to which the pages being compared belong. Virtual machines belonging to a particular tenant have the same Tenant ID. Therefore, the difference between Slicedup and standard deduplication is that given two identical pages, these will only be merged if both pages share the same Tenant ID. As a result, a finer granular deduplication is obtained where memory is only shared with those virtual machines of the same tenant. This solution provides

Figure 4.2: Overview of Slicedup, comparing it with standard deduplication. Two tenants with two virtual machines each are shown. On the left, memory deduplication is applied to the entire memory of all virtual machines, allowing side-channel attacks. On the right, the same situation is shown with Slicedup, where the sharing is limited to the virtual machines of the same tenant and stopping the attacks between tenants.

a fair trade-off, where the isolation of virtual machines of a tenant is kept along with the sharing effectiveness of memory deduplication within a specific group.

Figure 4.2 shows an overview scenario with two tenants running two virtual machines each one, both located in the same physical host. The figure compares standard deduplication (left) and the proposed Slicedup (right). With standard deduplication, the memories of all the virtual machines running on the same host are shared without distinction. The only condition for merging two memory pages is that their contents must be identical. As we have seen in Section 4.3, this is prone to side-channel attacks between different tenants. In the example, it can be seen that Tenant T1 is able to attack Tenant T2. By contrast, the right side of the figure shows the same situation with Slicedup. In this case, sharing memory requires not only that the contents are identical but also that they belong to the same group/tenant. As a result, the memory sharing is logically separated into different groups of virtual machines, thus enforcing security boundaries. The attack that occurred in the former case between Tenant T1 and Tenant T2 is now prevented because T1 and T2 do not share memory.

A simulation has been undertaken to provide an estimate of the memory sharing rate obtained with Slicedup in multi-tenant systems. We have observed that the memory saved by deduplication has a logarithmic behaviour as more virtual machines are added. For example, first we measure the memory saved by deduplication on a host machine running two identical virtual machines, and then we gradually add more virtual machines to see the increment of memory saved. The exact amount of memory saved depends on the contents they generate, so different kernel/userland combinations produce different discrete memory saving results. However, the logarithmic distribution is always met.

In order to provide a fair simulation without producing any tailored kernel/userland biased configuration, we have used a generic approach based on previous works [1, 70]. From experiment results of Suzaki et al. [1] and Red Hat [70] we fitted the points into the $\log(x)$ function by using the *least squares fit* technique, obtaining the function represented in Figure 4.3. This function is used in the simulation to obtain the amount of memory saved by deduplication for a given number of virtual machines. In the figure, x-axis is the number of virtual machines running at the same time and the y-axis shows the estimated percentage of memory saved by deduplication.

Figure 4.3: Logarithmic function obtained to determine the estimation of memory saved by deduplication for a given number of virtual machines. This function is provided for use in the simulation.

Table 4.1: Estimation of memory saved comparing standard deduplication and Slicedup.

Physical Memory	Num. of Tenants	Standard		Slicedup	
		Total VMs	Memory Saved	Total VMs	Memory Saved
16 GiB	2	16	9.17 GiB (57.3%)	16	7.52 GiB (47.0%)
	4	16	9.17 GiB (57.3%)	16	5.87 GiB (36.7%)
	6	16	9.17 GiB (57.3%)	12	3.17 GiB (19.8%)
32 GiB	2	32	21.6 GiB (67.6%)	32	18.34 GiB (57.3%)
	4	32	21.6 GiB (67.6%)	32	15.04 GiB (47.0%)
	6	32	21.6 GiB (67.6%)	30	12.00 GiB (37.5%)
64 GiB	2	64	49.86 GiB (77.9%)	64	43.27 GiB (67.6%)
	4	64	49.86 GiB (77.9%)	64	36.67 GiB (57.3%)
	6	64	49.86 GiB (77.9%)	60	30.19 GiB (47.2%)

Once this function has been obtained, we can proceed with the simulation using a specific model of the virtual machine. For this, following the approach used by Red Hat [70], we use generic virtual machines of Windows XP which consume 1 GiB of RAM. The actual specific virtual machine model used in the simulation is not relevant, since the same model is used to compare standard deduplication and Slicedup. The objective of the simulation is to determine the extent to which the sharing rate decreases by logically separating the sharing of memory by groups of virtual machines at the expense of providing security against side-channels between different tenants on the same host.

Table 4.1 shows the results of the simulation, comparing both standard deduplication and Slicedup. It shows different combinations of total physical memory available on the host and different number of tenants or groups of virtual machines running in the same host. The number of virtual machines to be executed is determined by partitioning the available memory equally among the different tenants. For example, if there are 16 GiB available to distribute among six tenants, each one can allocate two virtual machines that initially consume 1 GiB. Once the number of virtual machines has been determined, the amount of memory saved by deduplication is obtained for each case.

The results obtained with the standard deduplication are independent of the number of tenants, because the deduplication is applied globally to all virtual machines. On the other hand, since Slicedup restricts the memory sharing to virtual machines belonging to the same group, the more groups there are, the fewer opportunities for sharing their memories with other virtual machines. For example, for the case with 64 GiB of physical memory in the host, the profit decreases from 77.9% to 67.6% when the sharing is split into two tenants, even though the total number of virtual machines running in the host is the same in both cases. In general, the memory saved with Slicedup depends on the number of tenants that are co-residing in the host. As expected, when more tenants co-reside in the host, the less memory sharing is obtained. It is the responsibility of the cloud infrastructure providers to decide on the number of tenants [125, 126].

It is important to keep in mind that although standard deduplication provides better sharing results, it is prone to side-channel attacks. Hence, these results represent only the best case scenario regarding memory sharing, but it cannot be taken as a solution. Slicedup offers relatively good memory sharing rates whilst preventing side-channel attacks between tenants.

Therefore, it offers a compromise solution between memory sharing effectiveness and security, allowing memory deduplication without compromising the system security.

4.5 Discussion of Slicedup and other approaches

Memory deduplication was designed as a performance technique to increase the memory savings of a system. It has been proved [32, 33, 75–79] that it offers an effective and efficient improvement of the physical memory resources management when it is enabled. However, the side-channel produced by memory deduplication is a security problem for the clients of cloud infrastructure providers. Although several studies proposed different possible countermeasures to avoid this issue, there is no consolidated solution which offers similar performance than the original implementations and provides a defence to all the possible attacks without adding complexity. This section presents a brief overview of those approaches and discusses their advantages and disadvantages, concluding with Slicedup.

Payer [83] proposed HexPADS as an anomaly detection system. It is a signature-based Attack Detection System that relies on performance counters. HexPADS analyzes running processes, measuring their performance and checking a set of signatures. It is able to detect long-running side-channel attacks with low overhead. Nevertheless, it is prone to false positives and false negatives. Besides, as a signature-based system, it doesn't detect new attacks (unknown signature). Furthermore, given that it is based on performance counters, other advanced and stealthy cache attacks can bypass the detection, such as Flush+Flush.

Oliverio et al. [84] proposed VUision as a new design of memory deduplication that cuts information leaks and Rowhammer attacks based on memory deduplication. It hides the ability of the attackers to distinguish between shared pages and non-shared pages, thus reducing the attack surface. To achieve this, the authors follow a fundamental principle that they call Same Behavior (SB), which means that the attacker will obtain the same results whether the page being tested is merged or not. VUision allows page sharing among different tenants with an acceptable memory sharing rate. On the other hand, the Same Behavior principle reduces the pages that can be candidates to be merged (only idle pages). Unfortunately, VUision is intricate to implement. Author's PoC implementation relies on using reserved bits of the PTE as an alternative to avoid the use of the present bit, which would need intrusive changes to the Linux kernel.

Other solutions were proposed, for example, to encrypt the memory of a given process to avoid deduplication [81, 85], software diversification to detect anomalies [85], to share only pages containing zeros [86], or to completely disable memory deduplication [87]. However, those ideas didn't get to consolidate a suitable solution that would provide secure memory sharing.

Slicedup achieves its purpose with a straightforward and simple but effective approach. It merges not only idle pages but also the active ones (as standard deduplication) and side-channel attacks between tenants are completely prevented. There are also a few drawbacks to this approach. The memory sharing efficiency is tied to the number of tenants co-located in a given physical host. Since the memory sharing among virtual machines belonging to different tenants is not allowed to mitigate side-channel attacks, the set of memory pages that can be potentially shared decreases when more tenants are located in the same physical host. Besides, although Slicedup protects tenants against attacks from other tenants, it does not protect against attacks from virtual machines belonging to the same group/tenant. In that scenario, information disclosure and physical memory massaging [124] are still feasible.

However, Slicedup offers strong protection on systems where all virtual machines in a particular tenant trust each other. Consequently, attacks from distrusting tenants are ineffective. Cloud infrastructure providers can benefit from Slicedup because it provides an additional layer of abstraction for virtual machine placement policies, offering a feasible alternative to resource isolation as a defence against side-channel attacks [127] which would require placing virtual machines of each tenant in dedicated hosts. Slicedup allows providers to securely place several virtual machines belonging to different tenants on the same host and to use memory deduplication for maximizing the utilization of host resources [126] and thus increasing their profits.

4.6 Conclusions

In this chapter, Slicedup has been presented. Slicedup is a memory deduplication design for multi-tenant cloud systems that offers a trade-off between a) sharing the memories of all the virtual machines running in a host, which weakens the system, and b) disabling completely the memory deduplication mechanism, which implies the loss of all benefits obtained from memory sharing.

Slicedup offers an additional layer of abstraction for virtual machine placement policies, allowing cloud infrastructure providers to securely place several virtual machines belonging to different tenants in the same host without having to sacrifice the deduplication mechanism. The shared memory rates between virtual machines of a given tenant are equivalent to the standard deduplication. Additionally, side-channel attacks based on sharing memory among different tenants are prevented due to the isolation provided by Slicedup that prevents memory sharing across different security domains.

Thanks to Slicedup, deduplication can be enabled in multi-tenant clouds. In the following chapters, we will discuss and analyze the impact that the kernel randomization security mechanism has on the effectiveness of memory sharing by deduplication and provide solutions to this problem for such multi-tenant cloud environments.

Chapter 5

Multi-Tenant Kernel Randomization

Kernel randomization is a widely adopted protection technique present in all modern operating systems. It is a very effective technique that thwarts unknown attacks. Unfortunately, as discussed throughout this chapter, its randomness has a significant impact on memory deduplication savings.

Both techniques are desired by the industry, the first one because of the high level of security that it provides and the latter to obtain better resources' exploitation.

In this chapter, we identify why the most widely and effective technique used to mitigate attacks at kernel level fails to provide protection and shareability at the same time. We analyze the current standard Linux kernel randomization and how it affects to the shared memory of each kernel region.

Then, based on the analysis, we propose KASLR-MT, the first effective and practical kernel randomization protection that maximizes the memory deduplication savings rate while providing a strong security.

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5.1 Introduction

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) [10] is considered one of the fundamental building blocks for cloud services. The service provider supplies the storage, networking and virtualization, so that the user has full control over the system from OS layer upwards. Efficient resource management is imperative to deal with a proper cloud infrastructure. Hardware resources are a critical asset in the business, and it must be managed and utilized adequately [128].

Since the cloud is an essential part of the daily life of our society, it is absolutely important to offer confidentiality, integrity, and availability in any cloud computing architecture. Although cloud service providers desire to yield as much security as possible in their infrastructure, it is not always possible [129].

Unfortunately, there is no perfect protection that guards against all kinds of threats. In fact, current security protection mechanisms are far from that and, in some cases, they introduce prohibitive overheads. Furthermore, in some cases, the efficiency of other existing mechanisms aimed to improve the performance of the system can also be severely affected. Kernel randomization is an instance of this issue. When it is enabled along with memory deduplication, the memory saving effectiveness is considerably reduced. Since it is not recommended disabling the kernel randomization mechanism, cloud providers will sustain a forfeit of memory resources.

Throughout this chapter, we point out the reasons why the kernel randomization penalizes the effectiveness of memory deduplication. The Linux kernel randomized zones are identified and a comprehensive analysis on the deduplication effect of randomizing them is presented. Based on this analysis, we propose KASLR-MT, a new Linux kernel randomization approach compatible with memory deduplication. After implementing the proposed solution for the Linux OS and evaluating its effectiveness, the chapter finishes with a discussion on Linux kernel modules and how position-independent code could alleviate the issue under certain circumstances.

5.2 Assumptions and Attacker Model

Chapter 4 describes Slicedup, which offers the ability to enable memory deduplication in multi-tenant cloud environments while preventing side-channel attacks between different tenants. This is achieved by constraining memory sharing within security domains formed by the virtual machines belonging to each tenant. Henceforth, we are focusing on each of these security domains where memory deduplication is applied to several virtual machines belonging to a given tenant. The same can be applied to single-tenant dedicated hosts with several virtual machines and deduplication enabled.

Randomizing the kernel mitigates the exploitation of vulnerabilities that rely on knowing kernel virtual memory addresses, for example return-oriented programming (ROP) attacks [19, 50, 130], which allow attackers to dynamically *re-compile* the kernel code at execution time. Without the protection of kernel randomization, attacks exploiting those vulnerabilities will always be successful, since those kernel addresses are not a secret that the attackers need to obtain. For this reason, disabling kernel randomization in favor of having an effective memory deduplication with the highest possible savings rate is not a real option since it introduces serious weaknesses that could compromise the full cloud provider.

Figure 5.1: Overview of the attacker model, showing a hypervisor running three virtual machines. Two of them (VM-1 and VM-2) belong to one tenant (T1), while the third (VM-3) belongs to another tenant (T2). Attacks from remote machines and from other tenants must face the kernel randomization protection to succeed.

In cloud environments, where there are several virtual machines that can directly or indirectly interact with each other, this is even more risky. Any kernel vulnerability could compromise all guest virtual machines of the entire cloud, even if the guests live in different physical machines. In that case, attackers do not need to conduct any prior attack to determine the location of the kernel in memory. The location is well known and the attack will always succeed.

The scope and the goal of this chapter is to enable the protection of kernel randomization while minimizing to a negligible extent its impact on memory deduplication. This will enable cloud providers to use the kernel randomization technique to secure guest kernels against control-flow hijacking attacks and code-injection attacks without losing the benefits of memory deduplication. We assume that the kernel contains a software vulnerability that requires to bypass the kernel randomization protection to be successfully exploited. In addition, our model threat assumes that a local attacker has or can easily get full control of an entire virtual machine and therefore we aim to protect virtual machines of a particular tenant from other tenants and from the Internet. Hence, our goal is that attackers that exploit a kernel vulnerability from remote machines or from virtual machines pertaining to other tenants face the full kernel randomization protection, while keeping the impact on memory deduplication to the minimum.

Figure 5.1 shows the overview of the described attacker model. The hypervisor is running three virtual machines, two of which (VM-1 and VM-2) belong to one tenant (T1), and the third (VM-3) belongs to another tenant (T2). Attacks from remote machines and from other tenants are covered by the attacker model. It is assumed that virtual machines pertaining to the same tenant trust each other so if one of them is compromised, the others are susceptible to being attacked.

5.3 Linux Kernel Randomization

Both the problem of kernel randomization impacting the effectiveness of memory deduplication and the solution proposed below are applicable to any operating system that uses this security technique. Taking advantage of the open source nature of the Linux operating system, it will be used as a model to analyze the problem and to provide an appropriate solution. However, the solution proposed in section 5.6 is generic and applicable to any OS. This section describes an overview of how standard kernel randomization works in the Linux kernel v5.0.6 for the x86_64 architecture. We describe how the bootloader and the Linux kernel randomizes its memory.

In Section 2.5, we described two different approaches to randomize code: position-independent code and relocations. Current Linux kernel implementation is not PIC compliant. It uses text relocations, patching dynamically all the position-dependent references after the final address of the code memory region is randomly calculated.

At the early stages of the boot process, the Linux kernel is decompressed in memory by the bootloader. One of its purposes, along with other system initialization operations, is to place the regular kernel into a random location.

The random numbers used by KASLR are requested at boot time, and at this stage there is not much entropy available. Having quality random numbers is key to have an effective KASLR, otherwise the addresses will be predictable and the protection useless. In order to obtain random numbers, Linux uses different sources of entropy such as `rand`, `rdtsc`, system timers, etc. The outcome of all the available sources is combined by using the XOR operation, and the result value is diffused by using circular multiplication.

The decompressor uses two random numbers to randomize both the physical address and the virtual address where the kernel will be loaded and mapped respectively. The physical address determines where the regular kernel image is going to be decompressed in memory. This image is an Executable and Linkable Format (ELF) file with a relocation table appended to it. Relocation information is generated by the static linker and it is needed for patching the virtual addresses of every position-dependent reference. Each virtual address that needs to be updated has its corresponding entry in this relocation table.

Once the kernel is decompressed into the randomly chosen physical address, the kernel image is parsed to extract the information about the segments that compose the kernel virtual memory. All the loadable segments are placed into their corresponding location. Then, relocations are processed. The kernel needs to be patched taking into account the new base address that differs from the base address that it was linked to. Listing 5.1 shows the pseudo-code of the loop processing and fixing relocations.

After the relocations have been applied by the bootloader, the execution control is transferred to the kernel. At this point, some system initialization operations are performed, including the randomization of the remaining four memory regions. First, the physical direct mapping (`physmap`), the dynamic memory region (`vmalloc`) and the virtual memory map (`vmemmap`) are randomized. Later, when the first module is loaded, the modules base address is randomly calculated (`modules`).

Although each region is randomized independently, there is a position order. The physical direct mapping will always be placed at a lower virtual address than the `vmalloc` region, which also will be placed at a lower virtual address than the `vmemmap` region.

Code 5.1: Pseudo-code of relocations update

```
for each relocation do
    reloc_addr = <read relocation entry>
    // Calculate its current physical location
    ptr = (reloc_addr + phys_map)
    check_memory_bounds(ptr)

    // Update virtual address
    *ptr += kaslr_virt_offset
```

The randomization algorithm tries to use the available entropy in the most efficient way possible. The first region is bounded to the lower third of the entire virtual space available for these three regions. A random address within the bounds is selected to map the memory region. The remaining space, subtracting a padding to avoid region overlapping, is then divided by two in order to place the second region, following the same approach. Similarly, the last region is placed at a random address within the remaining space after subtracting the padding corresponding to the second one.

The final memory region to be randomized is the zone where modules are loaded. It uses a different logic from the previous memory regions, since it is not calculated until the first module is loaded in the system. When the first module is loaded, a random number of pages between 1 and 1024 is determined and it is added to a static base address, establishing the virtual base address where the allocation of all the loadable modules starts. From that point, subsequent modules are sequentially allocated in the order as they are loaded. Once a module is loaded into its final location, relocations need to be done to fix-up their references. These relocations include absolute addresses and relative offsets. We have found modules with references to different parts of the memory, including the kernel code and data, the physmap region, their own memory, and even the memory of other modules. It is worth noting that even relative offsets depend on address randomization if they refer to memory regions being also randomized. In that case, the relative offset may differ, since the distance between referee and referrer is not constant. In addition, the module load order is not deterministic so the final order, and therefore the relocations applied to modules, can be different in different kernel boots. This issue is discussed in more detail in Section 5.9.

To summarize, the Linux kernel randomizes a total of six different addresses:

- **Kernel Base Physical Address:** Physical address where the kernel is decompressed.
- **Kernel Base Virtual Address:** Virtual address of the kernel text mapping, containing the code and data segments.
- **Physmap:** Direct mapping of all physical memory. Also used to dynamically allocate physically contiguous memory.
- **Vmalloc:** Memory region to dynamically allocate virtually contiguous memory.
- **Vmemmap:** Kernel virtual memory map, containing metadata of physical page frames.
- **Modules:** Virtual base address where modules are loaded.

5.4 The Problem: KASLR vs Deduplication

In this section, we present how kernel randomization reduces the effectiveness of memory sharing by deduplication in virtualized systems.

As detailed in section 2.2, the memory deduplication mechanism merges pages with equal content. Regardless of whether they comprise code or data and independently of their virtual address, two or more pages will be merged if their contents are identical. On the other hand, as described in section 2.5, kernel randomization could affect the host's memory sharing effectiveness if the relocation randomization approach is used. Unfortunately, as we present in section 5.3, we found that current Linux versions uses the relocations approach for randomizing the kernel.

The main issue is that current Linux kernel randomization is following a relocation approach that modifies code at boot time depending on random addresses, but memory deduplication requires to have equal content to merge pages. This conflict results on either having KASLR enabled but reducing the shared memory or disabling KASLR to have the maximum deduplicated memory.

Figure 5.2: Overview scenario, with a hypervisor using memory deduplication and running three virtual machines. Kernel memories of two virtual machines are detailed, showing their load address along with some contents of the code and data regions.

5.4.1 Breaking Shared Code

Memory deduplication fails to merge kernel code because of the randomization. Figure 5.2 exemplifies this concept. It shows the same hypothetical `printk()` kernel call from 2 kernels that were mapped at different base addresses. Kernel 2 base address is `0x40000` and kernel 3 base address is `0x80000`. The resulting `mov $addr, %rdi` is patched by the kernel loader accordingly to the random kernel base address at boot time.

In more detail, the instruction is placing the virtual address of the string into a register and passing it to the `printk()` function, following the *System V AMD64 ABI* convention [131]. The absolute reference in the `mov` instruction differs because the data region was loaded at different addresses. These absolute addresses need to be fixed-up at load time, before even running the kernel, altering the page content. As a consequence, those pages cannot be merged by deduplication because their content after the relocation will differ. This is just an example to illustrate the issue that prevents memory deduplication from merging Linux code. The Linux kernel is a modern and advanced operating system containing many coding tricks to improve both the readability and efficiency of the code, and this issue can appear in different ways.

Therefore, a full analysis is necessary, presented in section 5.5 to determine, on the one hand, to what extent the code is being modified because of the randomization and, on the other hand, which randomization zones produce most kernel and modules code modifications.

5.4.2 Breaking Shared Data

Relocations do not only affect to code but also to data variables whose contents depend on the virtual address of the memory location being referenced. For example, a data pointer containing the address of a dynamically allocated object. Therefore, the problem occurs when memory contents depend on the position of the memory location being referenced and this location is randomized. A very well-known example in userland applications is the usage of a GOT/PLT to jump to libraries. The GOT contains pointers to where library functions reside in memory. Therefore, the fact of randomizing libraries prevents the merging of the page holding the GOT.

Similarly, the Linux kernel contains structures that hold pointers to functions. Those pointers depend on the kernel base address. As a consequence, all pages containing one single pointer referencing to a randomized address will not be merged by memory deduplication. This can be extended to any memory in Linux that holds data, such as `vmalloc`, `vmemmap` and modules data.

Returning to figure 5.2, we can observe an array of pointers in the data section of both kernels, where the second element points to an address of its corresponding code section. Similar to what occurs with the relocation in the `mov` instruction, given that the base address of these two kernels differ, the pointer will differ as well. As a consequence, the host cannot share these memory pages.

5.5 KASLR Influence on Deduplication

Randomizing the memory layout of guest kernels reduces the effectiveness of memory deduplication. In this section, in order to design a new compatible KASLR, we present a comprehensive analysis of the impact of each randomized area to the memory deduplication.

Our goal is to precisely measure to what extent a particular memory region (Linux code, Linux data, modules code, modules data, vmalloc and vmemmap) differs when randomizing memory base addresses (kernel physical address, kernel virtual address, physical mapping, vmalloc, vmemmap and modules). Since there are six memory base addresses to be randomized, we have tested $2^6 = 64$ combinations per each memory region. For example, enabling randomization for all memory base addresses except one, all except two, etc. All tests were executed using Ubuntu 19.04 with Linux v5.0.6 carrying out 8 probes per each combination, resulting in a total of $64 * 8 = 512$ virtual machine executions. By comparing all the probes of each combination, we can obtain the percentage of equal pages. By doing this, we can precisely achieve the following:

1. **The KASLR influence:** of each combination to identify which randomized memory base address have more impact on memory deduplication.
2. **The best combination:** for our purpose. In our case, we aim to fully randomize as many memory base addresses as possible. To achieve that, we need to obtain those that have low or zero impact on memory deduplication. As detailed in the solution section 5.6, those memory base addresses will be randomized as usual, and we are not modifying the kernel code that randomizes them.
3. **Not biased and Independent Results:** of the number of virtual machines. Instead of calculating the memory deduplication differences before and after randomization, we are calculating how different or equal a memory region is after applying randomization. The first approach could be tuned to obtain almost any number by choosing a high number of virtual machines. For example, if half of the memory of a virtual machine can be deduplicated, then if we have two identical machines, the memory deduplication will save 50% of the memory but if we have three, the deduplication will report 66% of memory saved. Hence, although this is reflecting the actual savings, it is not appropriate to know the real impact of KASLR.

All the virtual machine instances have been executed and memory dumps of the kernels have been extracted from the information contained in their page tables. Our analysis focus on obtaining the percentage of pages that are equal for each case, independently of the region's size. Note that our analysis obtains separately the randomization effect produced to Linux code and Linux data regions, but it is not possible to randomize both separately. On the other hand, the fact of randomizing the physical mapping can influence one or more memory regions, but this is a special case; it is a virtual mapping to all physical memory and not actually a memory region, so its contents must be ignored in the analysis.

Even though the Linux kernel guests use pages of 2 MiB, the memory deduplication implementation in Linux works with 4 KiB pages. Therefore, our analysis calculating how equal a memory region is after applying all randomization detects differences at page level, that is, a single bit difference in a page is reported as a full 4 KiB page mismatch.

The results of the analysis are shown in tables A.1 to A.6, in appendix A. Tables A.1 and A.2 show the analysis of the Linux code and data respectively. Tables A.3 and A.4 do the same for

the code and data of the modules, table A.5 shows the analysis of `vmalloc` and finally table A.6 presents the results of the `vmemmap` memory region. The column *% equal pages* on the tables indicates the percentage of similarity between a particular memory region across all memory base address randomization combinations. Each table is discussed in more detail in the following subsections.

5.5.1 Linux Code Impact

The results of the randomization effects on the Linux code shown in table A.1 point out that the Linux code memory region is only and drastically affected by the randomization of the kernel virtual address. When the randomization is applied to the kernel virtual address, the percentage of equal pages is reduced from 100% to 2.6%, regardless of whether other areas are randomized or not. Although we discussed in section 5.3 that Linux is using relocations to implement the kernel randomization, the results indicate that almost all kernel code pages are altered in this relocation process, resulting in a non-shared Linux code region.

This result might seem surprising from a naive point of view in expectation to have more PIE parts of the kernel. It is noticeable not the fact that randomizing the Linux code will affect to the memory deduplication of its code pages but obtaining that 97.4% are patched due to the randomization process, which points out that the relocations are spread throughout the Linux code memory area.

5.5.2 Linux Data Impact

The results for the Linux data memory region shown in table A.2 show that the percentage of equal pages when all areas are randomized is 64% in average, and by only disabling the randomization of the kernel virtual address, this value is increased to 80%. Hence, only by randomizing the kernel virtual address causes deduplication to decrease around a 20%.

The Linux data contains absolute addresses referencing to parts of the kernel itself (to either code and data regions). Considering that a single absolute reference affects the entire page, approximately 15% of pages in this region contain this kind of references, according to our experiment results. As shown in table A.2, randomizing other memory areas has negligible effect on the percentage of equal pages in the Linux data. This can be observed in the 5th column (kernel `vaddr.`), which is the base address that most affects the percentage of equal pages. In contrast, the randomization of all other addresses do not have a direct influence on the contents of Linux Data.

5.5.3 Modules Code Impact

Regarding the Linux modules code, table A.3 points out that when both kernel virtual address and the modules base address are not randomized, then around 25-30% percent have equal content. Any other combination will reduce by around 52% the sharing rate reaching 11-12% of equal pages. Therefore, randomizing either the kernel virtual address or modules is enough to reduce modules code sharing rate by around 52%.

The latter is not surprising because when modules are loaded at a random position, all the relocations with absolute addresses alter the contents of the module's code region (e.g., accessing to a variable of its data region). However, why randomizing only the kernel virtual address has the same effect as randomizing the modules base address could be less evident.

The reason of such behavior is that any reference to kernel symbols (e.g., `kmalloc()` function) must be fixed up. Then, if the kernel virtual address is randomized, these relocations will differ. In the case of kernel references, the issue occurs with any type of relocation (absolute or relative) [131].

A result that might be seen as unexpected is not having the highest percentage of equal pages for the modules code when the randomization of all memory areas is disabled. This occurs because modules load order is not preserved across different kernel boots, even when the kernel randomization is fully disabled. This issue is further discussed in Section 5.9.

5.5.4 Modules Data Impact

The minimum percentage of equal pages in the data section of modules is achieved when the modules base address is randomized. The obtained value, as table A.4 shows, is 30% and enabling or disabling the rest of memory areas does not affect to this value. On average, enabling the modules base address randomization will reduce around 12% the number of equal pages of the modules' data.

When the modules base address is not randomized, the percentage of equal pages of module data is between 38-48% (42% average). From this range, the lowest sharing rate is obtained when the kernel virtual address is randomized. This confirms that the modules' data region contains pointers to the kernel. However, it can be less obvious to realize that module data could contain pointers to its own data memory region, which breaks the shareability because of the unpredictable load module order even when the modules base address is not randomized. Around 64% of pages in modules data contain at least one absolute reference to its own module memory (code and data), and 23% to the kernel region.

5.5.5 Vmalloc Space Impact

The results of the `vmalloc` memory region shown in table A.5 reveal a really low percentage of equal pages in all cases. Therefore, the Linux kernel randomization is not affecting the contents of the `vmalloc` memory region, having in all cases a 3% of equal pages.

This is not surprising since `vmalloc` is mainly used to dynamically and temporally store data by the kernel, and randomizing memory areas does not affect to that content. This memory is always random in our proposal since it has no effect on memory deduplication.

5.5.6 Virtual Memory Map Impact

The results for the `vmemmap` memory region shown in table A.6 indicate that only by randomizing the `vmemmap` address, the percentage of equal pages for this memory region drops to zero compared to the 38% obtained on average when the `vmemmap` memory region is not randomized.

The `vmemmap` memory region contains lists of objects with references to previous and next objects that reside in the `vmemmap` memory region itself. Therefore, by randomizing this area all those pointers will be different and the pages will not be mergeable.

Table 5.1: Impact of randomizing Linux base addresses on the different memory regions.

Randomized Addresses	Impact on Linux Kernel Memory Regions					
	Linux Code	Linux Data	Modules Code	Modules Data	vmalloc	vmemmap
Kernel Base (Physical)	none	none	none	none	none	low
Kernel Base (Virtual)	high	med	high	low	none	none
Physical Direct Mapping	none	none	none	none	none	none
Vmalloc/ioremap	none	none	none	none	none	none
Vmemmap	none	none	none	none	none	high
Modules	none	none	high	med	none	none

none < 5% | low 5-15% | med 15-30% | high > 30%

5.5.7 Analysis summary

In order to summarize the impact of the kernel randomization on each memory region, we classified the relative sharing loss obtained from tables A.1-A.6 into none, low, medium and high impact. This measures the relative percentage of equal pages that can not be merged when the kernel randomization is enabled. For example, the modules' data memory region loses 28.5% of relative equal pages (from 42% to 30%) when the modules base address is randomized.

Table 5.1 summarizes the kernel randomization impact on the different memory regions. Three memory regions are highly impacted because of the kernel randomization (Linux code, modules code and vmemmap) and two have a medium impact (Linux data and modules data). As detailed in section 5.6, KASLR-MT will handle those five memory regions in order to restore back the memory sharing rate.

5.6 KASLR-MT: A Multi-Tenancy KASLR

In this section, we present KASLR-MT, a kernel randomization design for multi-tenant cloud systems which is compatible with memory deduplication while providing a strong level of security. As summarized in section 5.5.7, there are memory regions with none/low impact and others with medium/high impact on memory deduplication. Based on that, we have designed KASLR-MT to keep a strong security while maximizing memory deduplication sharing rate, as analyzed in section 5.8.

As stated in section 5.4 and studied in section 5.5, kernel randomization produces alterations in memory contents that breaks memory sharing. To remedy this situation and yield memory sharing by deduplication in the host, kernel memory layouts of guest virtual machines should be as similar as possible.

A quick workaround to achieve this, although it is not a solution by itself, would be to disable kernel randomization in the guests. If kernel randomization is completely disabled, guest kernels are deterministically placed in a default address settled at compile time. Comparing

guest instances of the same kernel, all of them produce the same kernel memory layout. As a consequence, relocations that are different when the kernel is randomized are equal when it is not. Even though this approach can be a suitable method in certain environments, for example private clouds properly secured against external attacks, we do not recommend disabling any security mechanism. As stated in section 5.2, the fact of disabling KASLR to obtain better memory deduplication savings introduces serious weaknesses.

In order to properly tackle the randomization-vs-sharing problem, we propose Kernel Address Space Layout Randomization Multi-Tenancy (KASLR-MT), a para-virtualization based solution that enables the hypervisor to provide the kernel memory layout to the guest virtual machines in multi-tenant cloud environments. It gives the host machine the ability to decide the locations of different kernel memory regions of guest virtual machines. There are two possibilities for each kernel memory region:

1. **None/Low impact memory regions.** If a memory region has low or negligible impact when all memory base address are randomized, then this memory region can be randomized without sharing its base address with any other kernel. Note that the base address of this memory region will be different among virtual machines in both, same and different tenants.
2. **Medium/High impact memory regions:** If a memory region has medium or high impact when any memory base address is randomized, then this memory region must be randomized in a per-tenant basis, *sharing* its base address with other kernels belonging to the same tenant. Therefore, the base address of this memory region will be the same among virtual machines belonging to the same tenant and different among virtual machines of different tenants.

This solution is designed for multi-tenant cloud systems, where different tenants are owners of different groups of virtual machines. Thus, virtual machines belonging to a same tenant can attain a common kernel memory layout, allowing the host machine to share more memory. Security is kept, since the kernel memory layout is still unpredictable from the attacker perspective. This is valid even if virtual machines are not exactly identical, because the granularity of memory deduplication is 4096 bytes, which enables it to deduplicate parts of the virtual machines. KASLR-MT will provide the maximum possible benefit compared with the memory deduplication when the kernel randomization is enabled.

The cloud infrastructure maintains a table with one-to-one correspondence, linking Tenant-ID and a unique random key. Each unique key serves as a seed to deterministically produce base addresses of guest kernel memory regions. The table relation must be bijective so that there are no duplicate keys in the cloud infrastructure, and keys must be unpredictable. Otherwise, since the algorithm to produce addresses from a given key must be highly deterministic, an attacker who can predict the key of a victim tenant will be able to guess the kernel address space layout of the victim's virtual machines. It is the responsibility of the infrastructure provider to maintain and protect the table. It is located in the host machine, so it is not directly accessible from within the virtual machines.

Figure 5.3 shows the design of KASLR-MT. Since the table relating each tenant with its key is stored in the host machine, the hypervisor transfers the corresponding key to a virtual machine when it is turned on. The method of transferring this key is implementation-dependent. Guest kernels will use the key as input to the Address Producer to get all the memory addresses of regions that want to randomize. This design is flexible because the host does not need to know

Figure 5.3: Design of KASLR-MT. A tenant key is transferred to the guest to deterministically produce the final addresses of kernel memory regions.

the layout of the guests or how many addresses they will need. The guests will deterministically produce their corresponding layout using the provided key as a seed. On the right part of the figure, the kernel memory of four different virtual machines are depicted. Tenant T1 owns two of them (VM-1 and VM-2) while the other virtual machines (VM-3 and VM-4) belong to Tenant T2. Both VM-1 and VM-2 obtain the same memory layout because both kernels are using the same key (K1) as input to the Address Producer algorithm. On the other hand, VM-3 and VM-4 use the key of Tenant T2 (K2), obtaining a different memory layout.

The table information needs to be distributed to all the host machines forming the cloud infrastructure. Coherence of this distributed state in the infrastructure is important to support virtual machine migration. If, otherwise, the keys were only kept locally in host machines, a migrated virtual machine whose kernel memory layout was generated with a different key would introduce layout diversity within a same group of virtual machines. If this occurs, since the key used to generate the memory layout of the migrated VM is different from other VMs, the problem of memory sharing breakage reappears.

The lifetime of a tenant's key goes from when its first virtual machine starts to when its last active virtual machine turns off, independently of the state of other virtual machines belonging to different tenants. A key cannot be changed if any virtual machine is running, since it would introduce layout diversity as well; i.e., kernel memory layout of guests started after a key change would likely differ from those started before. When the last virtual machine of a given tenant turns off, the key can be safely purged. In fact, it is mandatory to purge it, in order to force the creation of a new key for subsequent guest kernels. For the generation of new keys, the process is exactly the same as in the beginning. The host has to ensure that the tenant-key correspondence is one-to-one and that there is not any key collision.

With KASLR-MT, kernel memory base addresses can be randomized in two different ways:

1. **Per-Tenant:** For a given memory region, a random key is generated by the host and associated to a tenant. The key is shared across all virtual machines belonging to the same tenant to enable them to generate the random base address. Guests will have the same memory base address (random) for a particular memory region. KASLR-MT uses a Per-Tenant approach for memory regions where the impact is high or medium.
2. **Per-VM:** For a given memory region, a random key is generated by the host and associated to a virtual machine. Every time a guest reboots, the region will have a different memory base address and it will not be shared across virtual machines belonging to same or other tenants. KASLR-MT uses a Per-VM approach for memory regions where the impact is low or none.

KASLR-MT combines the deduplication effectiveness of disabling kernel randomization and the statistical defense provided by the kernel randomization protection. The approach followed by KASLR-MT is similar to how the virtual addresses of userspace libraries are randomized by some major operating systems (e.g., Windows and Mac OS), i.e., using a per-boot ASLR scheme: a random system-wide value is computed once at system startup, and it is used to calculate the virtual address where libraries are loaded at. This random value is not changed until the next system reboot. Similarly, our design uses a random key, which determines the guest kernel memory layout, for all the virtual machines of a tenant until the moment when the last one shuts down. However, with per-boot userspace ASLR, a local attacker already knows the address space layout of the target application because it is also mapped in the address space of the attacker process. This is not the case for KASLR-MT because, from the attacker's point of view, the victim's kernel memory layout remains random and unknown. For this reason, KASLR-MT offers the same protection as KASLR. Further details can be found in section 5.8.

5.7 KASLR-MT Linux Implementation

In this section, we present the KASLR-MT implementation in the Linux kernel based on the results of section 5.5.

Table 5.2 show the randomization approach followed by KASLR-MT to maximize the deduplication sharing rate in the Linux kernel. Following this approach, it is expected to obtain a memory sharing rate similar to that obtained when kernel randomization is disabled. As discussed in Section 5.5, the randomization of the kernel base physical address has a slight influence on the vmemmap memory region. However, since this impact is low, we consider that it is not worth to randomize this address Per-Tenant for our implementation. This threshold could be different in some cases depending on the requirements of the cloud infrastructure provider. For example, an exigent provider with a high priority on memory sharing might consider that even those regions with low impact should be randomized Per-Tenant. The flexible design of KASLR-MT allows an easy adjustment of this configuration in the implementation according to the needs of each provider.

Code 5.2: Modifications to the current `find_random_virt_addr()` function of the Linux kernel to enable KASLR-MT to generate a deterministic kernel memory layout.

```

776 static unsigned long find_random_virt_addr(...)
778 {
...
791     slots = (KERNEL_IMAGE_SIZE - minimum - image_size) /
792             CONFIG_PHYSICAL_ALIGN + 1;
793
--     random_addr = kaslr_get_random_long("Virtual") % slots;
++     if (kaslrmt_enabled)
++         random_addr = kaslrmt_prn[0];
++     else
++         random_addr = kaslr_get_random_long("Virtual") % slots;
798
799     return random_addr * CONFIG_PHYSICAL_ALIGN + minimum;
800 }
```

Table 5.2: KASLR-MT randomization approach for the different Linux kernel memory base addresses.

Kernel Base Addresses	Randomization
Kernel Physical Address	Per-VM
Kernel Virtual Address	Per-Tenant
Physical Direct Mapping	Per-VM
Vmalloc/ioremap	Per-VM
Vmemmap	Per-Tenant
Modules	Per-Tenant

To communicate the random key to the guest Linux kernel, we use the kernel's command-line parameters, passing directly its corresponding key value. Since Linux normally prints the contents of the `cmdline` to the kernel ring buffer at the beginning of its boot process, we need to retrieve the key and clean-up the `cmdline` buffer before it is printed out, to avoid leaking this information. If the key is leaked, every address being randomized from that key could be calculated.

Once the key is obtained, three addresses need to be produced from it by feeding the Address Producer with the key. Actually, for our proof of concept, we need to get a pseudo-random number per address, which will be used to calculate deterministically the final virtual address. To achieve this in a secure and robust way, we could use a cryptographically secure pseudorandom number generator (CSPRNG), seeding it with the transferred key to produce pseudo-random numbers, or a proper key derivation function (KDF) chain, as used in some encryption algorithms (e.g., AES-GCM-SIV [132]). However, since our purpose is to develop a proof of concept to evaluate our design, we have followed a simple approach to simplify the comprehension, inspired in this kind of algorithms. For final implementations, a CSPRNG must be used in the Address Producer. The general idea is depicted in figure 5.4. After extracting the key from the kernel command-line, a digest of the key itself is calculated by using the `sha1` algorithm, and the result is treated as a pseudo-random number to get the final kernel base virtual address. The same procedure is done two more times, to extract the pseudo-random numbers for obtaining the `vmemmap` address and the `modules` base, incrementing the key by one before the digest calculation. The resulting pseudo-random number has a length of 160 bits, which is greater than the 64 bits obtained by `kaslr_get_random_long()`.

Figure 5.4: Block diagram describing our proof-of-concept implementation of the Address Producer component.

Each pseudo-random number is used instead of a per-region random number. Listing 5.2 exemplifies how the virtual address of the kernel base is obtained, using the KASLR-MT pseudo-random number obtained from the tenant key instead of calling to `kaslr_get_random_long()`. The remaining addresses are calculated similarly.

Regarding the key length, given that we are using the kernel command-line as input method, we consider that keys should use common ascii alphanumeric characters. However, keys should have enough entropy to resist brute force attacks against a leaked kernel address. If a kernel address is leaked, an attacker could be able to recover the key by brute forcing the hash algorithm. Based on that the maximum entropy that can be obtained through `get_random_bytes()` is 64 bits, we consider this value as a proper entropy for a KASLR-MT key value. In addition, we want to use common printable ascii characters, avoiding the space and DEL characters. Therefore, the valid ascii characters are from value 0x21 ('!') until value 0x7e ('~'). This is a total of 94 characters in our alphabet of valid characters for a key. Considering a desired entropy of 64 bits, the key size must be at least 10 characters:

$$x * \log_2(94) = 64 \rightarrow x \approx 9.76$$

5.8 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate the memory deduplication effectiveness of KASLR-MT as well as the security considerations.

5.8.1 Memory Deduplication Savings

In order to measure how much kernel memory is being saved by deduplication with KASLR-MT compared with Linux KASLR, we have launched another experiment, running from 2 to 30 simultaneous virtual machines belonging to the same tenant and running in the same host. The experiments were conducted with a single tenant to observe the effectiveness of KASLR-MT among virtual machines sharing memory within a particular group (see Chapter 4). For this reason, it is not necessary to compare memory sharing of different tenants since Slicedup prevents the sharing of memory between VMs of different groups/tenants. Each virtual machine configuration is the same as used in section 5.5, a generic GNU/Linux Ubuntu 19.04 with Linux v5.0.6, with Gnome desktop and full networking (NAT mode provided by Qemu). The physical machine used to run the experiments has an Intel Xeon W-2155 processor (Skylake server

(a) Redundant memory running different simultaneous kernels. (b) Redundant memory split per kernel region, for 30 kernels.

Figure 5.5: On the left, 5.5a shows the total percentage of redundant memory running from 2 to 30 kernels simultaneously. On the right, the case with 30 kernels is split per kernel memory region and 5.5b shows the percentage of redundant memory for each region. The guest kernels run Linux v5.0.6 for the x86_64 architecture.

microarchitecture) and 32 GiB of SDRAM memory. The hypervisor used is KVM (Linux kernel 4.19-ARCH) along with Qemu VMM version 4.0.0.

Userspace activities modify the kernel state (changes in data structures as existing processes, open files, etc.). Inevitably, even though these alterations are not related with kernel randomization, they are present in the measurements. The possible combinations of userspace workloads are endless. For this reason, virtual machines run the GNU/Linux Ubuntu distribution in the experiment with the aim of obtaining a real environment with a representative userland workload. However, since the scope of this chapter is to study the effects that kernel randomization has in memory contents, memory pages belonging to userland should be discarded.

Figure 5.5a shows the resulting percentage of redundant memory for each case. With only two kernels, if kernel randomization is enabled there is a 27.65% of redundant memory, which increases to 45.09% by disabling it. With our solution, the value obtained is close to the latter, a 44.02%. The percentage increases logarithmically as more kernel memories are added, until they approach a theoretical limit, where the curve grows slower. However, when kernel randomization is enabled, the curve has less slope; this is caused by a greater number of pages with matchless contents. This limit is approximately 70% when kernel randomization is not enabled, 67% in our solution, and 35% when kernel randomization is enabled.

Taking a stabilized case, for example with 30 kernels, we have split the memories of all the kernels by region, as shown in figure 5.5b. From it, we can confirm which are the kernel regions benefiting from our solution. The Linux code region gets exactly the same sharing as when kernel randomization is disabled, while the Linux data region (including `.data`, `.bss` and other data sections) is close, with only 2.7% of sharing loss. The modules code and data regions are also benefiting despite the fact that the loading order factor, which is independent of kernel randomization, is affecting their contents similarity (elucidated in section 5.9). Similarly, `vmemmap` can share a 34.9% of its contents with our solution, an 8.3% less than when kernel randomization is disabled; but still a good portion, considering that its contents are almost entirely matchless (0.2%) when kernel randomization is enabled. With regard to `vmalloc`, we can see that it has similar redundant memory, independently of kernel randomization.

Consequently, Figure 5.5b shows that KASLR-MT provides good memory sharing results close to the best case scenario (i.e., having standard KASLR disabled). Thus, it achieves the goal of increasing memory savings while keeping security levels equivalent to having standard KASLR enabled.

5.8.2 Security Considerations

Regarding security implications of KASLR-MT, it extends the memory saving benefits keeping the protection provided by KASLR. Therefore, the memory deduplication savings are restored back without disabling the kernel randomization, enabling Linux systems to have both, high ratios of memory savings and security.

The trade-off for more memory sharing is to share akin kernel address space layouts among virtual machines belonging to the same group. Effectively, this solution maintains an equivalent protection offered by kernel randomization. On the one hand, it protects against external attackers including network applications interacting with the kernel and unknown tenants running virtual machines in the same host machine, since the kernel memory layout for these attackers is still unknown as with standard KASLR. On the other hand, attacks from those virtual machines that share the same kernel address space layout are equivalent to local

attacks (userspace applications attacking its own kernel). In all of these cases, the kernel memory layout is unpredictable from the attacker perspective.

There is a case where KASLR-MT has a drawback: an attacker successfully bypassing the kernel randomization of a particular machine will be able to use that leak to bypass the kernel randomization of another machine belonging to the same tenant. However, the effort required to bypass KASLR-MT is the same as KASLR.

5.9 Discussion

In this section, we discuss some affairs that have not been thoroughly detailed for being out of scope.

As advanced in previous sections, the loading order of Linux loadable modules is not deterministic. We are focusing on the kernel's automatic module loader at boot time, without explicit user/administrator action once the system is running [133]. Linux can perform the module auto-loading in two different ways: by using hardware-driven mechanisms sending events to userland daemons (e.g., udev) when hardware is discovered, or by using an older mechanism that uses the `request_module()` kernel function to load the module from userspace. In all cases, this job is done when a certain module is needed and has not yet been loaded. This is common for device drivers compiled as modules.

Most of the cases, modules auto-loading is done asynchronously, exploiting the advantages of parallelism to increase performance. As a consequence, even if kernel randomization is disabled, a similar effect occurs in the code and data memory regions of the modules, caused by the intrinsic randomization derived from the unpredictability of their loading order.

Boot 1		Boot 2	
Module	Virtual Address	Module	Virtual Address
floppy	0xffffffffc0002000	floppy	0xffffffffc0002000
pata_acpi	0xffffffffc0017000	pata_acpi	0xffffffffc0017000
i2c_piix4	0xffffffffc001c000	i2c_piix4	0xffffffffc001c000
e1000	0xffffffffc002f000 →	← e1000	0xffffffffc0028000
ip_tables	0xffffffffc0052000	autofs4	0xffffffffc004b000
psmouse	0xffffffffc005b000	psmouse	0xffffffffc005b000
autofs4	0xffffffffc0081000 →	← x_tables	0xffffffffc0086000
x_tables	0xffffffffc008d000	ip_tables	0xffffffffc0097000
sch_fq_codel	0xffffffffc00b8000	sch_fq_codel	0xffffffffc00b7000
irqbypass	0xffffffffc0178000	qemu_fw_cfg	0xffffffffc0172000
joydev	0xffffffffc017f000 →	← irqbypass	0xffffffffc0178000
mac_hid	0xffffffffc019b000	mac_hid	0xffffffffc01a3000
serio_raw	0xffffffffc01c3000	serio_raw	0xffffffffc01b8000
input_leds	0xffffffffc01e0000	input_leds	0xffffffffc01c1000
crct10dif_pclmul	0xffffffffc0200000	crct10dif_pclmul	0xffffffffc01c6000
nfit	0xffffffffc0205000	crc32_pclmul	0xffffffffc01fe000
qemu_fw_cfg	0xffffffffc0237000	joydev	0xffffffffc020e000
crc32_pclmul	0xffffffffc0266000	kvm	0xffffffffc024b000
kvm	0xffffffffc026b000	nfit	0xffffffffc076f000
kvm_intel	0xffffffffc092d000	kvm_intel	0xffffffffc08e2000

Figure 5.6: Name and final virtual address of a list of modules being auto-loaded into the Linux kernel at boot time, for two different kernel boots, without enabling kernel randomization. The loading order is not preserved across boots.

Furthermore, taking into account that the list and number of modules being loaded into a kernel may vary depending on the task in which it is involved, even if a pre-established loading order is determined for a certain group of Linux modules, the boundless variety of different possible modules makes it a complex issue.

Figure 5.6 compares a list of modules being auto-loaded into the Linux kernel at boot time for two different kernel boots (*boot 1* and *boot 2*) when the kernel randomization is fully disabled. There are modules loaded in different positions and virtual addresses. For example, the `ip_tables` is loaded in position 5 in *boot 1* and in position 8 in *boot 2*, resulting in different virtual addresses where they have been loaded. A situation that could seem unexpected is when a module is loaded in the same position in both boots but in different virtual address. An example is the module `e1000`, where the base address in *boot 1* is `0xffffffffc002f000` and `0xffffffffc0028000` in *boot 2*.

This behavior alters modules memory contents in a similar way as kernel randomization does. As a consequence, all their absolute references (in code and data) will not be equal when different kernel memories are compared.

Therefore, even fully disabling the kernel randomization, the load order module and addresses where they are allocated are not the same across different kernel reboots. The asynchronous userspace module loading requests provide a flexible and time saving boot time but, unfortunately, it also reduces the memory sharing rate.

As a future work, having modules compiled and linked as position-independent code (PIC) could alleviate this issue. Unfortunately, current Linux versions do not support PIC and an analysis to obtain the real benefit would be necessary since, as we have discussed, modules also contain references to other kernel parts that can break the memory sharing. Furthermore, other considerations must be taken into account, for example whether the modules are randomized as solid blocks or at a finer granularity, e.g. per-function. In the latter case, it would not be enough only to use position-independent code. This issue is discussed in more detail in the next chapter.

5.10 Conclusions

In this chapter, we presented KASLR-MT. This solution is intended to be beneficial in multi-tenant cloud systems, where several tenants are owners of one or more groups of virtual machines, and all of them share the resources of a single physical machine by the use of virtualization technologies. Therefore, KASLR-MT is a new Linux kernel randomization design for multi-tenant cloud systems, compatible with memory deduplication, which maximizes memory savings rate while providing a strong security.

We identified why the most widely and effective technique used to mitigate attacks at kernel level, KASLR, fails to provide protection and shareability at the same time. To design KASLR-MT, we performed a deep analysis on how kernel randomization affects to the shared memory. Then, we propose KASLR-MT, the first effective and practical Kernel ASLR memory protection that maximizes the memory deduplication savings rate while providing a strong security.

We have implemented and tested KASLR-MT in the Linux kernel and our results showed that KASLR-MT is flexible, highly scalable and maximizes the memory savings rate while providing a strong security.

Chapter 6

Extending KASLR-MT to Function-Granular Randomization

In the previous chapter, the impact of standard kernel randomization on the memory deduplication sharing effectiveness has been thoroughly explored, and KASLR-MT has been proposed as a solution to this problem. Due to the relentless struggle between attackers and defenders over the cybersecurity landscape, both attack techniques and defensive countermeasures are continuously evolving. Kernel randomization is an example of defensive security mechanism that keeps evolving today.

Function-Granular KASLR aims to be the next step in the near future for the kernel randomization mechanism because it provides much more security than current kernel randomization approaches. Some kernel hardening implementations include this feature by randomly shuffling kernel and modules functions.

Unfortunately, function-granular kernel randomization also impacts significantly on the effectiveness and potential benefits of memory deduplication. Both function-granular kernel randomization and memory deduplication are desired and beneficial; the first for the strong protection it gives, and the second for the reduction of costs in terms of memory consumption.

In this chapter, we analyze the impact of function-granular kernel randomization on memory deduplication revealing why it cannot offer maximum security and shareability of memory simultaneously. We also discuss the reasons why having a full position independent kernel code counter-intuitively does not solve the problem introducing a challenge to kernel randomization designers.

To solve these problems, we propose a function-granular kernel randomization modification for cloud systems that extends the KASLR-MT design of the previous chapter and enables full function-granular kernel randomization while reduces memory deduplication cancellations to almost zero.

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6.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, we discussed that randomizing big chunks of kernel memory has a significant impact on the effectiveness of memory deduplication. Randomizing major memory blocks is the approach followed by almost all current operating systems. However, since the complexity of the attacks increases as more defense mechanisms are introduced, in some cases this approach is insufficient and can be bypassed, such as with info-leaks [134, 135].

An information leakage or *info-leak* is the result of the exploitation of a vulnerability that allows the attacker to disclose a secret from a memory area, either its content or its location [136]. Attackers typically need to conduct info-leaks to know the targeted memory layout before continuing with subsequent stages of an attack. Without an info-leak, all attacks that require prior knowledge of valid addresses are severely hindered. The importance of providing protection against this type of attacks along with the lack of protection against them in current security mechanisms has motivated the emergence of new proposals to satisfy these needs.

Function-Granular Kernel Address Space Layout Randomization (FG-KASLR) [137] is a novel feature that adds more protection to the widely adopted kernel randomization security mechanism. With it, kernel and modules functions are independently randomized, increasing the entropy of the kernel memory mapping and thus significantly reducing the negative impact of a possible information leak. For that reason, it is a desired kernel hardening technique that is expected to become a mainstream feature in all major operating systems in the near future.

Unfortunately, function-granular kernel randomization introduces new challenges to cost-effective resource management. As with the randomization of major memory blocks seen in the previous chapter, function-granular randomization introduces sub-page content modifications leading to a prohibitive memory overhead due to the memory deduplication cancellation in cloud systems. Since it is not recommended disabling security protections such as kernel randomization, cloud providers will sustain a forfeit of memory resources.

To overcome this problem, we analyze the impact of function-granular kernel randomization on memory deduplication, and we identify why other approaches fail to finally propose a solution that maintains the levels of security provided by the function-granular kernel randomization protection mechanism while reducing the memory deduplication cancellation to almost zero.

6.2 Assumptions and Attacker Model

In the section 5.6 of the previous chapter, we discussed that disabling kernel randomization in order to have an effective memory deduplication is not a real option since it introduces serious weaknesses that could compromise the full cloud provider. Randomizing the kernel is important to mitigate the exploitation of vulnerabilities relying on knowing kernel virtual memory addresses. Without kernel randomization, attacks exploiting those vulnerabilities will always be successful, since those kernel addresses are not a secret that the attackers need to obtain.

In cloud environments, where there are several virtual machines that can directly or indirectly interact with each other, this is even more risky. Any kernel vulnerability could compromise all guest virtual machines of the entire cloud, even if the guests live in different physical machines. In that case, attackers do not need to conduct any prior attack to determine the location of the kernel in memory. The location is well known and the attack will always succeed.

On the other hand, even under the assumption that the protection provided by kernel randomization is present, we must also consider info-leaks, a widely used attack approach to bypass kernel randomization. Info-leak attacks can bypass current kernel randomization models since the leak of a single address discloses the location of an entire region. For this reason, it is imperative to provide protection against this kind of attacks, to minimize the attack surface of an info-leak, and thus to mitigate its consequences and to enhance the security provided by the kernel randomization technique.

Therefore, the scope and the goal of our research is to provide a function-granular kernel randomization protection that mitigates info-leak attacks while minimizing to a negligible extent its impact on memory deduplication. This will enable cloud providers to use the protection provided by the newest and more secure kernel randomization techniques without losing the benefits of memory deduplication. It is hard or impossible to assume that operating systems are free from info-leak attacks. Recently, an info-leak in the Linux kernel through 5.7.6 was disclosed under the CVE-2020-15393 identifier [138]. Hence, a practical and effective solution should consider info-leak attacks.

Additionally, our threat model assumes that a local attacker has or can easily get full control of an entire virtual machine and therefore we aim to protect virtual machines of a particular tenant from other tenants and from the Internet. Hence, our goal is that attackers that exploit a kernel vulnerability from remote machines or from virtual machines pertaining to other tenants face the full kernel randomization protection, while keeping the impact on memory deduplication to the minimum. In the event of a successful info-leak attack, the information extracted by the attacker must be insufficient to know the complete layout of the affected kernel memory region.

The scenario is similar to the one shown in section 5.2 of the previous chapter, but this time we must provide protection against info-leaks. Refreshing Figure 5.1, it showed the overview of the described attacker model. The hypervisor is running three virtual machines, two of which (VM-1 and VM-2) belong to one tenant (T1), and the third (VM-3) belongs to another tenant (T2). Attacks from remote machines and from other tenants are covered by the attacker model. It is assumed that virtual machines pertaining to the same tenant trust each other so if one of them is compromised, the others are susceptible to being attacked.

6.3 Linux Function-Granular Kernel Randomization

As discussed above, kernel randomization is an important security mechanism that is currently present in all main operating systems. Although their different implementation may vary, all of them follow a similar pattern that consists of randomizing both physical and virtual address where the kernel is loaded. For example, the kernel randomization implementation of the currently recent Linux versions randomizes only the base addresses of several parts of the kernel, such as the kernel code and data, which are loaded as a block at a random position, but no randomization is applied between the code and data memory areas. The same applies to the other randomized kernel memory regions, which are each entirely randomized as a single block. From now on, we will refer to this approach as *coarse-grained* kernel randomization.

Since the randomization is applied at boot time and unchanged until next reboot, any info-leak disclosing a specific chunk of a kernel memory region is actually uncovering the location of the entire kernel memory region, thus circumventing the KASLR protection for that particular region. In this regard, even if a given kernel randomization implementation has an extremely high entropy, a single info-leak cancels it out completely, reducing it to zero. Following the previous

example, a single info-leak revealing an address pertaining to either the code or the data regions will immediately de-randomize both memory areas. In that case, the KASLR bypass will be effective until next reboot [60, 61]. For this reason, a finer-grained kernel randomization is needed to address such challenges.

Function-granular kernel randomization, also known as function re-ordering, is the next step in the progression of defense mechanisms against respective attack strategies characteristic in cybersecurity research. With function-granular kernel randomization, the kernel and modules functions are randomly shuffled at boot time. Unlike the coarse-grained approach, an info-leak will only de-randomize a very tiny portion of the kernel code or data and will not be valid to de-randomize important functions that attackers typically used to elevate privileges or build return-oriented programming (ROP) attacks. Figure 6.1 shows a general outline of this concept, where kernel functions are independently randomized by the bootloader at boot-time using a random number generator (RNG).

Function-granular kernel randomization provides not only more entropy but also mitigates info-leaks and correlation attacks [139]. For this reason, it is to be expected that the trend of the kernel randomization protection will be towards a finer grained approach. For example, Linux is currently undergoing early stages of development of a finer-grained kernel randomization approach named Function Granular Kernel Address Space Layout Randomization

Table 6.1: Randomization elements in Linux. All of them must be randomized to have a full and function-granular kernel randomization.

Randomization Elements	Description
Kernel Physical Address	Randomizes the physical address where the kernel is loaded.
Kernel Virtual Address	Randomizes the virtual address where the kernel is loaded.
Function Reordering	Randomizes the kernel and modules <i>per-function</i> .
Modules Base	Randomizes the base virtual address where modules are loaded.
Physical Direct Mapping	Randomizes the virtual memory address where physical memory resides.
Vmalloc/ioremap	Randomizes the base address where the kernel allocates dynamic memory.
Vmemmap	Randomizes the base address of the Kernel virtual memory map.
Poking	Randomizes the special virtual address used to patch kernel code dynamically.

Figure 6.1: General outline of kernel function-granular randomization. The order of kernel functions is dynamically shuffled at boot-time, before the kernel starts its execution.

(FG-KASLR) [137, 140]. This new technique is a step forward for kernel security and it would likely be adopted by other operating systems in the near future.

The implementation of the Linux kernel randomization have been evolving over time. The first randomization additions in the kernel were introduced in version 3.14, in which the physical and virtual addresses were randomized, along with the modules load offset. Later, from version 4.8, kernel physical and virtual addresses were decoupled and randomized separately and three more memory regions were randomized: the physical memory mapping, `vmalloc` and virtual memory map (the third was added in version 4.9). The last addition was the randomization of the poking address, introduced in version 5.2. This address is used to patch dynamically a running kernel without having to reboot. It is useful to get a highly flexible and adaptable kernel without having to compile different versions depending on the available hardware, such as the number of CPUs.

The first *request for comments* (RFC) patch for function-granular kernel randomization was for the version 5.5, in early 2020 and still under discussion at the time of writing this thesis [137, 140]. The current implementation of the Linux kernel is not PIC compliant. It uses text relocations, patching dynamically all the position-dependent references after the final randomized virtual address is settled. The relocation information is generated by the static linker. Then, the linker generated output binary is parsed for relocation information and symbol locations, and generates a simple table of addresses which contain relocations which will need to be adjusted once the final base address of the kernel is determined at boot time.

FG-KASLR follows the same approach going a step further. It uses an existing compiler option to place functions into individual executable code sections at build time. Section header information about these sections is preserved in the final output binary as part of the kernel build process. These section headers contain the address ranges of each individual function that was not collected back into the main executable code segment. The address ranges are used to randomly shuffle and re-layout the kernel image at boot time. After that, relocation information is consulted to patch up the corresponding references.

Previously with simple base address layout randomization, the table of relocations appended to the kernel image during the build process only needed to include absolute relocations and relocations that were relative to other segments which were not moved. Because the relative location of symbols in sections that have been randomized has been changed, the generated table of relocations is substantially expanded to include relative relocations. Each relocation entry in an address range that has been randomized must be updated to reflect the code section's new location. In addition, the Linux kernel creates several data tables of addresses. These tables are inspected and adjusted to reflect any changes in addresses. Most of these tables are required to be sorted by address so that the kernel can do fast table lookups using a *bsearch* algorithm. After the addresses have been adjusted, each table will need to be re-sorted.

FG-KASLR extends the kernel randomization by adding a new step when loading the kernel. After randomizing the kernel base address, the loader is responsible for randomly shuffle the functions order. The same approach is used for loadable modules. As a result, it is required to randomize eight different addresses/offsets/components (*randomization elements*) to have a full FG-KASLR as table 6.1 shows.

Although FG-KASLR is a novel and desired hardening technique that brings stronger security to the Linux kernel randomization mechanism, unfortunately, it re-introduces the important

issue of memory deduplication cancellation that KASLR-MT managed with coarse-grained kernel randomization. Section 6.4 discusses in detail how and why function-granular kernel randomization cancels the KSM benefits.

6.4 The Problem: Relative Offsets

Kernel randomization can cause undesired effects on the memory sharing effectiveness, especially in virtualized systems. In this section, we discuss the conflict between memory deduplication in the host machine and function-granular kernel randomization in the guest virtual machines.

In the previous chapter, we discussed the problem that affects memory sharing and the efficient utilization of memory resources when deduplication mechanisms such as KSM are combined with address randomization security mechanisms such as KASLR, especially in environments that rely on virtualization technologies. We also provided solutions for the standard coarse-grained kernel randomization approach. However, motivated by info-leak attacks, newer and more secure kernel randomization are being proposed. Function-granular kernel randomization is an example of this and the technique is currently being tested in the Linux hardened community.

As of the date of writing this thesis and to the best of the authors' knowledge, KASLR-MT is the only design that solves the problem of memory deduplication breakage in the presence of kernel randomization in cloud systems without compromising the security of users. However, with the appearance of function-granular kernel randomization, the problem re-emerges with new challenges.

In standard kernel randomization, the absolute references breaks shareability when the kernel is randomized due to text relocations, dynamically patching, etc (seen in section 5.4). The kernel code is the most affected memory area and this is because all kernel code pages that are dynamically patched by absolute relocations at boot-time cannot be merged. An example that causes this is when a certain kernel function references another one. Unfortunately, this approach randomizes the kernel regions as entire blocks and info-leak attacks will fully bypass the kernel randomization.

In this case, the main culprit is the utilization of absolute relocations. For the currently used coarse-grained kernel randomization, where kernel regions are randomized as entire blocks, alternatives such as compiling the kernel with position-independent code could provide additional benefits and alleviate the problem, because the use of relative offsets in this case do not change the memory contents regardless of the address where the code is loaded.

The main challenge with function granular kernel randomization that invalidates previous solutions is that randomly reordering kernel functions will produce different code. Since function-granular kernel randomization dynamically shuffles the order in which the functions are placed, the relative distance from a given function to another will be different and, therefore, the relocation patch will alter the memory contents. It is important to note that the relative offsets are a problem even if the kernel developers adapt their code to be PIC compliant. Therefore, it is an important problem that cloud providers must overcome, to which there is no available solution at this time.

Since the relative distance between functions is not determined at compile time, function-granular kernel randomization uses more relocations than the coarse-grained kernel randomization. Once all functions are randomly loaded into memory, relative offsets such as those used for calling functions must be relocated. As an illustrative note, the compiled image of the kernel contains approximately 849000 more relocations only by enabling function-granular kernel randomization.

This problem not only affects to code but also to the sharing of data memory. This is because the differences caused by randomization affect data variables when their contents depend on the location of any randomized region being referenced. For example, a function pointer in the kernel data region containing the virtual address of a shuffled function. The kernel contains different structures with pointers referencing to other kernel locations (e.g., functions and variables). Consequently, a single value or pointer that refers to a randomized location breaks the shareability of the entire page. This issue concerns all kernel memory regions containing any kind of data, such as vmalloc, vmemmap and module data.

Figure 6.2 sketches an example of the problem. It shows a snippet of the memory of two identical kernels with function-granular kernel randomization. Alternatively, it can also be seen as two different boots of the same kernel, since the changes in memory contents occur in the same manner. The example shows the memory content of two functions and a data variable. One of the functions calls the other and later it accesses to the variable in the kernel data region. The most relevant part is the opcode value of the instructions because that is the actual content present in memory. It can be seen in red, that the bytecode value of Boot 1 (dbffffff) is different from the byte code value of Boot 2 (15000000). Those bytecode differences are because the distance between the next instruction and the destination is different (different relative offsets).

This is produced when the function-granular randomization shuffles the order in which the functions are loaded. Therefore, the relative distances within a given block are no longer constant. This concerns both distances to other functions and data. To the left of figure 6.2, the callee function is loaded first at the virtual address 0x1135 followed by the caller function at (0x1148). The relative offset in the instruction that calls to callee is -37 bytes

Figure 6.2: Example of memory contents altered by different relative offsets, showing a snippet of the memory of two identical kernels with function-granular kernel randomization. The code represents a `caller()` function that calls another, `callee()`, and accesses a data variable (`data_var`). Because of function-granular kernel randomization, the order of both functions is shuffled at boot-time. Consequently, memory contents differ because the relative offsets are not constant, which breaks their shareability.

(backwards), and the distance between the data access instruction and the location of the accessed variable is 3738 bytes. On the right, the order of the functions has been shuffled and the caller function is loaded first at 0x1135 followed by callee at 0x115c. The relative offsets are now 21 bytes (forward) to the callee function and 3757 bytes to the data variable.

These alterations in memory contents are the root of the problem and prevents KSM to merge those pages. Although the figure shows only changes in memory contents of kernel code, the problem is also present in data regions. For example, a data variable containing the virtual address of the callee function, since this address is different (0x1135 on the left and 0x115c on the right) the variable value in data region will be different. In fact, the problem exists whether this data reference is absolute or relative. It is important to note that, in this illustrative scenario, the first function is always loaded at the same base virtual address for the sake of simplicity. However, the base address of the kernel memory region where the first function is loaded is also randomized.

Therefore, function-granular kernel randomization affects the shareability of kernel memory contents, preventing KSM to merge kernel code and data regions. Even though current Linux kernel implementation is not PIC compliant, there is a widespread presence of instructions with relative offsets, especially on architectures such as x86_64 and ARM with support for calculating addresses relative to the program counter (PC), also known as PC-relative addressing support. Listing 6.1 shows a few real x86_64 instructions with relative offsets extracted from the Linux v5.5, which confirms that the Linux kernel is affected by the problem. The relative offsets are highlighted and their meaning is detailed through the comments, indicating the subtraction of the destination and the address of the next instruction. For example, the first shown instruction is a Load Effective Address (`leaq`) instruction, which is the first instruction executed when the kernel starts running. This instruction loads the address 0xffffffff82803f58

Code 6.1: Samples of affected x86_64 machine instructions with relative offsets, extracted from the Linux kernel v5.5 binary. The offsets in the instructions' opcode are highlighted in bold to indicate the part of the contents that changes when the functions are shuffled.

```

0xffffffff81000000 <startup_64>:
0xffffffff81000000:  48 8d 25 51 3f 80 01  leaq  0x1803f51(%rip), %rsp
# dst: 0xffffffff82803f58; rip: 0xffffffff81000007; rel. offset: dst - rip = 0x1803f51

0xffffffff81000007:  e8 e4 00 00 00      callq ffffffff810000f0 <verify_cpu>
# dst: 0xffffffff810000f0; rip: 0xffffffff8100000c; rel. offset: dst - rip = 0xe4
...
0xffffffff81000020:  eb 20              jmp   ffffffff81000042 <secondary_startup_64+0x12>
# dst: 0xffffffff81000042; rip: 0xffffffff81000022; rel. offset: dst - rip = 0x20
...
0xffffffff81000030 <secondary_startup_64>:
...
0xffffffff81000047:  f7 05 8f 2b 63 01 01 00 00 00  testl $0x1, 0x1632b8f(%rip)
# dst: 0xffffffff82632be0; rip: 0xffffffff81000051; rel. offset: dst - rip = 0x1632b8f
...
0xffffffff8100005c:  48 03 05 ad 1f 81 01  add  0x1811fad(%rip), %rax
# dst: 0xffffffff82812010; rip: 0xffffffff81000063; rel. offset: dst - rip = 0x1811fad
...
0xffffffff810000a0:  48 8b 25 a1 68 92 01  mov  0x19268a1(%rip), %rsp
# dst: 0xffffffff82926948; rip: 0xffffffff810000a7; rel. offset: dst - rip = 0x19268a1
...
0xffffffff82e63131 <vmemmap_pte_populate>:
...
0xffffffff82e631de:  48 23 35 4b d8 ae ff  and  -0x5127b5(%rip), %rsi
# dst: 0xffffffff82950a30; rip: 0xffffffff82e631e5; rel. offset: dst - rip = 0xffaed84b (2's)

```

into the `rsp` register. Since the address of the next instruction is `0xffffffff81000007`, the relative offset (`0x1803f51`) is the distance between them. It reveals that the problem affects any instruction that computes a distance relative to its position, regardless of its semantics. This clearly points out that PIC code does not solve the problem.

Memory deduplication and function-granular kernel randomization could actually coexist in a system but, in practice, the deduplication is silently failing. Therefore, knowing the impact of function-granular kernel randomization on deduplication is key to know the extent of the problem and to propose a practical solution.

6.5 Function-Granular Randomization Impact

Function-granular kernel randomization produces different memory contents across several kernels, reducing the effectiveness of memory deduplication in cloud systems using virtualization technologies. In this section, we present a comprehensive analysis of that randomization impact on memory deduplication for each affected kernel memory region.

Our aim for this section is to measure rigorously to what extent a particular kernel region (Linux code, Linux data, modules code, modules data, `vmalloc` and `vmemmap`) changes its contents when different randomization elements of function-granular kernel randomization are enabled (kernel physical address, kernel virtual address, function reordering, modules base, physical mapping, `vmalloc`, `vmemmap` and poking virtual address). Given that there are eight randomization elements, we have tested and analyzed $2^8 = 256$ combinations per each kernel memory region. We have executed 4 probes per each combination, being a total of $256 * 4 = 1024$ executions. Then, the percentage of equal pages can be obtained by comparing the probes for each given combination. The OS used for executing the tests is Ubuntu 20.04 LTS with Linux v5.5.

By doing this analysis, we accurately identify **1) the influence** of function-granular kernel randomization for each combination, to identify which randomization elements have more impact on the effectiveness of memory deduplication; **2) the best combination** that maximizes the security provided by kernel randomization while minimizing the negative effects on memory deduplication. This will be key to identify which randomization elements have minimum impact on memory deduplication. As we will discuss later in our proposed approach, those elements can be randomized due to their low or negligible impact. Finally, we obtain **3) non-biased results** that are independent of the amount of virtual machines executed in the experiment. Otherwise, the results obtained might be influenced by merely tweaking a certain number of virtual machines. For example, supposing that 50% of the total memory can be saved when running two identical kernels, then adding a third kernel identical to the others would report 66% of memory saved by deduplication. Although that measure indicates actual memory savings, it is not adequate to determine the real impact of the effects produced by function-granular kernel randomization.

For these reasons, instead of calculating the differences of deduplicated memory before and after randomization, we measure the degree of memory contents variation of the kernel memory regions after applying randomization. By doing this, memory contents that are not influenced by kernel randomization and therefore do not contribute to the measurement are excluded to avoid errors in the measurement of the percentage of equal memory pages. An example of such excluded content are memory pages filled with zeros.

Table 6.2: Analysis of the impact that function-granular kernel randomization has on the shareability of Linux memory regions. A black dot (●) indicates that the randomization element is enabled, while a white dot (○) indicates that the randomization element is disabled. The table is divided into six kernel memory regions. For each kernel memory region, the best combination for the memory deduplication when enabling the highest number of randomization elements is highlighted in green background.

Linux Kernel Memory Regions	Randomization Elements								% Equal Pages
	poking vaddr.	vmemmap area	vmalloc/ioremap	physical mapping	modules base	function reordering	kernel vaddr.	kernel paddr.	
Linux Code	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	100
	●	●	●	●	●	○	○	●	100 (-0.0)
	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	0.1 (-99.9)
Linux Data	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	82.5
	●	●	●	●	●	○	○	●	81.5 (-1.0)
	●	●	●	●	●	○	●	●	49.9 (-32.6)
	●	●	●	●	●	●	○	●	44.3 (-38.2)
Modules Code	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	33.3
	●	●	●	●	○	○	○	●	31.3 (-2.0)
	●	●	●	●	●	○	●	●	8.6 (-24.7)
Modules Data	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	51.2
	●	●	●	●	○	○	○	●	49.8 (-1.4)
	●	●	●	●	○	○	●	●	40.6 (-10.6)
	●	●	●	●	●	○	●	●	35.8 (-15.4)
Vmalloc Space	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	5.0
	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	4.0 (-1.0)
Virtual Memory Map	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	88.2
	●	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	83.1 (-5.1)
	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	0.0 (-88.2)

Therefore, we focus on calculating the percentage of equal pages for each case, independently of the size of the kernel memory region being analyzed. This measure is particularly tailored to measure the impact caused by randomizing kernel areas exclusively, and thus recognizing memory pages that change because of the kernel randomization by comparing two or more memory dumps of the same object. To eliminate non-randomization noise in the measurements, local redundancy of each object is not taken into account when determining the percentage of equal pages. This accurately determines how memory pages are changed due to kernel randomization.

It is important to note that although the analysis shows the results of the Linux kernel code and data regions separated, they are not actually separately randomized in current implementations. Both regions are randomized together in accordance with the obtained kernel virtual address. Apart from that, as a feature of function-granular kernel randomization, the order of the code functions is randomly shuffled.

On the other hand, the Linux direct physical mapping is a fairly special case. It is not actually a real memory region, but a virtual mapping to the entire physical memory. For this reason, the physmap cannot be treated as a virtual memory region with contents and it is discarded in the tests. However, it is included as a randomization element because, although it is purely a virtual mapping, its virtual base address is randomized and this can influence one or more kernel memory regions if they contain values that refer to the randomized virtual address of the direct physical mapping. An example of these references are pointers to dynamically allocated physically contiguous memory areas.

Another important aspect to consider is the page table size. Although Linux kernel guests use 2 MiB pages, the Linux implementation of memory deduplication (KSM) operates with pages of 4 KiB, regardless of the guest's view. In our analysis, we consider that the block size to be compared is 4 KiB, as this is the minimum block size in which KSM operates. As a result, a single bit difference in a 4 KiB block is reported as a mismatch of the entire page, since KSM could not merge it.

Because the total number of combinations obtained in the analysis is too large to be listed ($256 * 6 = 1536$ rows), table 6.2 shows a synthesis of the most significant cases. The table is primarily divided into the six *Linux kernel memory regions* being analyzed. The first row of each of the six memory regions is the best case for the memory deduplication. This is when the kernel randomization is disabled. The last row is the worst case, where the function-granular kernel randomization is fully enabled (all the randomization elements are enabled). To effectively summarize from 1536 to 22 rows we are not considering cases whose difference in terms of deduplication is less than 5%. This way, the best possible combination for a given configuration can be reached quickly. For example, in a kernel randomization configuration where the kernel virtual address is randomized, table 6.2 shows that the best combination for the Linux data memory region is the third one, with a 32.6% of randomization overhead. For each kernel memory region, the best combination for the memory deduplication when randomizing the highest number of randomization elements is highlighted.

The results of the randomization effects on the Linux code point out that memory sharing of this region is drastically impacted by the kernel virtual address and by the function reordering. When any of these two are randomized, the percentage of equal pages is reduced from 100% to almost zero, independently of whether other areas are randomized or not. Only a small percentage of pages remain unaffected (0.3 and 0.1 respectively). This reveals that the absolute and relative references are widespread across the kernel code. On the one hand,

randomizing the kernel virtual address affects absolute references but not relative ones. This is because even if the kernel is randomized in a coarse-grained way (without function reordering), all memory pages with relocations of absolute addresses break the sharing benefits but relative offsets within the same region are kept intact. On the other hand, the randomization of the functions order not only affects absolute references but also to relative offsets. This is due to the increment of entropy in the order in which kernel functions are placed as figure 6.2 shows.

The results for the Linux data memory region show that the best case (kernel randomization off) has 82.5% of equal pages. As it is a data region, it is expected that this region contains non-shareable data, independent of kernel randomization (e.g., timestamps), so obtaining 82.5% of equal pages as the best case is not a surprise. The Linux data memory region is also impacted by the kernel virtual address and by function reordering. Enabling the rest of randomization elements has a small impact on deduplication, just a 1% of overhead. However, only by randomizing the kernel virtual address, the percentage of equal pages drops to less than 50%. Similarly, deduplication is decreased to around 44% by randomizing the functions order. The reason is that Linux data contains references to parts of the kernel itself (to either code and data regions).

Regarding the Linux loadable modules, it could be expected at first glance to obtain an outcome similar to the Linux kernel code and data regions. However, there is a particular aspect in modules that makes them slightly more complex to analyze. When a module is loaded, all their relative references to other modules are patched and therefore its contents depend on the position of other modules. Since the loading order of Linux loadable modules is not deterministic, those memory patches will produce different memory contents and therefore the percentage of equal pages will be reduced. It is important to note that once a module is loaded in a different address, all subsequent modules will be affected. Unfortunately this is out of control of the kernel randomization and for this reason, the best case when the randomization is disabled only reports a 33.3% of equal pages.

The percentage of equal pages for the modules code is reduced by more than 72%, from 31.3% to 8.6% when the kernel virtual address and/or the modules base offset are randomized. However, the randomization of functions has a much greater impact. In this case, it drops almost entirely down to 0.2%. This case is not shown in the table because the difference with respect to the worst case (which is basically adding the kernel virtual address and modules base offset) is only 0.1% and, therefore, less than the 5% established as a threshold. The reasons of this behavior are the same as with Linux code.

Once a certain module is placed in a memory location randomly assigned to it, and after its functions are shuffled, it is necessary to patch all its relocations. This includes relocations of relative offsets, such as those present in function calls, and relocations of absolute addresses. All of these relocations modify the contents of the module's code region (i.e., by accessing to a variable in its data region). Furthermore, the issue is present not only with references to the module itself but also with any reference to the kernel symbols (e.g., `printk()` function).

The outcome in modules data is similar to modules code, but more relaxed. The three most significant randomization elements that impacts modules are the kernel virtual address, the modules base offset and function reordering. The best case has 51.2% of equal pages, while the following case, disabling the named addresses, has 49.8%. Of these three randomization elements, the function reordering is the one impacting most, followed by the modules base and the kernel virtual randomization.

The results of the `vmalloc` kernel region show about 4% to 5% of equal pages in all cases, regardless of the randomization elements being enabled or disabled. This behavior is certainly expected, since this is a memory region that serves dynamically allocated virtually contiguous memory that is mainly used to store data temporarily. Therefore, based on the obtained results, one can state that function-granular kernel randomization has minimal influence on the contents of the `vmalloc` memory region.

The last kernel memory region analyzed is the Linux Virtual Memory Map. This region contains lists of objects with references to previous and next objects located in the same region. This aspect is evidenced by the fact that randomizing the `vmemmap` virtual address has a high deduplication impact on its own memory region. The best case has 88.2% of equal pages, and 83.1% when enabling all randomization elements except `vmemmap`. Then, the percentage of equal pages drops to zero when the `vmemmap` virtual address is randomized. In our experiments, we observed that randomizing the kernel physical memory has a slight influence on the `vmemmap` region. That is reasonable since the objects located in this region represent metadata about the physical memory, so this is caused by information that depends on the physical location of the memory pages such as the page frame number. However, since this influence is less than 5%, the configuration that maximizes the number of enabled randomization elements with minimal impact on memory contents for this region is when all randomization elements are enabled except `vmemmap` itself.

6.6 Proposed Solution

Section 6.4 states that as of the date of writing this thesis and to the best of the authors' knowledge, KASLR-MT is the only kernel randomization design for cloud systems but it is designed for coarse-grained kernel randomization and must be adapted to meet the new requirements arising from the challenges of fine-grained kernel randomization. Therefore, its design must be expanded to include both info-leak attacks protection and high rates of shared memory desired by cloud providers.

In this section, we present our proposal to enable cloud providers to take advantage of modern kernel randomization protection mechanisms while having high rates of deduplicated memory allowing them to take more profit from their resources and still offer to users the same level of protection as function-granular kernel randomization, including info-leaks. Afterwards, we present the implementation of the proposal for Linux on `x86_64`.

6.6.1 Function-Granular Randomization Compatible with Memory Deduplication

In order to properly tackle the problem of severe memory sharing breakage derived from the memory contents alterations introduced by the randomization of kernel memory regions and functions, we propose an effective function-granular kernel randomization for cloud systems compatible with memory deduplication. The benefits obtained from this proposal include a more efficient use of available resources by removing the cancellation of memory sharing by the influence of relative offsets, as well as a strong protection against info-leaks attacks to guests.

Following the analysis results obtained in section 6.5, there are randomization elements with minimum impact and others with higher impact on the effectiveness of memory deduplication.

Figure 6.3: Overview of the proposed function-granular kernel randomization. Two tenants are shown, each one running two kernels. The kernels of Tenant 1 determine the same order of functions, which in turn is different from the kernels of Tenant 2. For Tenant 1, the functions in the kernels of Tenant 2 are unknown and unpredictable, and vice-versa. For the kernels of each tenant, KSM (deduplication) can merge the memory contents.

The design of the proposed approach allows the hypervisor to instruct how guests virtual machines map their memory regions. Guests use the information provided by they hypervisor to calculate the addresses of each Linux kernel memory region. This way, the kernel randomization is always enabled and different randomization elements can be tuned depending on the deduplication impact.

A randomization element has **none or low impact** if after enabling it has a negligible impact on the memory deduplication. For example, table 6.2 shows that enabling poking *virt.addr.*, *vmemmap*, *vmalloc*, *physmap*, *modules offset* and kernel *phys.addr.* reduces 0% the number of equal pages for the Linux code memory region. A randomization element has **high impact** if the fact of enabling it has a huge impact on the memory deduplication. For example, table 6.2 shows that the function reordering and kernel virtual address randomization elements reduce 99.9% the percentage of equal pages for the Linux code memory region.

The proposed solution is aimed for cloud systems with multiple tenants running their own virtual machines. Hence, kernels of one tenant share a common randomized memory layout. This increases the shared memory and keeps the effectiveness of the kernel randomization, since the final layout remains unpredictable for an external attacker. This applies also for non-identical virtual machines, because the minimum granularity of KSM is 4096 bytes, and there are still opportunities to deduplicate some parts of the virtual machine. It provides the maximum possible deduplication benefit when the kernel randomization is enabled. Regarding the negative effects on the memory deduplication caused by function-granular randomization, currently there is no other publicly known solution to this problem as it is completely new. As discussed in section 6.4, approaches such as adapting the kernel to be PIC compliant cannot solve the problem. This is mainly because the function-granular kernel randomization has relative offsets breaking the shareability that unfortunately PIC cannot prevent, since they are already relative.

As depicted in figure 6.3, the main idea of the proposed approach consist on having a cloud infrastructure which maintains a table with one-to-one correspondence, linking Tenant-ID and a unique random key. Each unique key serves to feed each virtual machine of a particular tenant, enabling them to deterministically calculate the addresses of all memory regions and the addresses of all shuffled kernel and modules functions. Cloud providers must ensure that keys are not duplicated. Besides, since the algorithm to produce addresses for a given key has to be highly deterministic, keys must be totally unpredictable. Otherwise, an attacker could predict the kernel memory layout of a victim. This can be achieved using a CSPRNG and ensuring that the generated key is not being used by another tenant. The novelty with respect to FG-KASLR is that all the virtual machines of a certain group/tenant will obtain the same layout while being a fine-grained layout for an attacker. In practice, the number of possible addresses of kernel functions is extended as with FG-KASLR, and at the same time the problem of memory sharing breakage is solved.

To provide support for live migration, the relevant columns of this table must be shared among the hosts machines forming the cloud infrastructure. Otherwise, two guests running in two different hosts belonging to the same tenant will have different kernel memory layout and this will prevent to deduplicate the kernel even if both guests are later running under the same host.

A tenant's key lifespan starts from the time the first VM is launched and ends when the last VM is shut down, even if the VMs are running on separate physical machines. Once any VM is running, the key cannot be changed. Otherwise, this would lead to kernels from the same group producing different memory layouts, breaking the shareability. The key of a given tenant can be safely cleared at the moment the last virtual machine is shut down. This key renewal is recommended as it enforces the generation of new kernel memory layouts for subsequent guests. This way, the kernel randomization layout is not always the same but is re-randomized over time. Each randomization element can be individually randomized in two different ways:

1. **Per-Tenant:** For a particular randomization element, a random key is produced by the host and associated with a tenant. The key is shared among all the virtual machines of the same tenant so that they can generate the same base address/offset/shuffle. Guests belonging to the same tenant will have the same (random) memory base address for that particular randomization element. For example, guests produce the same virtual base address of a kernel memory region. Similarly, if the function reordering is randomized Per-Tenant, the kernel and modules functions order will be the same among all guests of the same tenant. Our proposal uses a Per-Tenant approach for randomization elements with high impact on any kernel memory region.
2. **Per-VM:** For a particular randomization element, a random key is produced by the host and associated with a virtual machine. When a guest virtual machine reboots, the base address/offset/shuffle will be different, and it is not shared with other virtual machines belonging to same or other tenants. Our proposal uses a Per-VM approach for randomization elements with low impact on all kernel memory regions.

6.6.2 Linux Implementation

Based on the results of section 6.5 and considering the two ways to randomize the different randomization elements based on their impact on memory deduplication (low or high), we have implemented the proposed approach maximizing the deduplication while the function-granular kernel randomization is fully enabled. Those correspond with the green rows of table 6.2 and

the memory sharing rate is similar to that obtained when function-granular kernel randomization is disabled. For this implementation, we consider that a randomization element with high impact is when the reduction of equal pages is greater than 5%. This value depends on the developers decision and table 6.5 can be consulted to obtain the randomization elements that must be applied for a desired % of equal pages.

It is important to note that the green rows selected to implement our proposal contain randomization elements that are enabled in one row but disabled in another. For example, looking at green rows of table 6.5, it can be seen that the kernel virtual address is not randomized for the Linux kernel code memory region but it is for `vmalloc` and virtual memory map. To properly implement an effective function-granular kernel randomization while keeping high memory sharing rates we must combine all selected rows to obtain which of the randomization elements will be enabled. If a randomization element is enabled in all rows, it will be randomized *Per-Tenant*, otherwise *Per-VM*. Table 6.3 shows the type applied to each randomization element used in our implementation.

Table 6.3: Randomization approach for the different Linux randomization components.

Randomization Element	Type
Kernel Physical Address	Per-VM
Kernel Virtual Address	Per-Tenant
Function Reordering	Per-Tenant
Modules	Per-Tenant
Physical Direct Mapping	Per-VM
Vmalloc/ioremap	Per-VM
Vmemmap	Per-Tenant
Poking	Per-VM

In our proof of concept, the hypervisor passes via kernel's command-line a random key and whether a randomized element is either Per-VM or Per-Tenant. For the latter, we used a single byte where a 0 means randomization Per-VM and a 1 randomization Per-Tenant. This is all the information required by guests to implement the proposed approach. Since Linux normally prints the contents of the `cmdline` to the kernel ring buffer at the beginning of its boot process, the key is cleaned-up after being retrieved. This way, we ensure that the `cmdline` buffer cannot leak the key. If the key is leaked, every address being randomized from that key could be calculated.

The hypervisor must ensure that the random key contains enough random material to initialize a cryptographic random number generator. Once the key is obtained by the guest, it is used to derivate all memory addresses to be randomized. In our proof of concept, guests use this key to feed a ChaCha20 cryptographic random number generator [141] to deterministically obtain random numbers to be used to calculate the kernel base virtual address, modules base, vmemmap address as well as the kernel and modules function order.

The function reordering element is not just a single address, but a random number per function is obtained to calculate the final memory address where the function will be loaded. As shown in listing 6.2, since the random number generator has been initialized uniquely using the key from the host, the kernel and modules functions will appear random from the outside. This approach ensures compatibility for future releases of the new Linux kernel randomization.

Code 6.2: Modifications to the current `shuffle_sections()` function to enable the proposed solution to generate a deterministic kernel function layout.

```
478 static void shuffle_sections(...)
...     ...
483
-- parse_prandom_seed();
++ if (cloud_fgkaslr_enabled)
++     cloud_fgkaslr_shuffle_init(fgkaslr_seed);
++ else
++     parse_prandom_seed();
485
486 for (i = size - 1; i > 0; i--) {
...     ...
```

6.7 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed solution in terms of security and memory deduplication. We are comparing our proposal against FG-KASLR and the previous design of KASLR-MT, when function-granular kernel randomization and memory deduplication are fully enabled.

To quantify the amount of kernel memory being saved, a second experiment has been conducted. We ran distinct series of simultaneous virtual machines, starting with 2 and gradually adding more VMs up to 30. All these virtual machines use the same configuration as the one mentioned in section 6.5: a generic GNU/Linux Ubuntu 20.04 LTS with Linux v5.5, with Gnome desktop and full networking (NAT mode provided by Qemu). The physical machine used to run the experiments has an Intel Xeon W-2155 processor (Skylake server microarchitecture) and 32 GiB of SDRAM memory. The hypervisor used is KVM (Linux kernel 5.4-ARCH) along with Qemu VMM version 5.0.0.

The kernel memory space can be modified not only by the kernel itself but also indirectly by the userspace. There are userspace activities that modify the internal state of the kernel. Although such variations are not due to the randomization of the kernel, they may appear in the measurements taken. The number of possible userspace workload combinations is unlimited. Moreover, it would be plausible to create custom workloads to produce biased results, for example, by creating userspace activities that produce a high memory deduplication rate, but also the contrary. In an effort to be as less biased as possible, our guests run a default GNU/Linux Ubuntu distribution.

6.7.1 Memory Savings

Redundant memory is essential for the memory deduplication mechanism to be able to save memory from the contents of the virtual machines. From the experiment results, we observed that the percentage of redundant memory grows logarithmically over time as more kernels are added. The percentage of redundant memory was stabilized when 30 kernels were running simultaneously and no significant percentage benefit was observed by adding more kernels to our tests. Therefore, we run 30 kernels to obtain results since this enabled us to have results independent of the number of virtual machines. Figure 6.4 shows a comparison of the

Figure 6.4: Percentage of redundant memory for each kernel memory region, comparing FG-KASLR (**FG**), KASLR-MT (**MT**), the proposed solution (**P**), and the maximum possible value (**MAX**), which corresponds with disabling kernel randomization.

percentage of redundant memory when 30 Linux kernels are running, splitting each kernel memory region. This percentage is calculated by observing how many pages KSM can merge for each approach, comparing FG-KASLR (**FG**), KASLR-MT (**MT**), the proposed solution (**P**), and the best case for memory sharing (**MAX**), which corresponds with disabling kernel randomization.

This confirms that previous approaches are cancelling memory sharing by sub-page content modifications due to the function-granular randomization. It also confirms that the proposed approach is close to the best case scenario in terms of redundant memory. The kernel code is the memory region that benefits most, being able to share 97.6% of its memory region which is a significant improvement compared to the 25.9% achieved by the base function-granular kernel randomization. Kernel data is also improved from 72.4% to 88.3%, which means that 15.9% more of the total memory data will be shared. Modules code shareability improvement goes from 2.9% to 51.0%, which means that half of the modules code memory region is shared in contrast of the 3% of shareability achieved by FG-KASLR. Modules data shareability has been improved by a factor of 2, from 31.7% to 63.5%. Regarding vmalloc, the percentage of

memory that can be deduplicated is very high, 92.6% and any improvement would be very low. The vmemmap memory region is the most benefited, since current kernel randomization reduces the percentage of shared memory to 0.3% while our proposal raises this value to 81.9%. Overall, the proposed approach provides a very significant memory deduplication improvement, overcoming all already existing approaches.

6.7.2 Security

To assess the security of the proposal, no actual experiments need to be executed since we have not modified the kernel randomization algorithm. Either a memory area is randomized per tenant or per virtual machine but no weaknesses or strengths have been introduced to the randomization algorithm itself. In both cases, from outside the tenant, every memory region will be seen as a full and unknown randomized memory region. Attackers will not have any advantage and the function-granular kernel randomization protection will be not weakened.

As table 6.4 shows, the proposed solution provides a strong protection against info-leak attacks. Unlike the coarse-grained design of KASLR-MT, the new approach is able to mitigate info-leak attacks from remote attackers such as attacks coming from the Internet, from virtual machines running in other tenants and even from userland, regardless whether the virtual machine being attacked belong to same tenant or not. This provides a wide and reasonable protection level where only administrators with root privileges belonging to the same tenant can attack themselves, which seems very unlikely. The rest of the scenarios are covered and protected by the proposal.

In addition to info-leak attacks prevention, our approach also mitigates code reuse attacks, since addresses will appear fully random for attackers. This is because randomizing at function level not only mitigates info-leaks but makes harder code reuse attacks. Therefore, attacks such as malicious installed applications, remote network applications interacting with the kernel and attacks coming from other tenants will face the maximum protection that function kernel randomization provides. As a result, attackers will not find any advantage to bypass the kernel

Table 6.4: Summary of security protection comparing KASLR-MT (**MT**) and the proposed solution (**P**). A tick (✓) means that the corresponding approach provides protection against Info-Leak attacks targeting the kernel memory region of the corresponding row.

Attack Target / Kernel Region	Mitigates Info-Leak Attacks to Kernel from:					
	Userspace		Inter-Tenant		Remote	
	MT	P	MT	P	MT	P
Kernel Code	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Kernel Data	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Modules Code	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Modules Data	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Vmalloc	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Vmemmap	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Physical Memory	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓

randomization of any of the memory regions that were pre-determined by our proposal. The proposed solution is as secure as the original kernel randomization, whose security has been already proved [61, 142–144], but our proposal enables to have both security and high memory saving.

6.8 Discussion

In this section, we discuss some affairs that have not been thoroughly detailed for being out of scope but have positive security implication in our proposed approach.

As described in section 6.2 and throughout the article, the goal of our approach is to protect the kernel against attacks from remote machines and from virtual machines belonging to other tenants located in the same physical machine. Our proposal can also provide protection against userland attacks as discussed in section 6.7.2 and it assumes that all machines belonging to the same tenant are trustworthy. However, depending on whether the randomization of a memory region is per virtual machine or per tenant, the final implementation could also extend its protection against attacks coming from the same tenant.

Based on the results obtained in the analysis section 6.5 to obtain a reasonable trade-off (less than 5% of deduplication loss) we decided to randomize some memory regions per tenant and others per virtual machine. Table 6.3 shows that the kernel physical address, the physical direct mapping, `vmalloc` and the poking virtual address are randomized per virtual machine. Therefore, the locations of those memory regions will be different among the virtual machines running in the same tenant. In practice, this means that a virtual machine cannot use its own memory layout to determine the location of those memory regions of another virtual machine running in the same tenant.

Hence, attacks relying on knowing the addresses of those memory regions will be prevented even if the attack comes from a virtual machine of the same tenant. For example, exploits targeting physical memory such as abusing the virtual dynamic shared object (vDSO) by altering paging structures [145] will fail since they require the physical address where the kernel was loaded. In general, addresses randomized per virtual machine protect the associated memory regions even from attacks coming from virtual machines running in the same tenant.

Therefore, the design allows a flexible configuration that can be adapted to different needs. The choice we made regarding which memory regions are randomized per tenant and which per virtual machine showed in this article are the ones that present a reasonable tradeoff between security and memory deduplication benefits. However, from the analysis provided in section 6.5, other configurations can be used to provide protection against attacks coming from the same tenant.

Finally, the design is flexible enough to provide different randomization information to different virtual machines of the same tenant, allowing special virtual machines to increase its shareability or security. For example, a tenant running 10 virtual machines could have one of them more exposed and therefore a wise decision could be to have more memory regions randomized per virtual machine rather than per tenant. Under this scenario, 9 virtual machines will have a good balance between security (see the security protections in table 6.4) and shareability, and the one more exposed will slightly reduce the overall shared memory to have a full independent kernel randomization.

6.9 Conclusions

Function-granular kernel randomization is an important and effective security mechanism that protects against code reuse and info leaks attacks. FG-KASLR aims to be the future kernel randomization and it is currently available for some Linux kernel hardened versions.

FG-KASLR improves current kernel randomization not only by extending the entropy but also by preventing info-leaks and correlation attacks. Unfortunately, it also prevents memory deduplication to work effectively reducing to almost zero the number of pages that can be shared among the same kernel running on different virtual machines. For some memory regions, our analysis showed that the number of pages that can be merged among all kernel memory regions falls drastically when the function-granular kernel randomization is enabled.

After identifying why function-granular kernel randomization fails to provide protection and shareability at the same time, we performed a comprehensive analysis of its negative impact on memory deduplication. Then, based on the analysis results, we proposed an effective and practical function-granular kernel randomization approach for cloud systems that provides high rates of memory sharing and keeps security.

We have implemented our proposal in the Linux kernel version 5.5 and results showed that the proposed approach maximizes the memory deduplication savings rate while providing a strong security equivalent to FG-KASLR. This enables cloud providers to have both, high levels of security and an efficient use of resources.

Part II

Preventing Boot-Time Entropy Starvation in Cloud Systems

Chapter 7

E-BOOT

Due to the impracticability of generating true randomness by running deterministic algorithms in computers, boot-loaders and operating systems undergo the lack of enough supplies of entropy at boot-time.

Unfortunately, this situation leads to undesired side effects, affecting the security of important kernel components and causing large blocking waits in the start-up of userland processes.

In this chapter, we analyze the boot-time entropy starvation problem, performing a comprehensive analysis of the Linux kernel boot process revealing that the problem not only affects userland applications but up to 33 kernel functions at boot time. Those functions are weakly fed by random numbers from a non-initialized CSPRNG.

To overcome this problem, we propose E-Boot, a novel technique that provides high-quality random numbers to guest virtual machines. E-Boot is the first technique that completely satisfies the entropy demand of virtualized boot-loaders and operating systems at boot time.

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7.1 Introduction

Nowadays, new cloud paradigms and virtualization technologies have emerged due to the compelling tendency to shift to a finer granularity, with the aim of increasing the ability to dynamically scale resource utilization and maximally exploit the infrastructure resources. Serverless computing [16, 17] is an example of cloud computing model that has recently reached a relevant situation in its development. In contrast to *Infrastructure as a Service* (IaaS) [10], where the provider supplies storage, networking and virtualization so that the client has full control over the system from OS layer upwards, the serverless computing model enables dynamic resource allocation, leaving the scaling of infrastructure requirements to the provider. This approach avoids over-provisioning of resources, eventually decreasing effective costs.

Serverless computing allows developers to focus on the application business logic without having to worry about infrastructure management. This leads to the appearance of new computing models and modern technologies offering native high scalability by following the *Function as a Service* (FaaS) [146] paradigm, such as `metacall.io` and `quarkus.io`. Similarly, virtualization technologies are also increasingly leaning towards a finer granularity and more efficient computing. An example of this trend are micro-virtual machines (microVMs), which run custom and tightly fitted kernels that only feature components strictly necessary for a given service, avoiding unnecessary processing and memory usage. One of the representative technologies of microVMs is Firecracker [147], an open source virtual machine monitor (VMM) that uses the Linux Kernel-based Virtual Machine (KVM) to create microVMs. This lightweight approach allows a better fitting in workload balancing and a reduction of the start-up time. In addition, the model is security-aware and reduces significantly the attack surface.

Although cloud providers must ensure the highest possible level of security in order to prevent attacks, there are scenarios where this is not always possible. An important example is the boot-entropy starvation problem [148–151], which appears when a system (e.g., boot-loader or operating system) requires entropy at boot-time but it is unable to generate or collect enough entropy.

The lack of enough entropy at boot-time derives into different problems, including the generation of weak cryptographic keying material [149] and the synchronous blocking of components [152]. As a result, some hardening and protection techniques used by boot-loaders, operating systems and userland applications are weakened, or they are blocked until the quality entropy is available. The latter is not an option for operating systems because stopping the boot process could lead to a boot failure or unacceptable delay. This is a significant problem since it fails to meet the security requirements of current cloud computing models. In this chapter, we deeply investigate this problem and propose a novel solution for cloud computing.

7.2 Background

The importance of entropy and the generation of random numbers are sometimes undervalued. Although the intuitive idea is quite simple, having a good entropy source in deterministic machines is a challenge. This section presents a brief introduction of entropy and an overview of the Linux CSPRNG.

7.2.1 Entropy

Entropy is an abstract concept with multiple definitions that vary depending on the area of knowledge. According to the literature, there are three types of entropy [153]: thermodynamic entropy, residual entropy and information entropy. This might create confusion, since the same concept is used with slightly different meanings. In this thesis, we focus on the latter definition of entropy, related to the information theory field. Thereupon, information entropy is a foundational concept that measures uncertainty or randomness.

It is commonly understood as the amount of surprise caused after producing a random value. The higher the entropy, the more uncertainty and, therefore, the more surprise there will be when reading the result of a randomized process. It is an important concept with several applications. For example, it is widely used in many areas of machine learning (e.g., training of Decision Trees [154]), for proving the security of unconditionally secure cryptosystems [155], for detecting incipient damages in a 3D 9-bay truss-type bridge [156] and to derive the mutual information measure in medical image co-registration [157].

Digital computers are deterministic physical machines. By definition, it is not possible to produce true (information-theoretically secure) random numbers from a finite state machine [42]. This is a challenge for operating systems, which try to mitigate this problem by collecting entropy from external non-deterministic and unpredictable events and chaotic sources, typically from hardware including peripherals and dedicated devices to generate randomness. However, when an operating system starts its execution, there is usually little or no entropy available until the kernel is initialized and able to start collecting entropy from those external sources. In addition, certain systems as embedded devices and virtual machines suffer more constraints to gather entropy for different reasons, such as short boot times and/or the lack of physical hardware providing uncertainty. This reduces the random numbers that virtual machines can produce and incurs a negative impact in security and performance.

7.2.2 Linux CSPRNG Overview

Most modern operating systems offer interfaces to one or multiple internal CSPRNGs to allow userspace programs and the kernel itself to obtain computationally secure random numbers for any desired use, such as the Address Space Layout Randomization [49, 56]. In this section, we present the most recent CSPRNG design used by Linux from version v4.8 [158] to 5.5.8, the most recent version at the time of writing this thesis.

Linux maintains special memory areas called entropy pools, holding true random data derived from different sources of entropy. When raw random data is added to an entropy pool, the input is mixed with the already existing contents using a linear-feedback shift register (LFSR) function. This is how Linux allows updating its entropy pool with any data without compromising the overall unpredictability of the pool contents. Even if a chunk of totally predictable data is mixed into an entropy pool, the uncertainty of its contents does not decrease. Therefore, any pool contents update means either increasing its entropy or keeping the same, but never decreasing it.

Each pool has an associated conservative estimation of available entropy in the corresponding pool. This estimation is decoupled from the contents, implying that not all the input being mixed in the entropy pools is necessarily credited. It is not always possible to accurately measure how much entropy has a certain input. In such cases, the input is mixed with the destination pool anyway, but without incrementing the entropy estimation. This is because, in the worst case,

even if the input does not provide any additional entropy (e.g., a totally predictable pattern) the existing unpredictability of the pool contents is not decreased.

When random data is requested from an entropy pool, the raw contents of the pool are never directly exposed. Instead, the contents are hashed using SHA-1 and the resulting digest is folded by mixing the most significant bits with the least significant bits using the XOR binary operation. The resulting 80-bit value is the one returned as output.

The kernel tries to gather randomness from wherever possible throughout its execution uptime, feeding a primary entropy pool called `input pool`. For example, a typically reliable way to obtain true randomness is from the unpredictable arrival of external events. Additionally, userland programs are also able to provide data to update the primary `input pool` to increase the uncertainty. However, entropy from userland is not always credited and only privileged users can update the estimation accordingly to the data provided.

Linux offers essentially two different sources of pseudo-random data: 1) a secondary entropy pool called `blocking pool` and 2) a CSPRNG based on the ChaCha20 cryptographic function [141]. Both are periodically fed with true entropy from the `input pool`. On the one hand, the `blocking pool` retrieves random data using the operation previously described, using the folded SHA-1 digest of its contents. This pool is typically smaller than the primary `input pool`, although this can be modified at compile time. An important peculiarity of the `blocking pool` is that random data requests to this pool depend on the available entropy accounted by its associated estimation. For each request, the entropy estimation decreases and, if the estimation goes below a threshold, successive requests will block until enough entropy is available. On the other hand, the CSPRNG algorithm is based on the ChaCha20 stream cipher to produce as many bytes as requested. At boot-time, its state (`primary_crng`) is initialized, but for that it requires at least 128 bits of true random data. Afterwards, the CSPRNG is regularly re-seeded. The stream cipher allows the kernel to produce an effectively large sequence of cryptographically secure pseudo-random numbers from a small amount of

Table 7.1: Overview of interfaces provided by the Linux kernel to obtain random values.

Interface	Description
<code>get_random_bytes()</code> <code>get_random_u32()</code> <code>get_random_u64()</code>	Kernel's internal functions that uses the CSPRNG to return random data. Those functions can only be used from the kernel and no user applications can directly access to them.
<code>/dev/random</code>	Special file that uses the internal <code>blocking pool</code> to return random bytes when read from userspace. If the estimation of available entropy is low, the read operation will block until some more randomness is gathered.
<code>/dev/urandom</code>	Special file that uses the internal CSPRNG to return random bytes when it is read from userspace. In contrast to <code>/dev/random</code> , the read operation never blocks.
<code>getrandom()</code>	System call included in Linux version 3.17 [159] that returns random bytes to userspace. Useful when applications have not available file descriptors and cannot open files (i.e., <code>/dev/random</code>) to obtain random bytes. It is also useful in ch-rooted environments.

random data. In contrast with the `blocking_pool`, random data requests to the CSPRNG do not need to block.

With this design, the kernel provides four different relevant interfaces to generate random bits from its CSPRNG and entropy pools, one for internal kernel usage and the rest for userland programs. Table 7.1 shows an overview of these four interfaces. The file `/dev/random` uses the `blocking_pool` to obtain random values. The file `/dev/urandom` uses the CSPRNG instead. The function `get_random_bytes()` also uses the CSPRNG, but it is not reachable from userspace. Finally, the `getrandom()` system call returns random data from either `/dev/urandom` or `/dev/random` depending on the flag argument of the call.

7.3 Entropy Sources

An entropy source is a device or technique from which entropy or randomness can be directly produced. As we highlighted in section 7.2, it remains a challenge for operating systems to generate entropy. This section presents an overview of characteristics and limitations of the main four entropy sources from which a modern computer can obtain true randomness. Later, we present a brief analysis of all of them, synthesizing the relevant features when utilizing them in virtualized operating systems.

7.3.1 OS External Events

Unpredictable external events are a suitable method to obtain true entropy in deterministic machines. One of the basic entropy sources from which an operating system can derive true randomness is by sampling events from human interface devices (HID) and other interrupts, including events from rotating disk drives, network adapters, mouse movements, keys pressed, etc. In these cases, the main source of uncertainty is obtained by taking a time-stamp when those HID interrupts arrive with a high-resolution timer, which is typically available in all modern computers. Therefore, some little entropy can be obtained from the unpredictability of the arrival of such events.

However, this approach has some shortcomings when it comes to virtual machines. The virtualization of disk devices and the lack of any type of HID peripherals in these environments substantially reduces the obtained entropy. Since entropy comes from external events, the randomness generation bitrate is slow and the time required to gather enough entropy as to initialize a CSPRNG could be large.

7.3.2 CPU Jitter

The high complexity of modern digital computers yields opportunities to take profit from the unpredictability of small fluctuations of different clocks at the nanometric scale to obtain real entropy from deterministic machines. A practical way to obtain true random numbers from modern digital computers is by measuring the small timing variances in the execution of machine instructions and non-modellable noise derived from memory access times, exploiting the complexity of operating systems and the underlying hardware [45]. Listing 7.1 shows an example of a random bit generator based on the CPU jitter completely implemented in software. It takes a base reference time-stamp, and a loop flips the value of a boolean variable an undefined number of times, where the condition of termination is that the current time-stamp is

greater than the reference plus a threshold. This is the general idea followed by some programs such as TrueRand [160] and its derivatives [161, 162]. Another approach is to measure how much time a sleep operation takes [163].

However, the confidence of this method is controversial [164]. Generally, since it relies on a lack of knowledge of complex systems (existing workload, scheduler, state of cache memories, etc), the generated output by using the CPU jitter technique can be predictable to a knowledgeable attacker. Similarly, in simpler systems (e.g., without multiple execution threads and interruptions), the unpredictability is really challenging. Also, CPU jitter entropy is produced by measuring timings, so it cannot produce large streams of random bits in a short period of time.

Code 7.1: Example of a random bit generator function.

```
ref = read_tsc()  
while(read_tsc() < (ref + THRESHOLD))  
    b = !b  
  
return b
```

7.3.3 Hardware RNG

Hardware RNG (HRNG) is a specialized hardware circuitry used to obtain randomness from the inherent uncertainty of physical phenomena such as thermal noise [165, 166], quantum events [167, 168], frequency drift in oscillators [169, 170] and analog feedback circuits [148, 171].

There are many manufacturers providing different kind of HRNG devices. For example, a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) is a cryptographic microprocessor which includes a secure TRNG, similar to Intel's 82802 Firmware Hub (FWH) chip [172, 173]. The Unified Extensible Firmware Interface (UEFI) is intended to be a modern replacement of the Basic Input/Output System (BIOS) firmware interface [174], offering several improvements such as faster boot and a new disk architecture to support more and bigger partitions. From version 2.4, the UEFI specification [175] defines an entropy gathering protocol [176], designed for UEFI drivers to provide randomness to upper levels from its internal RNG. In addition, other devices as smart cards [177–179] and RNG tokens can be used as an entropy source. RNG tokens are typically attached to the machine via USB port [180], for example, the Altus Metrum ChaosKey [181] and YubiHSM [182]. HotBits [183] is another example that uses a commercial monitor connected to the computer via serial port to derive randomness by detecting radioactive decay events. Similarly, there are peripherals and sensors that can obtain randomness from other physical sources such as audio, video and radio devices [184–187].

Another convenient approach to obtain random numbers is by using on-CPU HRNG, which allows the obtaining of entropy from the CPU itself by executing a machine instruction. The CPU has an internal RNG that produces as much entropy as required. Many CPU manufacturers include a RNG in their specification. For example, the VIA C3 Microprocessors family with PadLock engine includes an electrical noise-based RNG accessible through the `xstore` instruction [188]. In similar way, recent x86 architectures provides two assembler instructions,

RDRAND and RDSEED. According to Intel [189], both instructions are compliant to the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) standards on random number generators (SP 800-90A, B & C) [190]. Although both instructions return random numbers likewise, the implications of their usage are subtly different. The difference is that RDRAND gets the entropy from a cryptographically secure pseudo random number generator and RDSEED from a true random generator. Similarly, s390 z14 IBM machines have the CPACF set of cryptographic instructions [191, 192], and machines with PowerISA 3.0 has the DARN instruction [193].

Having a dedicated HRNG, whether it is within a device or integrated in the CPU, allows the programmer to obtain cryptographically secure randomness. In most of the cases, this randomness can be produced at fast bitrates. For example, Intel's `rdseed` and `rdrand` are capable of producing 742.4 Mbit/s and 6.4 Gbit/s of random data, respectively [189], while some USB RNG tokens can offer bitrates of around 327 Kbit/s [194]. However, there are also exceptional cases where a HRNG offers low bitrates. For example, solutions based on radioactive decay are typically limited to 800 bit/s [183].

Unfortunately, not all physical machines are equipped with HRNGs. Even when any HRNG is available, it must be carefully used by virtual machines, because it can cause issues when those virtual machines are migrated to other physical machines lacking HRNGs. In addition, there are some users and developers that do not fully trust in hardware-based RNGs. In recent years, the appearance of news relating to global cyberwar has motivated a public concern about espionage campaigns carried out by intelligence agencies and all kinds of threat actors seeking to introduce stealthy backdoors in hardware to benefit their interests [195–200]. Furthermore, in order to use HRNG devices, operating systems require to load a driver in order to communicate with the device. Using them can provide entropy to userland applications and to the kernel itself, but only after the operating system is booted. Therefore, even having a dedicated HRNG device fails to provide entropy to key stages of the operating system boot process where cryptographically secure random numbers are required. An example is the kernel randomization security mechanism present in all modern operating systems, where entropy is required at a very early stage before the kernel starts its execution. In addition, most of the HRNGs do not provide any mechanism to update them in presence of vulnerabilities [201].

7.3.4 DRAM RNG

Another source of randomness can be obtained from the Dynamic random access memory (DRAM) chips. The main idea is to misconfigure key low level DRAM memory parameters to cause random alterations to memory cells, and use them as source of entropy.

The main three approaches to obtain randomness from DRAM are:

1. **Violating standard timing parameters.** When the time to refresh memory is reduced below a threshold recommended by the manufacturer, some errors are produced and the value of some random memory cells is changed [47].
2. **Retaining cell charge.** DRAM data is stored in capacitors that leak its charge when its bitline voltage goes below a minimum (V_{min}). This approach gets entropy from cells that randomly fails for a given refresh interval [202, 203].
3. **Reading cell contents at power-up.** When a device is turned on, memory cell contents are unpredictable due to interaction between different logic parts, such as pre-charge, row decoder and column select [204, 205].

The approach that provides good entropy with the lowest latency and highest throughput is “Violating standard timing parameters” [47]. It offers more than 5 MiB/s of true random data.

Unfortunately, the commands that govern the behavior of DRAM chips (i.e., row activation latency, power management, etc.) are performed by the memory controller. Memory controller parameters are typically configured by the firmware in the host machine before loading any operating system. To prevent security issues, virtual machines can only use a subset of physical resources, supervised by the hypervisor. Consequently, the exploitation of these techniques to obtain randomness from DRAM is inflexible, unscalable and prevents to use the DRAM chips being used to generate random data. This results in a non-practical way to obtain random data.

7.3.5 Brief Entropy Sources Analysis

Table 7.2 summarizes the entropy sources discussed in this section considering the random number throughput, virtual machine migration and quality.

Sampling unpredictable external events from the OS is a convenient method to obtain true randomness. Since this is internally done by the operating system, virtual machines can be migrated to other physical machines and use the same approach to collect random numbers. However, in some cases, the virtualization of devices and peripherals normally reduces the obtained entropy because the main source comes from the hardware devices. Also, this source requires a long period of time to generate effective amounts of random data due to its slow generation bitrate.

CPU Jitter is a software-based entropy source that generates random data from the CPU itself, exploiting the high complexity of underlying systems. It is compatible with virtual machine migration in cloud environments because it does not require any specialized hardware to generate random data. Using CPU Jitter to generate random data is slow and a certain amount of time needs to be elapsed to start generating randomness. In addition, unpredictability of data generated by CPU Jitter in some specific simpler environments (e.g., small and limited embedded devices or tiny virtual machines) could be dubious and less than expected.

Hardware-based entropy sources, including HRNG devices and on-CPU HRNGs, can offer true entropy with a normally fast generation bitrate, with a few exceptions (e.g., observing radioactive decay). Unfortunately, those chips are not widely available in all physical machines which introduces challenges to be used by virtual machines with live migration support. In

Table 7.2: Overview of entropy sources and their characteristics, with regard to cloud environments. Circles represent the ability of each source to fulfill a particular characteristic. For example, CPU Jitter is VM migration friendly but hardware RNGs are not. The half circles indicate that the fulfillment can be achieved but there are exceptions, such as the bitrate of hardware RNG devices.

Entropy Sources	Bitrate	VM Migration Friendly	Trustworthy Randomness
OS External Events	○	●	●
CPU Jitter	○	●	●
Hardware RNG	◐	○	◐
Abusing DRAM	●	○	●

addition, these sources have trust issues because they are typically black boxes, difficult to audit and, sometimes, to update. But the deficiency that probably matters most is that most of them require drivers and therefore the entropy can not be used by the operating systems until drivers are loaded. Unfortunately, this is preventing operating systems to obtain entropy at key boot stages. This affects hardening protection techniques that require entropy at early stages of the boot-time.

Using DRAM chips as source of randomness provides fast and true entropy based on unpredictable memory chip failures. This entropy is available in early stages, including pre-boot environments such as boot-loaders. However, it prevents to use those chips while obtaining the entropy and it also requires firmware modifications. This makes the approach unpractical, introduces overheads and reduces the memory available during the entropy generation.

The entropy sources described in this section are the four main techniques used for obtaining true randomness in modern computers. By definition, they are the actual root of entropy. However, these sources are not usually used by entropy consumers (final applications) but by entropy collectors instead.

7.4 Entropy Collectors

An *entropy collector* is a software program whose main job is to obtain entropy from different *entropy sources*, do some kind of processing and then provide random data to *entropy consumers*. In this section, we present an overview of the main entropy collectors, including different tools and techniques.

7.4.1 Userspace Entropy Daemons

Userspace entropy daemons are programs that run in userspace, normally as a background process, and are intended to remedy low-entropy conditions and boost entropy availability in the operating system. There are much available entropy collector daemons at userspace. Following we show the most well-known and widely used in Linux.

Haveged is an entropy daemon that relies on the processor's volatile state [206]. It is based on the HAVEGE (HARdware Volatile Entropy Gathering and Expansion) algorithm to gather entropy using jitter timings from changes in the processor state [207, 208] such as cache memories and branch predictors. Rng-tools tries to obtain entropy from a discrete list of sources (e.g., HRNG and CPU Jitter) to collect it and feed the kernel pool [209]. The daemon does not start if none of its listed sources is available.

Entropy Gathering Daemon (EGD) is a daemon aimed to be used in busy systems that do not feature the any special devices or system call to obtain entropy from the kernel [210]. This entropy daemon is based on unpredictable events such as the output of system administration programs (e.g., lastlog) to obtain randomness. Other programs gather entropy from peripherals using different techniques, for example exploiting audio devices [184, 211], video devices [185] and measuring time of sleep operations [163].

Userspace entropy daemons can be useful to avoid the depletion of operating system's entropy reserves in long-term running systems with high demanding of randomness. However, they are not available at early boot-time, since they cannot be executed until the system is completely

booted and running. This prevents operating systems and boot-loaders to use this approach during the boot process where randomness is required.

7.4.2 On-Disk Seed Files

The fundamental idea of on-disk seed files is to carry entropy across reboots. At system shut-down, a random seed is saved into a file in persistent storage. Next time the system starts up, this seed can be used to feed the entropy reserves of the operating system. This technique takes advantage of the fact that a running system has potentially accumulated more entropy than one just started. In situations where an attacker has knowledge of the environment (i.e., hardware, start-up activities, etc), the seed file makes it difficult to predict the OS internal entropy state, from the second time the system boots onwards.

In Linux systems, on-disk seed files are typically managed by userspace startup scripts or by the init process. Examples of them are `sysVinit-scripts` and `systemd-random-seed`. On the other hand, Systemd also uses a similar approach with its optional EFI boot-loader (`systemd-boot`) [212], storing a random seed in the EFI System Partition (ESP). Similarly, `Early-rng-init-tools` is a package of tools for Linux systems that uses different entropy sources and techniques to fetch entropy to earlier phases in the boot process.

On-disk seed files can be useful to increase unpredictability of OS internal entropy state, using entropy from previous executions. However, they must be treated carefully. In cloud environments, its usage in transient virtual machine instances sharing a cloned generic image and live operating systems can be dangerous, since an attacker using the same image has exactly the same seed file. In these cases, the actual entropy of the seed file should be considered zero. In addition, there is no feasible way to measure how much entropy has a certain seed file. Furthermore, on-disk seed file solutions based on EFI are typically discouraged in virtual machines, because the EFI variable space and the disk space can be shared, cancelling the security benefits [212]. Seed files must be handled secretly and their contents must be immediately updated after using them. In some cases, this fact imposes limitations, as the need of synchronous blockage waiting for having enough entropy to generate the seed file replacement.

7.4.3 Compiler-Assisted Latent Entropy

Compiler-assisted latent entropy is a technique that consists in applying subtle modifications to an operating system at compile time, without causing any semantic changes, adding logic to obtain randomness from the kernel's runtime state when it is executed.

At the time of writing this thesis, there is only one known solution using this technique, which is Latent Entropy, a GCC plugin [213] originally designed and written by the PaX Team for `grsecurity` [214] and later ported to the Linux upstream [215]. It has two parts: 1) *static* random values settled by the compiler and 2) *dynamic* random values computed at runtime. Essentially, different functions are instrumented with additional code that modifies local variables with randomly selected operations, such as addition, shifts and exclusive-or, and other values determined during the build process. Initialization routines, functions called at random times and functions with variable and unpredictable loops are good candidates. At the epilogue of these functions, the computed value of each local variable is mixed into a global variable, which accumulates the entropy. Eventually, the randomness of this global variable contributes to the operating system's internal entropy.

This technique provides per-build and per-boot randomness. On the one hand, static values and selected operations in the modified functions are different per-build. On the other hand, the unpredictability of the operating system's runtime is exploited to obtain dynamic per-boot randomness. For example, the order of functions being called, different branches taken within a function, etc. Interruptions and concurrency can also increase its unpredictability. In addition, contents of some registers such as the stack pointer or the frame pointer can be used to add unpredictability, taking advantage of the randomness provided by other mechanisms as kernel randomization. It is a transparent technique, independent of the hardware, that can be useful to increase the unpredictability of operating system's internal entropy state.

Unfortunately, this technique is still in an experimental state and the actual overhead introduced by the OS modifications is unknown. Current versions of Linux do not credit this entropy into the internal estimation. In addition, it is not feasible to produce large quantity of randomness (e.g. 128 bits) at early stages of the boot process.

7.4.4 Remote Entropy Services

Remote entropy services are a combination of technologies and techniques that allow users to obtain random data from a remote server. Thus, machines with one or more entropy sources can be exploited to provide randomness to remote machines.

An important example of this technique employed in cloud computing is known as Entropy as a Service (EaaS) [93]. This model consists in remote delivery of high-entropy data from a decentralized root of trust over a secure connection where clients can make requests to obtain random numbers. An implementation of this model is the client-server pair `pollinate` [216] and `pollen` [217].

A similar approach is the use of public randomness servers [218]. These servers typically offer randomness from a single high-entropy source or from a combination of different sources. For example, `Random.org` has an API to provide random data through HTTPS.

Remote entropy services can be useful in environments with internet access but with limited sources of entropy. These services offer a large number of clients the possibility of indirectly using expensive appliances in the server to obtain true randomness by observing real unpredictable physical events.

Unfortunately, in order to use remote entropy services, the network must be ready and a secure channel must be established to request random data. This is to ensure that the random data is transferred securely. Otherwise, attackers can use the random data requested by clients to break all client applications where the remote random data is being used as a unique entropy source. Unfortunately, this is the majority of the situations and the main motivation of using those remote services.

Therefore, since this approach requires the system to be completely booted and it also requires high quality random numbers to establish a secure connection, it cannot be used by bootloaders, operating systems or any device that requires entropy at early boot stages. Even overcoming this strong requirement, another issue discouraging clients of using a remote service is the fact that the service is externalized. Obtaining random data from remote servers forces clients to extend the trusted computing base (TCB) and exposes them in the presence of a server breach.

For private services such as EaaS, clients are forced to delegate part of their security to remote services. This discourages cloud providers from using remote servers as a trustworthy approach.

7.4.5 Virtual HRNG

Virtual HRNG is a technique used to enable virtual machines to access a single physical HRNG. Rather than assign a physical device to a single virtual machine, this technique allows multiple guests to obtain entropy from a real HRNG device.

A popular virtual HRNG solution used in the Linux Kernel-based Virtual Machine (KVM) is `Virtio-RNG`. It consists on virtualizing a HRNG device exposing a virtual HRNG device to each virtual machine [219–221]. For example, in Linux each guest will have a new `/dev/hwrng` virtual device. Note that this does not affect the host's internal entropy pool state.

In case of lacking physical HRNG devices, `virtio-rng` optionally allows to attach the virtual HRNG to other files in the host machine. For example, `virtio-rng` can be attached to the special file `/dev/urandom` or `/dev/random` providing true random and pseudo random data respectively. Although a virtual random generator is exported from the point of view of virtual machines, reading from `/dev/random` will consume entropy from the host's entropy pool. In this case, a rate-limit can be tweaked to avoid host entropy depletion. The Xen hypervisor also has a similar tool called `xentropyd` [222].

This technique basically offers the same benefits and limitations as hardware RNGs. For example, it allows fast bitrate streams of random data in guests, as long as it is available in the host machine.

The main drawback of using Virtual HRNGs is that the entropy is available too late. Boot-loaders cannot take advantage of this approach when operating systems are loaded at early boot stages. Drivers are necessary in the guest operating system to manage the virtual device and consequently the operating system boot process must be nearly completed. Although adding this driver to the kernel core could be seen a solution, the truth is that having this code in all kernels even in those that the functionality is not required discourages this approach to be implemented. In addition, this does not solve the problem completely, since the boot-loader also requires high quality random numbers (e.g., to load the OS in random memory locations), and this approach would also require code at the boot-loader level.

Although this is possible, to have a virtual HRNG client present in the boot-loader is not a minor change. For instance, the work being done in the Linux kernel boot-loader is relatively simple, so it would be difficult to justify this overhead. As discussed in section 7.6, this suggests that an appropriate solution is required when high quality random data is required at early boot stages.

7.4.6 Brief Entropy Collectors Analysis

In order to facilitate the comprehension and highlight the importance of entropy collectors, in this section we present a brief analysis of them.

Userspace entropy daemons gather randomness from several entropy sources to enhance the overall operating system's entropy. As userland processes, they do not impose limitations to virtual machine migration and are quite portable. However, userland entropy daemons are not

Figure 7.1: Flow of entropy/randomness from sources to collectors and consumers. Sources are the one generating the entropy. Collectors obtain entropy from entropy sources and provide random data to entropy consumers. It is also possible to obtain randomness directly from sources, but this is not recommended for most applications.

usable when the entropy is required at early boot-time stages. They are generally dependent on the availability of strong entropy sources. Otherwise, the provided randomness of these programs could be of poor quality.

On-disk seed files can be useful to carry entropy across reboots. However, seed files must be treated cautiously for several reasons. There is no feasible and secure way to measure how much entropy they contain. Also, there are hidden issues that could prevent this approach from being used. For example, in cloud environments, virtual machine instances may share the same seed file. Additionally, they cannot be used in early stages of the boot process because the filesystem needs to be available.

Compiler-assisted latent entropy exploits the unpredictability of potential variations in the kernel's runtime state to collect randomness. These variations can be caused by different reasons, for example interruptions upon external events, concurrency and address randomization. Unfortunately, it is not feasible to produce large quantity of randomness at early stages of the boot sequence with this technique. Furthermore, the actual obtained entropy is unknown, and part of their values are settled at compile time, providing zero effective entropy.

Remote entropy services offer the possibility of obtaining randomness through internet services. Although this technique can be useful in some scenarios, it cannot be used at early stages of the boot process. It requires to have the networking system up and working, as well as some high quality random numbers prior to establish a secure connection.

Virtual HRNGs allow host machines to expose physical HRNG devices to guest virtual machines. Guests can benefit from fast streams of true random numbers. However, the use of physical HRNG imposes restrictions to migrate the virtual machines to other hosts lacking the required hardware. In addition, guest operating systems need a driver to communicate with the host backend, which limits its usefulness at early boot-time.

7.5 Entropy Consumers

Entropy consumers, the right square of figure 7.1, are applications and OS components consuming entropy during its execution time to provide secure properties to the final user. For example, in order to provide a secure channel using HTTPS or SSH having high quality random numbers is required.

Although entropy consumers are usually userspace applications obtaining random data from entropy collectors, it is also possible to talk directly with entropy sources. However, this would require allowing direct access to those sources and also add this functionality to each application. This approach would probably break applications and virtual machines, since we can not guarantee that all physical hosts will have the same entropy sources. To alleviate this problem, entropy collectors provide this abstraction layer in order to provide high quality randomness to the entropy consumers while deal with the specific entropy sources of the particular host.

The same approach is being used at different levels. For example, an operating system can be at the same time an entropy collector and consumer. In this case the issue is not having an abstraction layer but to use an internal algorithm (entropy collector) fed from some random data obtained from an entropy source. This approach allows operating systems to have an unlimited high quality random numbers for itself and also to export an interface to enable userspace applications (entropy consumers) to obtain randomness.

7.6 The Problem: Boot-time Entropy Starvation

As discussed and analyzed in sections 7.3, 7.4 and 7.5, there are many solutions to generate and collect entropy to be consumed by the final user. Unfortunately, after analyzing all the literature, we found that none of those techniques can be employed to solve the boot-time starvation problem [148–151], since none of them is capable of providing quality entropy at the very first stages of the boot process.

The issue of lacking enough entropy to feed all the components that require it at boot-time is derived from the fact that it is not feasible to generate real randomness by only running deterministic algorithms in computers, especially in virtual machines and embedded devices. For example, operating systems are not able to gather enough entropy to initialize its internal CSPRNG [164] in early stages of the boot process. This forces to choose between two options. The first would be to block-and-wait random requests until there is enough entropy. This is not something desired or adopted, since the booting process could be stalled and the system could never boot. The second approach would be to return as much entropy as available instead of block-and-wait. Unfortunately, when the returned data is being used in security protection mechanisms such as kernel hardening techniques, those could be seriously weakened.

In the case of Linux, for instance, its internal CSPRNG needs a minimum entropy threshold of quality randomness available to seed the initial state, and it is not ready until this requirement is fulfilled. In headless systems without peripheral devices generating entropy, such as keyboard and mouse, the time needed to generate the minimum entropy threshold is larger. In cloud virtual machine instances, the missing opportunities to get good entropy from hardware is not only due to the lack of peripherals but also to the virtualization of other components as interrupt requests and block devices. At the time of writing this thesis, the availability of high entropy at the early kernel startup is a current concern.

A less obvious issue that could magnify the problem is how some OS improvements affect the entropy generation. For example, as of September 2019, Linux kernel developers had a controversial discussion in the last stages of v5.3 development cycle [152] due to an improvement in the *ext4* filesystem that indirectly caused unexpected boot hangs because the applied changes produced fewer interrupts early in the boot phase, which produced less entropy. In fact, this blocking problem in Linux systems has been going around for some time, since the incorporation of the `getrandom()` system call by libraries such as OpenSSL [223–225]. An example is the Secure Shell (SSH), a widely used service that provides authenticated and encrypted remote access. Its daemon (SSHD) maintains an internal PRNG, which is initially seeded when the program starts. That seed might be requested directly to the kernel or to the OpenSSL library which, in turn, maintains another internal PRNG that also needs to be seeded. Eventually, this entropy originally comes all the way down from the kernel, by means of the `getrandom()` system call. The default behavior of this system call is to block the caller if the CSPRNG is not ready. This blocking behavior leads to prohibitive long delays in the boot time of services requiring secure random numbers waiting for the proper CSPRNG initialization. This prevents users and administrators to connect remotely to the machine until the CSPRNG is ready, resulting in prohibitive connection delays. Furthermore, in situations where the blocked services are the only ones capable of providing fresh randomness into the system, it could even cause deadlocks.

The alternative approach to block-and-wait is to return as much entropy as available at the moment of the request. The problem of this approach is that non-blocking requests to an OS CSPRNG made during this low-entropy state produce potentially predictable pseudo-random numbers. This may lead to serious security problems [226, 227] if any of those weak random values are used to eventually generate sensitive data, such as long-term cryptographic keys. For instance, Heninger et al. [149] performed a large survey of TLS and SSH servers, discovering a widespread presence of vulnerable keys due to insufficient entropy during key generation. Even though not all the requests made to the CSPRNG during the non-initialized state might be intended to be computationally secure, it is conceptually wrong to request random data to a non-initialized CSPRNG. Unexpected security problems can arise by letting this happen [228]. For example, the Linux kernel `ratelimit` feature hides repeating messages if a certain limit is reached, to avoid flooding the message buffer of the kernel. If there are several requests to the uninitialized CSPRNG, the logs will only warn about a small part of them, potentially hiding any dangerous read which actually needed to be cryptographically strong [229].

Summarizing, the boot-time entropy starvation problem leads into two main issues:

1. **Weakened Protection Techniques:** Bootloaders and early stages of operating systems require entropy to securely protect some parts of the OS. For example, in Linux, the boot-loader uses random numbers for kernel randomization, and during the Linux boot process some hardening techniques also require random data. A more detailed list with Linux components can be found in table B.
2. **Blocking CSPRNG requests:** On systems that are not equipped with special hardware to generate random numbers, even when the kernel has been fully loaded, the CSPRNG could take up to several minutes to be initialized as shown in figure 7.4. For those systems, this delay is unacceptable since the problem is propagated to any userland application requesting random data to the kernel. As a result, those servers could be unavailable for minutes after a system reboot.

7.7 The Solution: E-Boot

In this section, we present E-Boot, a novel technique that solves the boot-time entropy starvation problem discussed in section 7.6 by providing high-quality entropy to virtual machines before they start their execution. E-Boot is the first solution that completely satisfies the entropy demand of virtualized boot-loaders and operating systems. Our approach enables boot-loaders and operating systems to access to high-quality random numbers from their very first assembler instructions without requiring any hardware support.

The main idea of E-Boot is to bring high-quality entropy from the hypervisor to guest virtual machines. This enables virtual machines to fulfill all early random data required, as well as to produce their own cryptographically secure random numbers at very early stages of the boot process. The technique can be applied by virtualization technologies (e.g., cloud computing environments) to solve the problem of lacking boot-time entropy where kernel hardening techniques require high-quality entropy to prevent and mitigate attacks.

Although many applications and devices can take advantage of E-Boot, the main benefits that offers for cloud computing are:

1. **Entropy available before VMs are executed:** The hypervisor fills a pre-reserved area in guest memory with random numbers. Each guest has its own pre-reserved area within their memories and this area is randomized the same way as the other randomized kernel regions. With this approach, once the virtual machine starts its execution, it can first access this pre-reserved area to retrieve the random numbers and later start its real execution. As a result, kernels and boot-loaders have entropy available from the very first assembler instructions. This is the first step shown in figure 7.2. The hypervisor fills all pre-reserved areas of all available and compatible virtual machines with random numbers.
2. **Hardened kernel security:** The entropy from the pre-reserved area can be used to early initialize the internal CSPRNG that all modern operating systems have. This is the second step shown in figure 7.2. For example, in Linux, there are many security techniques applied during the boot to harden the kernel. Those techniques require random numbers to be effective but, as we discussed in section 7.6, there is a lack of entropy and those techniques try to do the best effort. Using E-Boot, we can guarantee that the CSPRNG will be fully initialized and all hardening techniques employed during the boot-time will be fully satisfied with all the random numbers required.
3. **Prevents userland blocks:** Unlike what it might be expected, the problem of entropy starvation persists after the kernel has been completely loaded. As we discuss in the section 7.9, and show in figure 7.4, the CSPRNG initialization can be delayed up to 4 minutes. This time is required to collect enough entropy to initialize the CSPRNG, and therefore to provide random data to userspace applications. With E-Boot, this time is reduced to zero, and servers and applications are not blocked anymore.

It is important to note that E-Boot does not depend on external hardware, and it is fully compatible with live virtual machine migration including load balancing, resource management and availability. In addition, it does not interfere with the execution of any service running in the guest virtual machines [230]. As with any virtualized environment, guests should trust the hypervisor and therefore, the provided entropy.

Figure 7.2 shows the design of E-Boot. In step ①, the hypervisor fills the pre-reserved area of all virtual machines with random numbers. The hypervisor is responsible for selecting a proper source of randomness. Once this operation is completed, the hypervisor must indicate to the guest that the job was done. This can be done for example by indicating the quantity of present entropy in the pre-reserved area or by setting a flag. This brings transparency and backwards compatibility with other hypervisors that do not support E-Boot, since guest can ignore the entire pre-reserved area if the pre-reserved area was not filled or has zero entropy.

When the virtual machine starts its execution, the pre-reserved pool filled with random data is already available within its memory, ready to use whenever it is needed. Hence, the guest OS is able to use this entropy from the very first instruction in order to satisfy different random data requests from itself. As shown in step ② of figure 7.2, E-Boot enables operating systems to add randomness into their internal entropy pools in order to initialize their CSPRNG as soon as possible. This will ensure that all requests from the OS kernel and from userspace (step ③ in figure 7.2) programs are provided with the required high-quality random data. Note that guests do not require any additional driver running the entire virtual machine lifespan and this process is only being executed once at boot-time. The same principle applies to boot-loaders.

Therefore, E-Boot solves boot-time starvation and all derived problems with an efficient, transparent and lightweight approach, while being compatible with virtual machine live migration. Cloud systems and virtualization technologies can be benefited from it in multiple ways. On the one hand, it potentially accelerates the boot time of services that are otherwise blocked waiting for a CSPRNG initialization for obtaining secure random numbers [231, 232]. On the other hand, it provides strong security for those fundamental components that are necessarily established at an early stage in the boot process and remain untainted throughout the operating system lifespan, such as kernel randomization or memory hardening used by the Linux SLAB allocator at boot-time. It also enables the possibility to debug certain workloads that use deterministic PRNGs, providing known seeds to produce controlled and repeatable states across different boots.

This solution can be especially beneficial for virtualization technologies that focus on security while offering multi-tenant serverless services with a lightweight approach to minimize the attack surface, such as Firecracker [147]. Using E-Boot, micro-virtual machines can benefit

Figure 7.2: Design of E-Boot. Before a virtual machine is started, ① the hypervisor injects entropy into the guest's memory. ② When the guest virtual machine starts its execution, the pre-reserved area filled with random data is already present and reachable from the beginning. All early random data requests can be fulfilled. The OS's internal CSPRNG can be initialized early, allowing the generation of cryptographically secure random numbers. ③ Kernel components and userspace programs are benefited from it, obtaining secure random data and avoiding blocking waits.

from the availability of quality entropy from the beginning of their execution, without needing any additional driver being loaded in the kernel or any channel connected to the host machine.

7.8 E-Boot Implementation in Linux

In this section, we present the implementation of the proposed E-Boot in the Linux kernel v5.3 for the x86_64 architecture. Figure 7.3 shows an overview of it. Following the design presented in section 7.7, the first step is to enable the hypervisor to transfer high-quality random numbers to the pre-reserved memory area of all virtual machines.

When the Linux kernel is built from sources, not only the Linux kernel is compiled for a specific architecture but a bootloader capable to load the kernel is also built. On x86_64 and other architectures, by default the kernel is compressed and a single file named `vmlinux` containing the compressed kernel and the bootloader is created. In cloud computing, this `vmlinux` is loaded into memory by the hypervisor to later transfer the execution flow to it, more specifically to the Linux bootloader code contained in the `vmlinux` file.

The Linux bootloader is responsible for loading the Linux kernel into memory and transfer its execution control to it. Since, at this early stage, protection techniques such as the kernel randomization are already underway, E-Boot must be implemented in a way that provides entropy to the Linux bootloader before the kernel is loaded. In addition, after the kernel has been decompressed and loaded but before the execution control is transferred to the Linux kernel, E-Boot must copy random data from the Linux bootloader to the Linux kernel pre-reserved area. Once the entropy has been copied, then the bootloader will transfer the execution flow to the Linux kernel.

Therefore, E-Boot provides to the Linux bootloader entropy for itself but also for the Linux kernel. The memory space to hold the entropy of both must be pre-reserved in the bootloader. We have calculated that 32 bytes of entropy are enough for both, to solve entropy starvation and to offer enough randomness for all early random requests. The bootloader consumes

Figure 7.3: Implementation overview of the proposed e-boot in the linux kernel v5.3 for the x86_64 architecture.

16 bytes of entropy to assist kernel randomization step ③ in figure 7.3, and the Linux kernel consumes also 16 bytes of entropy to early start its internal CSPRNG, step ⑤ in figure 7.3.

To implement E-Boot, we have defined the pre-reserved area which consists of two main parts: 1) a header containing metadata information and 2) a buffer containing the random data, which will be referred to as the payload. The payload buffer is populated by the hypervisor when the virtual machine is loaded into memory. The header contains a 2-byte `magic` number and other two 1-byte fields for `flags` and for the `entropy_size`. The purpose of the magic number is to identify the pre-reserved area unambiguously, to avoid unwanted side effects. The flags field is used for two purposes: 1) to allow the guest to provide a hint to the hypervisor about the entropy preference (i.e., true or pseudo randomness) and 2) to allow the hypervisor to inform the guest that it supports E-Boot. The size field indicates how much random data has been placed in the buffer. We have ① modified two linker scripts [233] of the Linux source code, called `vmlinux.lds.S`, one for the boot-loader and another for the kernel. These scripts are mainly used to describe and control the memory layout of the generated Executable and Linkable Format (ELF) file, which is the file format used by the Linux kernel. The pre-reserved area is statically allocated within an ELF section of the images (boot-loader and kernel).

In order to provide the entropy to the guest virtual machine, as shown in step ② of figure 7.3, we have modified the Qemu Virtual Machine Monitor v4.2 [234]. After Qemu has loaded the guest `vmlinux` image file into memory, the E-Boot parses the file in order to find and fill the pre-reserved area of the bootloader. Before writing the random numbers, a magic number check is done by using the first field of the pre-reserved area header. This is to allow the hypervisor to know that the guest virtual machine is compatible with E-Boot. The second field in the header is one byte reserved for flags. Those flags are to pass information between the hypervisor and the guest virtual machines. For example, the first bit of the flags is set by the hypervisor to indicate that it supports E-Boot. This bit can be later checked by the virtual machine to know that it is running under a hypervisor supporting E-Boot. The second bit is used by the hypervisor to know whether the entropy requested must be from a true random number generator or from a CSPRNG. This bit is set at compile time and cannot be modified unless the `vmlinux` file is patched. The rest of the bits are unused. The third field of the header is the entropy size contained in the pre-reserved area payload. It is requested by the guest virtual machine at compile time. The hypervisor uses this value to know how many random numbers are being requested. If the provided entropy by the hypervisor is less than the requested, this size field will be updated accordingly, indicating how much actual entropy has been written in the pre-reserved memory area of the guest.

Once the hypervisor has completely updated the guest's pre-reserved area, it passes the execution control to the guest bootloader, which will decompress the kernel into a physical memory. If kernel randomization is enabled, the bootloader will calculate the physical and virtual addresses of the final kernel location. As shown in step ③ of figure 7.3, with E-Boot the kernel can use two 8-byte random values from the pre-reserved area and use them to calculate both random addresses, instead of generating a weak random number. Actually, our implementation performs an *XOR* of the provided random bytes with the little available entropy. This is to ensure that, if the hypervisor does not support E-Boot, the kernel randomization will be as good as before.

After calculating the final virtual and physical addresses, the Linux kernel is decompressed. The boot-loader parses the extracted (kernel) ELF file to move loadable segments to their corresponding address. E-Boot uses the same approach as the one followed in the bootloader.

It locates the pre-reserved area, step ④ of figure 7.3, and it transfers 16 random bytes from the pre-reserved area of the bootloader to the pre-reserved area of the Linux kernel. Then, the bootloader updates the flags and transfers the execution control to the Linux kernel.

At the very first moment the kernel starts its execution, the random numbers are already available in its pre-reserved area and ready to use. As described in section 7.2.2, Linux implements a CSPRNG based on the ChaCha20 [141] cipher, which needs 128 bits of entropy to initialize it. For this reason, as step ⑤ of figure 7.3 shows, E-Boot provides 16 bytes (128 bits) of random data, to be able to early initialize the Linux CSPRNG. Doing an early CSPRNG initialization not only solves the problem of entropy starvation but it also satisfies all hardening techniques employed during the kernel boot time. The left-hand column of the table B shows a full list of the components and techniques that are benefited from the proposed E-Boot. Note that any future technique, even techniques with high demand on high-quality random numbers at very early stages, will be completely satisfied thanks to the early CSPRNG initialization done by E-Boot, as step ⑥ of figure 7.3 shows.

To preserve full compatibility with hypervisors not supporting E-Boot, the random data is actually mixed with the kernel's internal entropy pool. This will ensure that the CSPRNG will have the same behavior when no entropy is provided to guest virtual machines. As detailed in the following section, the overhead of this operation is negligible.

To summarize, we define two statically allocated E-Boot sections for both the kernel and the boot-loader. The hypervisor provides the required random data prior to virtual machine start-up. The random data payload size in our implementation is 32 bytes, which are used for kernel randomization and CSPRNG initialization. However, this is completely customisable. In this case, the boot-loader consumes 16 bytes for kernel randomization and transfers another 16 bytes to the kernel.

7.9 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate how effective E-Boot is for solving the boot-time entropy starvation problem in Linux. Table B in appendix B shows all boot-loader and Linux kernel components that are addressed by the proposed E-Boot. Later, we evaluate the spatial and temporal overhead to demonstrate its feasibility on real systems. At the end of the section, the NIST Statistical Test Suite is used to assess the entropy generation in guests.

To obtain the real impact of E-Boot, we have performed a comprehensive analysis of the Linux kernel v5.3 boot process (for the x86_64 architecture) to ascertain all the kernel components that require random data in early stages, identifying the cases in which there is insufficient quality entropy available when these requests are made. Since Linux requires 128 bits (16 bytes) to initialize its CSPRNG, we will refer to “sufficient entropy” when Linux has collected 128 bits or more of high-quality entropy. Otherwise, we will refer as “insufficient entropy”, since the CSPRNG will not be able to initialize and all requests to its CSPRNG during the boot time will not be satisfied.

The experiments were carried out running an Arch Linux virtual machine with kernel v5.3, LXDE graphical desktop and full networking (NAT mode provided by Qemu). It executes only basic init-system processes and an SSH server. The physical machine used to run the experiments has an Intel Xeon W-2155 processor (Skylake server microarchitecture) and 32 GiB of SDRAM memory. The hypervisor used is KVM (Linux kernel 4.19-lts) along with Qemu v4.2.0.

Figure 7.4: Chronology of the kernel components requiring entropy at early boot-time, comparing availability of quality entropy with Standard, virtio-rng and E-Boot.

Table B in appendix B shows a list of Linux kernel functions requiring early random data while there is not enough entropy as to initialize the CSPRNG. As explained in section 7.2.2, the CSPRNG needs at least 128 bits of true random data to be initialized. By annotating all the requests that are made to the CSPRNG before it is ready, we have identified a total of 33 kernel functions that are affected by the lack of quality entropy with a standard Linux compilation. When E-Boot is used, all random data requests by those 33 functions are satisfied and the starvation problem is addressed.

In order to assess the effectiveness of our implementation, we compare E-Boot with current state-of-the-art alternatives that provide entropy to the kernel, considering the worst and best-case scenarios. On the one hand, we consider a *standard* kernel without any other entropy source than OS external events as the worst-case scenario. The reason is that although true randomness obtained by OS external events is a basic and built-in entropy source available in any standard Linux kernel, it takes a while to produce enough quality entropy solely with this source. This is because it is slow and unable to produce large streams of random bits in a short period of time. In our experiments up to 4 minutes as shown in Figure 7.4. This chronology has been obtained by recording the time at which each of the requests occurs throughout the boot process.

On the other hand, the current recommended approach to relax boot-time entropy starvation situations is to use virtio-rng as a virtual HRNG. Virtio-rng is able to provide fast-rate streams of random data to guest virtual machines, and therefore initialize the CSPRNG long before that the standard Linux. Hence, virtio-rng can be considered as the best-case scenario. It is important to note that virtio-rng can be compiled as a loadable kernel module or built-in. Although the default option is to compile it as a module, we have built virtio-rng as built-in to have it available as soon as possible during the kernel boot process. Therefore, we are comparing E-Boot against the best case of the best available solution.

The experiments results are summarized in the table B in appendix B. The three last columns indicate which solution provides entropy for each random data request. From the total of 33 affected kernel functions, virtio-rng is able to provide entropy earlier than standard, fixing the last 12 cases (36.36%), but there are still 21 being affected because of the insufficient entropy available. The reason is that virtio-rng needs the kernel to be initialized prior to be

ready to supply random data. Therefore, kernel components needing entropy before that point are unable to benefit from it. An example is kernel randomization, which needs entropy just one millisecond after the kernel starts. In contrast, our solution addresses all of them (100%) because it is able to provide the needed entropy from the very beginning, including components requiring entropy in the boot-loader before Linux starts.

Figure 7.4 represents a chronology of boot-loader and kernel execution time. It shows kernel components requiring entropy at early boot-time, along with important events as the kernel initialization and the moment that virtio-rng is ready. It is important to note that, in this figure, kernel functions have been grouped into components for sake of clarity and only the first request is represented. For example, `Userland Stack Protector & ASLR` consists of several kernel functions (`arch_rnd()`, `create_elf_tables()`, etc.). Also, time count is reset when the kernel is executed because they are two different execution environments.

With the standard configuration, the kernel is not able to generate enough quality entropy until after more than 4 minutes (245 seconds in average). To illustrate the example presented in section 7.6, we have measured the start-up time of OpenSSH v8.1. Our experiments showed that the SSHd server was around 4 minutes blocked in the `getrandom()` system call (244 seconds in average), and did not start accepting incoming connections until then. Both E-Boot and virtio-rng effectively remove this delay, because when the random requests from SSH arrive (at 1500 ms) both virtio-rng and E-Boot have initialized the CSPRNG, and therefore the userspace entropy requests were successfully satisfied. Consequently, user experience is considerably improved, since they can use those userland services as soon as the system boots, without having to wait more than 4 minutes to the CSPRNG initialization.

Although in userspace applications there is not much difference between using virtio-rng or E-Boot, virtio-rng is not able to provide entropy to bootloaders or initialize the CSPRNG at early stages of the Linux boot process. As shown in figure 7.4, virtio-rng is only able to provide entropy approximately after 360 ms, and therefore is not able to provide entropy to previous Linux components requiring it. Table B shows the detailed list of those components. In our experiments 63.63% of the functions were not satisfied by virtio-rng when it was compiled as a built-in, but this number reached 75.75% when it was compiled as a module.

7.9.1 Spatial Overhead

E-Boot introduces a negligible spatial overhead. The code added to the Linux kernel is simple and small. The pre-reserved areas increase the size of the generated kernel image file. The increment is caused by the addition of the E-Boot section in both images, boot-loader and kernel, which are statically allocated. This overhead is the sum of the header (4 bytes) plus the number of random bytes required.

Table 7.3 shows the spatial overhead in bytes. In our implementation, we use 36 bytes for the boot-loader (4 bytes for the header + 32 for random data) and 20 bytes for the E-Boot area of the Linux kernel (4 bytes for the header + 16 for random data). Note that the bootloader does not consume the 32 bytes but it contains the 16 bytes of random data of the Linux kernel.

The spatial overhead of the boot-loader is 68 bytes, including the 36 bytes of the E-Boot area. The overhead of the implementation is 316 bytes for the kernel image, including the 20 bytes of the E-Boot area. Therefore, the total spatial cost of the E-Boot areas including the code necessary to implement the E-Boot is 440 bytes, which is less than 0.01% of overhead.

Table 7.3: Spatial overhead of the proposed E-Boot with a total of 32 random bytes of random data provided by the hypervisor to be used by the Linux boot-loader and kernel.

Image	Size (bytes)		
	Standard	E-Boot	Overhead
Linux Kernel	58424752	58425088	336
Linux Boot-loader	8817272	8817376	104
Compressed bzImage	8999808	8999808	0

Although the overhead is negligible, we implemented E-Boot within the `init` sections to ensure that the memory is freed after the kernel is booted. Therefore, the actual memory overhead when Linux is running is zero.

7.9.2 Temporal Overhead

The temporal overhead introduced by E-Boot is almost negligible. Our experiments showed that $2 \mu\text{s}$ is the total time overhead when we add the boot-loader and the kernel overhead introduced by E-Boot.

The temporal overhead introduced by E-Boot slightly affects the latency of the virtual machine start-up, including the hypervisor and the guest kernel. However, once the guest is booted, the run-time cost is zero, since the code and the memory used are freed. The implementation of E-Boot introduces overhead in the following parts. 1) In the hypervisor, when it parses the guest image file to locate the E-Boot section. 2) In the hypervisor, when it populates the pre-reserved area with random data. 3) In the boot-loader, when it accesses to the pre-reserved memory region containing the random values to load two 8-byte values for kernel randomization. 4) In the boot-loader, after kernel decompression the kernel image file is parsed to locate its E-Boot section. 5) In the boot-loader, when it copies the remaining entropy to the kernel pre-reserved memory region. 6) Finally, in the kernel, when it accesses to the 16 random bytes to feed its internal CSPRNG.

Table 7.4: Detailed temporal overhead of the E-Boot implementation (in nanoseconds).

Order	Description	Hypervisor/ Bootloader/ Kernel	Overhead (ns)
1	Parse the boot-loader image to locate its E-Boot pre-reserved area.	H	492
2	Fill with random data, using <code>getrandom()</code> system call.	H	733
3	Load two 8-byte random values for kernel randomization (first use case).	B	91
4	Parse the kernel image to locate its E-Boot pre-reserved area.	B	482
5	Copy remaining 16 bytes from boot-loader to kernel's E-Boot.	B	163
6	Load 16 bytes of random data for kernel's entropy pool (second use case).	K	90
TOTAL:			2051

After running one million different executions of each of the above parts, as table 7.4 shows, we obtained a total overhead of about $2 \mu\text{s}$. The hypervisor overhead is around $1.2 \mu\text{s}$ and for

the guest is around 826 ns. The kernel only performs a simple load and write operation and its overhead is 90 ns. Therefore, we can conclude that the total temporal overhead introduced by E-Boot is negligible.

7.9.3 Entropy Assessment

In virtualization technologies, the hypervisor must be trusted by design. Likewise, E-Boot relies on the hypervisor's ability to provide quality entropy through the pre-reserved area. Consequently, it is the hypervisor's responsibility to ensure the quality of the entropy provided. However, the design of E-Boot contemplates the scenario where the hypervisor cannot provide entropy to their guests. The guests will use the entropy provided by the hypervisor only if the hypervisor set the proper flag that will be later read by the virtual machine.

Therefore, there is no risk or necessity to assess the entropy generated by the hypervisor. In our implementation we use the entropy provided by E-Boot directly to feed the CSPRNG of Linux. To ensure that this process is correct and we are not introducing any weakness into the CSPRNG of Linux, we have assessed its output using the NIST Statistical Test Suite (STS) [235].

Table 7.5: NIST statistical tests results showing the p-values and the proportion of passing sequences, with a significance level $\alpha = 0.01$. The total data size is 2.91 GiB, consisting of 1000 samples of $25 * 10^6$ random bit-streams each. To pass a test, the p-value must be at least α , and the proportion of passing sequences must be at least 0.980.

Statistical Test	P-value	Pass Rate	Assessment
Frequency	0.897763	0.990	PASSED
Block Frequency	0.536163	0.991	PASSED
Cumulative Sums	0.905546	0.991	PASSED
Runs	0.319084	0.992	PASSED
Longest Run	0.371941	0.984	PASSED
Rank	0.864494	0.993	PASSED
Discrete Fourier Transform	0.363593	0.991	PASSED
Non-Overlapping Template	0.190726	0.990	PASSED
Overlapping Template	0.016261	0.993	PASSED
Universal	0.253122	0.994	PASSED
Approximate Entropy	0.614226	0.991	PASSED
Random Excursions	0.075354	0.990	PASSED
Random Excursions Variant	0.519006	0.989	PASSED
Serial	0.089620	0.992	PASSED
Linear Complexity	0.707513	0.989	PASSED

The null hypothesis is that the Linux random number generator in the guest virtual machines is working correctly after seeding it with the E-Boot provided entropy. The aim for this test is

to ensure that E-Boot is not introducing any weakness in the generation of random numbers through the CSPRNG. To perform this test, we have executed 1000 virtual machine instances providing different random values in the pre-reserved area. After seeding and initializing the guest random number generator, we extracted 25 million of random bits from each virtual machine execution.

Table 7.5 presents the empirical results of the NIST's STS, showing that all tests were passed successfully and confirming the null hypothesis. P-values of different sub-tests (e.g., Non-Overlapping Template) have been combined using the Fisher's method [236]. The obtained results confirm that E-Boot is not introducing weaknesses in the guest's randomness generation.

7.10 Conclusions

In this chapter, we analyzed the boot-time entropy starvation problem and how it affects bootloaders, operating systems and userspace applications. We analyzed the Linux kernel boot process, revealing that the problem not only affects userland applications but up to 33 kernel functions were weakly fed by random numbers.

To overcome this problem, we proposed E-Boot, a novel technique that provides high-quality random numbers to guest virtual machines. E-Boot is the first technique that completely satisfies the entropy demand of virtualized boot-loaders, early boot stages of operating systems and userland applications.

We have implemented E-Boot in Linux v5.3 and our experiments showed that it effectively solves the boot-time entropy starvation problem. Our proposal successfully feeds boot time Linux kernel hardening techniques and also reduces to zero the number of userspace blocks and delays. The evaluation results showed that the total time overhead introduced by E-Boot is around $2 \mu\text{s}$ and has zero memory overhead since the memory is freed before the kernel boot ends, which makes E-boot a practical solution for cloud systems.

Conclusions

General Conclusions

Cloud computing relies on multiple technologies to provide cost-effective solutions. This thesis discussed that despite the effort and work that is being done in cloud computing technologies, there are still challenging problems to combine them with security solutions. Consequently, either the efficient use of resources is sacrificed for the sake of user protection, or security is sacrificed for greater profit.

The research presented in this thesis contributes to overcoming these problems by providing novel solutions that enable the use of cost-effective technologies without detriment of security, allowing the reduction of costs and thus increasing the profitability of the existing resources. Hence, `SLicedup` enables the utilization of memory deduplication in multi-tenant cloud environments, offering memory sharing benefits for cloud infrastructure providers while preventing side-channel attacks among different tenants.

In addition, we enhance the protection and extend the performance of security mechanisms by adding support and compatibility with such cost-effective technologies, so that cost reduction is significantly more effective whilst maintaining strong levels of security. `KASLR-MT` provides full coarse-grained and fine-grained kernel randomization protection for the kernels while being compatible with memory deduplication, which allows to increase the effectiveness of this memory saving technique and, consequently, to reduce overhead in terms of memory consumption.

On the other hand, to ensure and strengthen the correct functioning of important kernel security mechanisms in guest virtual machines, we also provide efficient solutions to enable the deployment of virtual machines in environments with a high availability of high-quality entropy from the beginning of its execution, which is a critical stage where long-term security systems are initialized, as well as boosting their boot time. `E-Boot` is the first technique that completely satisfies the entropy demand of virtualized boot-loaders at early stages of the boot process, effectively solving the boot-time entropy starvation problem efficiently and with a negligible overhead.

In conclusion, all the objectives established at the beginning of the PhD have been accomplished successfully. The combination of `SLicedup`, `KASLR-MT` and `E-Boot` offers important advantages to the efficiency of environments based on virtualization technologies such as multi-tenant cloud computing systems. Thereby, we provide practical, efficient and scalable solutions, applicable to both present and future technologies to solve real world problems.

Directions for Future Work

There is still more research to be done on mitigating some of the barriers behind security mechanisms to make them effectively usable and deployable by suppliers and customers. Some possible directions of future work include:

- Exploration of the concrete effects and consequences that memory encryption has on memory consumption in cloud environments. After the experimentation and knowledge obtained from the research on this thesis, we know that the mechanisms that potentially alter memory contents have a high impact on the shareability of the memory. Although memory encryption is a valuable feature for safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of contents, it introduces new challenges for significant mechanisms such as memory deduplication.
- Research about mitigating the runtime performance hit for fine-grained address randomization. There is a need for solutions that allow the security benefits to be maximally preserved while reducing runtime performance hits to acceptable levels. Many challenging factors have to be taken into account such as the degradation of runtime latency by the appearance of cache misses, or the potential degradation of the protection provided by the security mechanism itself in pursuit of fixing its performance hit, such as the inclusion of information leaks or side-channels.

Final Words

This thesis has been completed in three years. During this challenging period of time, I have worked hard to meet the objectives set at the beginning of the PhD, discussing several thoughts and ideas and continuously learning whilst exploring new horizons of knowledge.

It is not straightforward to do research in this field for several reasons such as its constantly fast-changing nature due to the ongoing struggle against attackers that are always ahead and the vast amount of specialized knowledge and sensitive aspects that need to be taken into account when dealing with low-level security mechanisms. An example of this is that the address randomization technique was initially proposed as a temporary solution to mitigate attacks based on prior knowledge of memory addresses until finding an appropriate defense against the used exploitation techniques such as code reuse. Today, after almost 20 years, this technique is not only still used but it is one of the fundamental defenses, both in userspace and in the kernel.

With this work, I have taken a few more steps towards the ambitious goal of building effective and efficient defense mechanisms, in order to make them more affordable and widely deployed. However, there is still a long way to go. I expect that in a foreseeable future, the currently advantageous scenario for attackers will be reversed to finally enjoy fully reliable and secure cloud systems for a better quality of life.

Appendices

A Impact of standard KASLR on the shareability of Linux memory regions

This appendix shows the analysis results of the impact that standard kernel randomization has on the shareability of the Linux kernel memory regions, referenced in Chapter 5. A black dot (●) indicates that the randomization element is enabled, while a white dot (○) indicates that the randomization element is disabled. The table is divided into six kernel memory regions.

Continued on next page.

B Kernel components requiring entropy at early phases of the boot process

Table A.7: List of Linux (v5.3) boot-loader and kernel functions called at boot time while there is insufficient quality entropy as to initialize the CSPRNG, comparing Standard, Virtio-RNG and E-Boot. The *At* column shows the first occurrence of each kernel function (in milliseconds). A tick (✓) means that there is enough quality entropy available when the corresponding function is reached.

[†]Note that this is the elapsed time since the bootloader started its execution, but the count is reset when the kernel gains control.

[‡]Random secret hash seeds are typically used to obtain an uniformly key distribution and to mitigate algorithmic complexity attacks against hash tables.

Kernel Function	Random Data Request			Description	Quality Entropy Available at Boot Time		
	At (ms)	Bootloader/ Kernel/User	Affected Component		Standard	Virtio-RNG	E-Boot
kaslr_get_random_long()	162 [†]	B	Kernel ASLR	Randomize kernel's physical and virtual addresses.	✗	✗	✓
kaslr_get_random_long()	1	K	Kernel ASLR	Randomize physmap, vmalloc and vmemmap memory regions and the poking address.	✗	✗	✓
add_to_free_area_random()	78	K	Page Allocator	When page allocator's freelist is randomized, this function randomly decides where to insert a new element (head,tail).	✗	✗	✓
cache_random_seq_create() shuffle_freelist()	85	K	Slab Allocator	Randomization of the slab allocator's freelist order to reduce its predictability, protecting against heap overflow exploits.	✗	✗	✓
kmem_cache_open()	88	K	Slab Allocator	Get a random value to harden the slab cache metadata against common freelist exploit methods, such as kernel heap attacks.	✗	✗	✓
init_espfix_random()	88	K	Memory Manager	Randomize the locations of kernel espfix, which protects against leaking high bits of the kernel stack pointer.	✗	✗	✓
boot_init_stack_canary()	89	K	Kernel Stack Protector	Set up a random kernel stackprotector canary value for the idle task (<i>a.k.a.</i> swapper).	✗	✗	✓
dup_task_struct()	92	K	Kernel Stack Protector	Set up a random kernel stackprotector canary value for a new process or thread.	✗	✗	✓
shuffle_zone()	92	K	Page Allocator	Page allocator's freelist is shuffled to improve cache utilization and to mitigate attacks exploiting its predictability.	✗	✗	✓
bucket_table_alloc()	93	K	Resizable Hash Tables	Set up a per-bucket random secret hash seed. [‡]	✗	✗	✓
setup_net()	93	K	Network Namespaces	Set up a random secret hash seed. [‡]	✗	✗	✓
kcmp_cookies_init()	93	K	Checkpoint / Restore	Get a random value to obfuscate pointers. This is done to prevent information leakage about locations of kernel objects.	✗	✗	✓
neigh_get_hash_rnd()	183	K	Neighbouring Subsystem	Set up an array of random secret hash seeds. [‡]	✗	✗	✓
rt_genid_init()	183	K	Network Namespaces	Set up a per-device random counter, used for routing purposes.	✗	✗	✓
key_alloc_serial()	308	K	Key Retention Subsystem	Allocate a random serial number for a key. This is used to avoid potential security issues through covert channels.	✗	✗	✓

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Table A.7 – Continued from previous page

Kernel Function	Random Data Request		Affected Component	Description	Quality Entropy Available at Boot Time		
	At (ms)	Bootloader/ Kernel/User			Standard	Virtio-RNG	E-Boot
arch_rnd()	312	K	Userland ASLR	Randomization of a process's memory mapping.	X	X	✓
randomize_stack_top()	312	K	Userland ASLR	Randomization of a process's stack top-address.	X	X	✓
arch_align_stack()	312	K	ASLR & Performance	Intra-page randomization of a process's stack, to avoid cache evictions by other processes when using Hyper-Threading.	X	X	✓
vdso_addr()	312	K	Userland ASLR	Randomization of a process's vdso.	X	X	✓
create_elf_tables()	312	K	Userland Stack Protector	Generate the rnd value in the ELF aux. vector (AT_RANDOM), used for stackprotector canary value and pointer mangling.	X	X	✓
arch_randomize_brk()	312	K	Userland ASLR	Randomization of a process's heap.	X	X	✓
ipv6_regen_rndid()	645	K	Networking (IPv6)	Generate a randomized interface identifier	X	✓	✓
init_oops_id()	645	K	Log & Debug	Generate a 64-bit random ID for oopses.	X	✓	✓
prandom_seed_full_state()	645	K	General-Purpose PRNG	Use the CSPRNG to seed the kernel's internal equidistributed combined Tausworthe PRNG (prandom) .	X	✓	✓
get_module_load_offset()	750	K	Kernel ASLR	Randomize the starting load address of modules. A random offset is settled when the first module is loaded.	X	✓	✓
urandom_read()	800	U	Several Processes	Non-blocking requests from different userland processes such as graphical manager, systemd and dbus-daemon.	X	✓	✓
generate_random_uuid()	805	K	Boot-ID	Generate a random Boot-ID. This UUID is exposed in the file /proc/sys/kernel/random/boot_id.	X	✓	✓
getrandom()	912	U	SSH & Systemd	Blocking requests from systemd-random-seed and SSHd userland processes, waiting until CSPRNG is ready.	X	✓	✓
addrconf_dad_kick()	1770	K	Networking (IPv6)	Get a random nonce for each IPv6 address for Duplicate Address Detection (DAD).	X	✓	✓
net_secret_init() ts_secret_init()	1800	K	Networking (Core)	Each function generates a random 128-bit secret key, both used for the kernel's SipHash implementation.	X	✓	✓
inet_ehashfn()	1800	K	Networking (TCP/IP)	Set up a random secret hash seed.‡	X	✓	✓
flow_hash_from_keys()	4785	K	BPF Flow Dissector	Set up a random secret hash seed.‡	X	✓	✓
__prandom_timer()	42048	K	General-Purpose PRNG	Seed the kernel's PRNG (prandom) periodically.	X	✓	✓

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